

“The Impact of Corporate Social Responsibility on Financial Performance: An Evidence from the Pakistani Banking Sector.”

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Abstract.

This investigation has focused to study corporate social responsibility (CSR) and its impact on financial performance of Pakistani retail banks. CSR is a popular practice by many organisations in developed countries. The concept of corporate social responsibility has evolved in the last few decades (Carroll, 1999). However, the concept is relatively new in developing countries like Pakistan. Corporate social responsibility (CSR) has been defined as the level of ethical accountability that possibly will be recognized by organisations ahead of uncomplicated compliance to the rules and regulations of the government (Kilcullen & Kooistra, 1999). Many researchers have studied about CSR relationship with financial performance but there are only a few studies in the context of developing countries. Therefore, this investigation fills the gap. There are different definitions and theories of corporate social responsibility included in the study. For example, stakeholder's theory and agency theory. Numerous researchers argue that an organisation can attain advantages by engaging with societal activities (Idowu & Pappasolomou, 2007). There are several reasons and motivations behind an organisation participating in CSR. Some organisations engage with societal activities to have a good impression in the perception of customers, investors and suppliers. Moreover, some scholars support the positive relationship between CSR and financial performance while some do not agree with it. Few researchers support the U-shaped relation between CSR and FP. One of the popular theories on the CSR pyramid was presented by Carroll (1991). The pyramid has four elements which are philanthropic, ethical, environmental and economic responsibilities. These responsibilities are constructed and linked with each other. Each responsibility in a CSR pyramid is giving support to other responsibilities. The conceptual framework of this investigation was constructed based on the CSR pyramid. The researcher used a mixed method approach and stratified sampling technique to collect data. The researcher used SPSS and NVivo software to analyse the data. The results indicated that there is a positive correlation amongst CSR and financial performance of Pakistani banks.

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This one is for you my Ibbi.

Mahwish Noor

DECLARATION.

This thesis is the fulfilment for the requirement Doctorate of Business Administration (DBA) for University of West of the Scotland. This research is not previously submitted for any degree and it is the result of my own independent work.

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List of Abbreviations.

CSR- Corporate social responsibility
CFP- Corporate Financial performance
FP- Financial performance
GDP- Gross Domestic Product
ROA- Return on Assets
ROE- Return on Equity
EPS- Earnings per Share
UBL- United Bank Limited
MCB- Muslim Commercial Bank
NBL- National bank Limited
ABL- Allied bank limited
UNDP- United Nation Development Programme
HDI- Human Development Index
WHO- World Health organisation
PSL- Pakistan Super League
GBG- Green Banking Guidelines
OSF- Omair Sana Foundation
SUIT- Sindh Institute of Urology Transplant

1 Chapter One.

1.1 Introduction.

Corporate social responsibility (CSR) is one of the elemental strategies practice by numerous successful organisations in twenty-first century (Horrigan, 2010; Min-Dong, 2008; Timbate & Park, 2018). Societal issues are increasing in many developing countries and the expectation of consumers from organisations is to employ their resources to help and minimise these dilemmas (Gigauri, 2012; Malik & Nadeem, 2014). Corporate social responsibility is considered as an industry itself because there is no foremost organisation's strategy is complete without declaration on corporate social responsibility (Musafer, 2012). An organisation can increase its productivity and enhance their financial performance by complying CSR as a part of organisational strategy. It has been noticed that one of the foremost challenges confronted by different business globally is CSR (Hopkins, 2003).

The concept of CSR is one of the argumentative concerns in the field of management as well as in modern business world. The sustainability of business and environment in competitive businesses vastly depends on proficiency of economical administration function (Bagh, et al., 2017). In today's world, societies are demanding from organisations to participate and get more involved for the progression of society (Belal & Momin, 2009). Corporations are making efforts to understand the concept of CSR with the intention of generating social value a head of prosperity growth by means of profit (Yang, et al., 2010). CSR is not considered as a cost by organisations but an investment in present era (Wibisono, 2007). The notion of CSR practiced by many multinational organisations and their financial performance are increasing as compared to those corporations who are not participating in CSR (Bagh, et al., 2017; Poddi, et al., 2009).

While there is a growing importance of CSR internationally, many organisations do not believe and invest in CSR. Particularly, in context of developing countries CSR is less practiced and Pakistan is no exception. The country is facing different challenges nationally and internationally because of various reasons like weak organisation and dishonest or corrupt practices (Bagh, et al., 2017). Organisations in Pakistan are generating profits, however their participation for society is limited and their focus on societal concerns is the least.

Several investigations have advocated the advantages of CSR and its significance on business performance (Brik, et al., 2011; Carroll & Shabana, 2010; Wang, et al., 2016; Lindgreen, et al., 2009). In order to improve the consistency of CSR practice and to enhance organisational performance it is important to investigate the factors related to CSR. This study thus focuses on the corporate social responsibility and the impact of CSR on the financial performance of Pakistani Banks. The banking sector is selected by researcher because it is considered as main player in economy of Pakistan and the importance of banks cannot be overlooked. This is the introductory chapter of the research, which provides an idea and guidance to the reader about the nature of the research. It also elucidates the research context setting, background, motivation behind study and the structure of the thesis. The following figure demonstrates an outline of the introduction chapter.

• Research Context Setting
• Background of the Research
• Purpose of the Study
• Statement of the Problem
• Rationale of the Research
• Research Objectives
• Research Questions
• Research Methodology
• Research Significance
• Structure of the Thesis
• Summary of Chapter

Figure 1: The map of the introduction chapter

1.2 Research Context Setting.

The researcher started this research with the previous knowledge in business administration. Preceding professional expertise provided understanding of the concept of corporate social responsibility and the issues with the implementation of CSR in Pakistan. The researcher has read a large number of articles about concerns related to CSR in developing countries specifically Pakistan which includes lack of awareness of the notion and lack of understanding of relationship between CSR and CFP. For instance, it has noticed that many companies in Pakistan are not making efforts to do something extra-ordinary for activities related to corporate social responsibility (Asfar, 2009). Similarly, one of the most reliable sources stated that in Pakistan CSR is approximately non-existent like it is in many other emerging countries (Jamshoro, 2013). The researcher has considered the element that organisations in emerging countries require some structure or mechanism for continued existence and the concept of CSR and CFP are essential for a long-term success of a firm. Consequently, corporate social responsibility can provide competitive advantage to firms in Pakistan.

It had become perceptible to the researcher that the concern of association amongst corporate social responsibility and financial performance is vital. On these grounds, there is an area of attention and the knowledge gap, therefore the researcher believed there was a requirement to study the impact of corporate social responsibility on financial performance in Pakistani banks. There are a number of organisations in Pakistan which are operating in different industries and sectors. However, the researcher has selected banking sector, because it operates as the backbone for an economy of a country. Banks plays an important role and are the centre for efficient functioning of financial activities nationwide and worldwide.

Moreover, there is a lack of literature in corporate social responsibility related to developing. Many organisations in Pakistan are working hard to make strategies and improve their financial performance. This research is of significance to firms by contributing to competitive strategy and it will be beneficial for the Pakistani organisations particularly banks. Furthermore, the study will provide researcher expertise and knowledge in the area of CSR which will be of great support in career development of the investigator. The personal involvement of the researcher in developing CSR strategy perceptions for banks in Pakistan and the acknowledgement of the knowledge gap encouraged the researcher to decide on this particular topic for investigation.

1.3 Background of the Research.

The above-mentioned paragraph provided the context and setting of the research in terms of researcher and the interest of chosen topic. This section of the study will present the background of the research related to the concept of corporate social responsibility. This investigation is concerned with the assessment and evaluation of the presence of corporate social responsibility (CSR) and its impact on the financial performance in Pakistani retail banks. Many researchers and scholars had investigated about the impact of CSR on FP but there are very few investigations in context of Pakistan (Bagh, et al., 2017). This research will fill the gap in identifying the presence of CSR and its impact on financial performance in Pakistani Banks. The background of the study comprises of a review of the concerns, the contemporary information about CSR in Pakistani banks and earlier studies on the issue.

When an organisation goes beyond the legal responsibilities to manage the impression, which they have on society, is called corporate social responsibility (Malik & Nadeem, 2014). It includes the interaction of an organisation with its customers, suppliers, employees and society.

“Corporate social responsibility is a commitment to improve community well-being through discretionary business practice and contribution of corporate resources” (Kotler & Lee, 2005, p. 3).

The main component of this definition is discretionary which focus on that firm must engage with CSR and be a part of the community voluntary but not because mandated by law.

Large organisations are encouraging corporate social responsibility and always behave socially. Nevertheless, it is hard to describe corporate social responsibility in both corporate and academic world (Malik & Nadeem, 2014). Many investigators and scholars have endeavoured to authenticate and to describe the precise description and definition of corporate social responsibility (Iqbal, et al., 2013). The decisions and deeds made by implement moderately beyond the companies direct financial advantage is acknowledged as CSR (Davis, 1960). The stakeholders of a company are regarded honourably and socially accountable way underneath the conception of CSR (Carroll, 1979; Hopkins, 1999; Malik & Nadeem, 2014).

Positive ethical capital can be generated by CSR amongst communities and stakeholders, this investment can give shareholders with security for an organisation's association-based intangible asset (Godfrey, 2005).

CSR has widely accepted and admired strategy by businesses around the world. Various organisations published reports on CSR and the demand of stakeholders is growing for business to assess these reports to make progress socially and economically. Several investigators and intellects have defined CSR in distinct manner. CSR is described as activities practice by a firm for the benefits of society without any legal pressure and primary profits of the firm (McWilliams & Siegel, 2001). The interaction of an organisation with employee, customers, suppliers and other stakeholders and the participation to ensure the fortification of the environment is part of CSR. It has become one of the business strategies and practiced by many organisations internationally. Organisations can attain advantages by practicing in societal activities and these benefits includes progression in financial performance (Kotler & Lee, 2005).

In this modern era, an organisation has to confront with several challenges and as consumers are well aware of different services and products, it becomes difficult to gain the competitive advantage. It creates for a firm to gain advantage over their competitors and attain improve financial performances by participating in corporate social responsibility. Although, in Pakistan, many organisations have less acquaintance of CSR activities and the crusade of CSR is few years old and not much recognized (Bagh, et al., 2017).

This study attempts to contribute to the literature in area of corporate social responsibility, which was studies by many scholars of developed countries. Although, the literature about the CSR in emerging country like Pakistan is relatively less. Moreover, this research also provides the further identifications of the factors related to CSR in Pakistani Banks.

1.4 Purpose of the Study.

Compared to developed countries, there are limited researches available in the developing world particularly in the context of Pakistan. Moreover, very few CSR related studies have focused on the banking sector. In order to fill the gap, the study is set to investigate the effect of CSR related factors on organisational financial performance. The study has chosen banking industry of Pakistan as an example of developing countries. The researcher has preferred and chosen Pakistan for this particular investigation because of several reasons. The first motivation behind the research is that there is a shortage of investigations in corporate social responsibility which can impact the financial performances of any organisation. Currently, there are few of the investigations taken place in the country which are associated with CSR but restricted to descriptions. Therefore, one of the main purposes of the study is to fill the gap by undertaking this investigation in context of Pakistan.

There are a number of banks in Pakistan which are listed in the Stock Exchange of Pakistan. These banks often make profits and performs well as it can be observed by reviewing the Stock Exchange rates. Many banks have taken the initiative by confronting the societal issues and participating in activities related to corporate social responsibility. Unpaid work, unethical practices and environmental concerns are some of the problems focused by banks to be part of the societal growth. But the law enforcement in the country is not strong and this lack of effective legal structure which can affect the implementation of corporate social responsibility. This research endeavours to comprehend the current CSR implementation in the retail banks of Pakistan and its impact of their financial performance.

Lastly, there are dearth of research in CSR in context of Pakistan and this research will fill the gap. The researcher also believes that if organisations in Pakistan take initiative and participate in CSR, it can bring positive change in society which will lead towards progress and growth of the country. Moreover, it is a moral accountability of the researcher to conduct a research which could be beneficial for the country, as the researcher belongs to Pakistan. This investigation will create some strategic suggestions and recommendations for the banks in Pakistan which has been a great motive for the researcher to select Pakistan for this study.

1.5 Statement of the Problem.

The notion of CSR is studied by many scholars and it comprises fundamental characteristics which are advantageous for the success and existence of an organisation. Although, most of the earlier investigations carried on the relationship of CSR and financial performance yet unexplored and indistinct which gave opportunity to researcher to perform one more study on this particular area (Wijesinghe & Senaratne, 2011). The concept of CSR has not still been explored in emerging countries like Pakistan (Bagh, et al., 2017) as it is in developed countries. Most of the organisation focus on increasing financial performance and many firms are not aware of the notion. Unlike developed countries, the concept of corporate social responsibility is new in Pakistan and mostly multinational firms in the country usually participate in CSR. In emerging countries, the place of corporate social responsibility is at early stage (Bagh, et al., 2017; Mujahid & Abdullah, 2014).

It is indicated by researchers that CSR has become one of the popular subject matter in previous few years. In business area, many organisations publish a report on corporate social responsibility alongside their annual reports (Malik & Nadeem, 2014). Now more social, economic and environmental advantages are demanded by different stakeholders or individual who impact an organisation. By considering the verity that emerging countries required to have some method for subsistence specifically if the firm is operating internationally. For the long run organisational success, the concept of corporate social responsibility and financial performance are crucial. Consequently, there is a matter of consideration and the knowledge gap. Pakistani banks are part of the society which can affect the economic situation of the country. Therefore, the researcher of this investigation believes that there is a requirement of this investigation which is the impact of corporate social responsibility on financial performance in Pakistani retail banks.

1.6 Rationale of the Research.

CSR includes the economic, legal, ethical and philanthropic activities by a firm to contribute to the society (Carroll, 1979). Activities, such as charity, donations, education, health, human rights, environment protection and employee's safety are part of corporate social responsibility (Crane & Matten, 2004). The main notion on which this study is focused is corporate social responsibility. In previous decades, the concept and definition of corporate social responsibility has evolved and different theories suggest different views. Some of the researchers were not in favour of CSR and suggested that a firm should not participate in activities related to CSR (Friedman, 1962). Whilst some were in favour of CSR and claims that an organisation should involve in societal activities. CSR has become a concern growing in disputing perspective that a firm should participate in societal activities. According to some researchers it is responsibility of an organisation to resolve social and environmental issues cause by them (Davis & Blomstrom, 1975; Carroll, 1979). Moreover, it is suggested that CSR can become cause of improved reputation of a firm with satisfied customers which can attract more investors and enhanced financial performance (Orlitzky, et al., 2003).

Whether an organisation should participate in corporate social responsibility and what are the main concerns in implementation of CSR are presented in this study. The literature review of the research will deal with the detailed theories and definition of the notion of CSR, overall and within the context of Pakistani banking sector. The issue of CSR is a moral issue which is based around the human cognition and perception. Specifically, in Pakistan, where the awareness of the notion of CSR is relatively less than developed countries.

Additionally, the association between corporate social responsibility and financial performance is the main focus of this particular investigation and therefore, numerous models and theories of CSR and financial performance are also presented in the study. The researcher has constructed conceptual framework of this research on the base of one of the famous models of CSR pyramid by Carroll (1999). The study presented the relationship of CSR and CFP in context of Pakistani retail banking sector. The stakeholder of an organisation plays vital role and have great impact on financial performance. Therefore, the researcher has divided ethical responsibilities further into employees, customers and environmental accountabilities. Additionally, the literature of the study also comprises CSR theories related to stakeholders.

The study investigates about the impact of CSR on CFP in Pakistani retail banking sector and the researcher used qualitative and quantitative method to gather data and then analysed it statistically. The research background, purpose, statement of problem and rationale leads to the research objectives which are presented in the following section.

1.7 Research Objectives.

The aim of the research is to explore the existing of corporate social responsibility by banks in Pakistan and to determine the relationship of CSR and financial performance.

In line of the above aim of the researcher will be focusing on achieving the following research objectives.

1. To analyse the current practice of corporate social responsibility in Pakistani banks.
2. To investigate the perception of Pakistani bank managers towards CSR.
3. To explore the impact of corporate social responsibility on financial performance of banks in Pakistan.
4. To offer recommendations for Pakistani Banks to encourage corporate social responsibility.

1.8 Research Questions.

The aim of the study entails that the following question is presented:

What are the current CSR practices in Pakistani retail banks and does CSR have impact on the financial performance of the banks?

The sub questions of the investigations are:

1. What are the current CSR activities practicing by banks in Pakistan?
2. What is the perception of Pakistani banks' managers towards corporate social responsibility?
3. Does corporate social responsibility have any impact on the financial performance of the Pakistani banks?

1.9 Research Methodology.

There are two diverse methodologies has used by the researcher which are descriptive and empirical surveys. In this research, the investigator has used two different methodology, which are descriptive and empirical surveys. The descriptive part includes secondary data, which was gathered from peered reviewed journals and articles. The information about the country with the detailed of financial performances of banks are also collected from the electronic resources like websites. The empirical survey comprises of questionnaires explores the comprehension of the top management executives of Pakistani banks. This investigation is based on qualitative and quantitative approach to answer the research question. The researcher used questionnaire-based surveys and structured interviews to collect the data. The research also contains secondary data which was gathered from peer reviewed journals, articles, books and authentic websites. The researcher used stratified sampling as a sampling technique. Moreover, SPSS and NVivo is used for analysation of data.

1.10 Research Significance.

This research contributes to the literature of corporate social responsibility. It also contributes to the CSR in developing countries specifically Pakistan. Different definitions of CSR are discussed with in several CSR theories. The emphasis of the study is on Pakistani banks and therefore the contribution of knowledge is made in context of the country. It also identifies the association amongst CSR and financial performances of Pakistani banks, which includes the analysation of return on assets, return on equity and earning per share. The research has made recommendation and implication for the management of Pakistani banks to create awareness about CSR which can result in positive impact on financial performance of the banks. It will be of significance to the policy makers of Pakistani banks to overcome the challenges and to ensure that CSR is implemented effectively. Inconclusion, this research is novel and contributes to knowledge because:

- It is one of the few researches on CSR impact on financial performances in Pakistani banking sector.
- Practicing managers and policy makers can overcome the challenges and implement CSR effectively.

- The research has social implications, with detail understanding about significance of CSR activities and presumed social behaviour.
- Findings should be of significance to similar developing countries.
- The research provides the new empirical evidence of practicing CSR and its relation to financial performance from developing country (which has different culture than western countries).

1.11 Structure of the Thesis.

The investigation has five chapters which are elucidated below:

Chapter 1: Introduction.

The first chapter is introduction of the investigation, which includes the background of the research. It also contains the research question, its aim and objectives with the scope of the study.

Chapter 2: Literature Review.

The second chapter of the thesis is one of the extensive parts of the investigation. It comprises of five parts. The first section elucidates the detail discussion about economic and social situation of Pakistan. The section shed light on the theoretical background of corporate social responsibility which includes definitions and evolution of CSR. The third part of the literature is about the theories of CSR which comprises of stakeholders theory, agency theory, legitimacy theory and CSR pyramid model. The fourth section demonstrates the literature related to the financial performance and corporate social responsibility. Last but not the least, final section of the literature review is about CSR and banks which elucidates position of CSR in developing countries and in banking sector.

Chapter 3: Conceptual framework.

This chapter is about conceptual framework which the researcher is constructed on the base of

CSR pyramid model (Carroll, 1991). It demonstrated relationship of CSR and financial performance in form of framework. The chapter also includes hypotheses which will be tested by researcher in later chapters.

Chapter 4: Research Methodology.

This chapter of the thesis focuses on the research methods, research design, data collection methods and sampling which is used to complete the investigation. The researcher used mixed methods approach to attain the data and the reasons behind using every strategy and approach is discussed in this chapter.

Chapter 5: Data Analysis and Presentation of the Result.

The researcher endeavoured to answer the research question and the objectives. This chapter demonstrates the results and finding of the investigation. It also includes the detailed descriptive statistics conducted by the researcher to analyse the results.

Chapter 6: Discussion, Recommendation and Implantation.

This chapter includes the discussion of the results and recommendation for Pakistani banks. Moreover, this chapter also comprises of the implementation and proposed strategy related to CSR for Pakistani retail banking sector.

Chapter 7: Limitation, Reflection and Conclusion.

The last chapter is the summary of research including the theoretical contribution of the research. It also discussed the limitation of the research with the suggestion for future research. It also includes the reflection of the researcher on the process of investigation and the conclusion of the study.

Figure 2 Map of the Research

(Author's work)

1.12 Summary of the Chapter.

Corporate social responsibility is widely accepted and practiced business strategy. Many organisations in developing countries are lacking behind in consistent practice of CSR. Pakistan is one of the emerging countries in which some organisations are practicing CSR while some companies are still struggling to comprehend the concept of CSR. This study is the investigation about the CSR and the impact of CSR on financial performance of Pakistani banks. The foremost aim of the research is to analyse the current CSR activities practicing by Pakistani banks. The study also focusses on the managers perception about CSR and CSR impact on financial performance.

There are several scholars have investigated about CSR in emerging countries but there are very few studies or investigations on corporate social responsibility in context of Pakistan. Hence, the research will fill the gap by contributing to the knowledge and providing literature in context of Pakistan. This chapter has elucidated the road map of the investigation. The qualitative and quantitative research approach is used in this research. The investigator has used descriptive and empirical research method which includes the survey and interview.

2 Chapter Two.

2.1 Literature Review.

2.1.1 Introduction.

This chapter of the research presents literature review which consist five parts. The background of the country is the first part of literature which involves socio-economic framework, legal framework and implementation of law in Pakistan. The political, social, economic situation is discussed in this section. The second section of this chapter is literature of corporate social responsibilities (CSR) which includes definition, evolution, benefits and criticism of CSR. The third section includes theories and models of CSR with their critical aspects. Theories related to financial impact on CSR are elucidated in fourth section. The fifth section of literature is about CSR in Pakistani banks. The aim of this chapter is to study the literature on CSR and the impact of CSR on FP and to explore the current practice of CSR in Pakistan.

2.1.2 Part one: Background of the country.

This section of the literature is focusing on the background of the country selected by the researcher. It discusses the social-economic context, legal framework, environmental performance and the non-governmental organisations' role of practising corporate social responsibility in Pakistan. It is essential to understand the background of the country, that makes a linkage between the topics (CSR impact on CFP) and the research question of the study (which focuses on Pakistan). This section plays an important role in this study and provides reader an insight of the context.

2.1.2.1 Socio-Economic Context of the Country.

There are few nations in the world have ironic history, the destiny of Pakistan has been formerly designed by its geography. India was one of the countries ruled by British for almost a century and in 1947, a part of the country become a separate independent nation called Islamic Republic of Pakistan. The ideology behind the partition of the country was that Muslims and Hindus have two distinct frequently incompatible approaches of life and consequently they cannot survive in one country. Pakistan means 'land of pure' which is the only country in the world to

have been formed in the name of Islam. In 1971, Pakistan had ethnic civil war that resulted in the separation of the East Pakistan and another sovereign country formed named as Bangladesh. At present Pakistan is a developing country and according to the Pakistan Economic Survey 2016-2017, it is the sixth largest population in the world, which is 199.1 million (Survey, 2017). The country is in South-Asia and spanning almost 796,095 square kilometres. India, China, Iran and Afghanistan are the neighbours of Pakistan and it has its coastline beside the Arabian Sea. The geographic location of the country gives a distinctive strategic benefit to the country as regards to emerging a local dealings or business association with Central Asia, China, Middle East and India. Islamabad, Karachi, Lahore, Peshawar and Quetta are the major cities of the country where Urdu is the national or official language (Lieven, 2011). In four provinces of the country, people also speak different languages like Sindhi, Panjabi, Pashto, Hindko, Balochi and Saraiki. The following figure illustrates the map of the country.

Figure 3 Map of Pakistan

Figure redacted for copyright reasons

According to Pakistan Bureau Statistics (2017), in Pakistan, there are 96.28% people are Muslim, 1.59% are Christian, 1.60 are Hindus, 0.22% are Qadiani, 0.25% are scheduled castes and 0.07% are others (Pakistan Bureau Statistics, 2017). Geographically Pakistan can be divided into three fundamental areas, which are northern highlands, the Indus River plains, and Baluchistan Plateau (Wynbrandt, 2009). Pakistan is economically not very strong country but the country's GDP grew at 4.7% in 2016 and expected to accelerate up to 5.2% in 2017 (AsianDevelopmentBank, 2017). Moreover, the third of population is poor in the country; around 60 million people are living below poverty line (Khan, 2016). According to World health organisation (WHO), life expectancy in Pakistan is approximately 66/68 in 2015.

The country has large number of available natural possessions other than its enormous functioning or working-age populace that provide a possible demographic advantage but causing a significant dare to people who make strategies in the establishment of occupation and sufficient societal facilities to the populace (Sajjad & Eweje, 2014). Nonetheless, the economy of the country is confronting with different crisis. The inflation is escalating, economic growth is deteriorating and the situation of law and order is also serious, it is challenging for nation to attain steadiness in economy and anticipated consequences. The above mention issues have effects on organisation' policy of corporate social responsibility in Pakistan. A number of organisations working under these circumstances endeavour for persistence instead participating in CSR activities, that might, rise their expense of operations. According to statistics an effectual financially viable strategy and strong structural modifications are required to attain sought after socio-economic development in the country. The GDP of the country in previous few decades demonstrates an instable trend in growth of the financial prudence of the country. Deficiency of electricity, insufficient monetary modifications, massive spending on war against extremism or terrorism, safety threats and monotonous ecological catastrophes have had devastating effects on the economy of Pakistan. In growth of any country electricity is vital and in Pakistan the energy deficiency causing huge hindrance in development. Many industries suffer due to the long hours shortage of power and it resulted in closure of industrial units of distinct businesses like textile and cotton ginning (Sajjad & Eweje, 2014). According to the Economic Survey of Pakistan (2013), the invested energy production capability in the country was 20,000 megawatts, however the genuine generation stays under the requirement, causing lengthy hours of electricity dearth. Thousands of workforces have to renounce their work in Pakistan because of the power shortage. The deficiency of electricity has cost the country around \$13.5 billion.

There are a number of substantial reasons for the power calamity in Pakistan which include ineffective management and insufficient corporate governance at government energy organisation, excessive losses of distribution and deficit of funding from the government (Planning Commission Of Pakistan , 2013). Another factor which is becoming hindrance in the development of Pakistan is escalating liabilities and inflation. The national debt of Pakistan is rising steadily that is Rs. 94,143 per citizen and 72.17% as GDP (National debt clocks, 2018). Nevertheless, without the fundamental structural modifications in sector of energy by the state or government of Pakistan, it is improbable to attain the anticipated or desired monetary consequences. On other hand, there is a huge amount of debt of Pakistan which made it challenging to assign adequate finances to societal activities. Several people in Pakistan are unemployed and confronting different problems like shortage of electricity and terrorism. Progression of an individual plays vital role in the development of a country. According to Statista, in Pakistan, the unemployment rate was 5.1% in 2007 and have reached to 5.9% in 2016 (Statista , 2018). It is also the fact that 40% of Pakistani are living in poverty that is 38.8% of the whole population of Pakistan, in which 54.6% poor population lives in rural areas whilst 9.4% in urban areas (Rana, 2016) . Moreover, the government of Pakistan is spending less on health and education. In the budget of 2017-2018, the government has allocated Rs. 902.7 billion for education which shows the increased amount from previous years but still the current spending on education in Pakistan is the lowermost in South Asia (Dawn, 2016; Tahir, 2017). Similarly, on health the spending of Pakistan is 0.6% of its GDP while Afghanistan and Iran are spending 6% of their GDP (Dawn, 2017). Moreover, the following figure shows GDP of Pakistan according to trading economics (2018).

Figure 4 Pakistan's GDP

Additionally, the population and fertility growth rate of the country is higher than other South Asian countries like Bangladesh and Nepal. Pakistan population is equivalent to 2.63% of the total world population (Worldometers, 2018). Moreover, the competitiveness and socioeconomic potential of the country is deteriorating gradually. For, instance, according to United Nation Development Programme, the human development index (HDI) of Pakistan is 0.550 and at present with the rank 147 (UNDP, 2018). In influential Global Competitiveness Index of World, Pakistan has improved its position by seven places but the performance remains secondary when competed the extent of anxiety and stress (Rana, 2017). The Global Competitiveness Report of 2017-2018 also recognises that one of the most challenging elements for doing business in Pakistan is corruption including incompetent bureaucracy, criminality and tax rates (Rana, 2017). It is also identified by analysts that the China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC) has helps the economy of Pakistan to improve its ranking on scale of Global competitiveness (Mourdoukoutas, 2017). The following table shows the selected years ranking of Pakistan in Global Competitiveness Index.

Table 1 Pakistan's Competitive Ranking

(Mourdoukoutas, 2017)

Table redacted for copyright reasons

The above discussion demonstrated the facts or statistic of the country but when it comes to corporate social responsibility in Pakistani organisations, it appears to be new concept for firms. However, numerous Pakistani organisations have formed unpleasant and adversative social and ethical impressions (Hussain-Khaliq, 2004; Huniche & Rahbek, 2006). Some of the organisations in the country like garment sector do not even pay minimum wage to the employee and often hire with temporary contract without societal benefits or claims (Lund-Thomsen, 2004). Furthermore, when it comes to the concerns about the environment, around 20% of the listed or registered organisations are becoming the cause of creating high pollution (Khwaja, 2012). Another example of less societal deed in Pakistan's organisation is leather

manufacturers, which was involved damaging the environment by creating water pollution (Lund-Thomsen & Nadvi, 2010). However, in Karachi, the authorities had closed six factories in distinct industrial areas because the organisations became unsuccessful to prove that they were not polluting the rivers (Bhatti, 2017). Furthermore, a number of telecommunication organisations are engaged in unscrupulous activity, which is deceiving consumers through advertising and promotion (Hasan, et al., 2011).

Similarly, many Banks in Pakistan are indicted of being disingenuous by promoting their product through advertising and formulating unethical ambiguous modifications in product. A report has shown that in 2009, the number of formal complaints to authorities, against unethical behaviour of Banks were 1608 (Zaidi, 2011). Several Pakistani organisations are also deceitful in paying taxes and involved in illegal fortifying profitable government contracts for example Marush International was entangled in tax evasion, forgery and also used fake documents for custom clearance for their consignments (Hayat, 2017).

The researcher has apprehended the impact of corporate social responsibility is very strong and it can also increase the profitability in the company but can be additional cost. Consequently, it is essential for an organisation to remain focus and keep finances into consideration before making any decision.

2.1.2.2 Legal framework of Pakistan

The legal framework in Pakistan has strong laws regarding protection of social and environmental organisational attributes for instance prevention from child labour and slavery (Fundamental rights and principles of policy, 2017). According to the article 17 in the constitution, every person has liberty to make an association whilst in article 25 preclude discrimination on bases of gender. Moreover, the provision of welfare, benefits of old age, consumers' rights and requirement of secure working conditions are clearly mention in the constitution (Article 9a, cited in (Fundamental rights and principles of policy, 2017)).

The legal framework for labour comes under control of Ministry of Labour and Manpower of Pakistan. There are different laws associated with labour rights, which includes acts like Punjab Industrial Relations Ordinance 2010 and the Bonded Labour System Abolition Act 1992. According to national law there is a prohibition of employment of children, where a child

means a person under age of fourteen (the Employment of Children Act 1991, cited in (NATLEX, 1991). Additionally, there are a number of laws, which focus on the allowances, self-assessment schemes, loans and security for employees (the Provincial Employees Social Security Ordinance 1965, cited in (PunjabLaws, 1965).

Furthermore, the national laws have covered the rights of consumers, which is associated with the unfair trade practice, false advertisements, services and concerns of consumers like price and quality of the product. For instance, it is mentioned in Consumer Protection Act 1995, that damage product is a responsibility of the producer or manufacturer of it. The Federal Government is main authority to ensure the implementation of consumer security laws within the country (IslamabadConsumerProtectionAct, 1995).

Similarly, when it comes to the fortification of the atmosphere, the legal system has included Environmental Protection Act 1997, which specified the prevention and control of pollution. According to this Act, organisations should arrange training programs and monitor arrangements for environmental management to safeguard the eco-system.

It is essential for Pakistani banks to comprehend and respect the legal frame-work of the country and should provide protection to the environment and customers. Several companies in Pakistan emphasis on the disclosure of fair-trade practice and societal activities but have less concern about the implementation of it. Any listed or register company has to disclose complete financial details like balance sheet, cash flow, in annual report of the company which is also called formal financial statement. Large organisations in Pakistan are accountable to follow the standards of ‘The international financial reporting’ whilst small and medium companies adhere to ‘accounting and financial reporting standards’. Security and exchange commission in Pakistan has established codes for the corporate governance for the safety and security of shareholders. It is ensured by the security and exchange that all listed or registered organisations, with more than 7 million capitals, divulge their financial information annually. The report also verifies and examines by different chartered accountants, works for the security and exchange, to maintain the standards. The organisations that do not meet the requirements of regulation are often have to confront with the legal charges. The main emphasis of the regulatory structure is on financial reporting of an organisation and less towards societal deeds or reporting of activities related to corporate social responsibility.

2.1.2.3 Implementation of laws

In Pakistan, the legal frameworks and legal acts are strong and have covered all the aspect regarding fortification of labours, atmosphere, customers, children and society but the implementation of these laws appears to be weak. The country has less attention towards environmental control and it has less efficient system for the protection of rights of consumers (Ahmad, 2006). Moreover, the government's focus on scrutinising on societal and environmental activities of organisations is very less which also demonstrates the deficiency of aptitude in government. Pakistan has some level of corruption and some companies do take benefits by having gratuitous indulgences from the authorities. According to the Transparency International, the biggest threat to the economy of the country is corruption. The organisation also presented the corruption index of all countries in which Pakistan scored 29% in 2014 (where 0 is highly corrupted and 100 is highly clean) (Idowu, 2016). It demonstrates that there is certain association between underdeveloped and corruption. One of the reasons behind the lack of interest of companies in activates related to corporate social responsibilities is depravity. Serval organisations in Pakistan are less interested in executing corporate social responsibility because of the insubstantial mechanism of implementing laws.

2.1.3 Part Two: Corporate social responsibility (CSR)

A number of scholars have noticed that a being good citizen can be seen as a virtuous and valuable corporate practice (Palacios, 2004). It is extensively acknowledged that a responsible organisation has to fulfil the crucial criterion of being a good corporate citizen (Carroll, 1991). The maintenance of the balance among the organisation's legal and social status is the focus of corporate citizenship (Goddard, 2005). Corporate citizenship is a particular structure that sheds different light on the responsibility of business because it focuses on the concept of society (Matten & Crane, 2005). Although, corporate citizenship seems significant but globalization has intensified the focus of business on transparency (Jamali & Mirshak, 2007).

In several organisations, the issues related to corporate social responsibility has increased. When Bowen published the seminal book called social responsibility of a business man in 1953, that was first formalised term of corporate social responsibility, referred CSR to the obligations of a businessperson (Falck & Heblich, 2007). Numerous authors have developed

the concept of corporate social responsibility after a decade later and since then the concept has been matter of significant exploration and discussion amongst both scholars and practitioners.

In 1950s, academic investigators and businesses begun exploring and studying to establish the relation between organisation and society (Carroll, 1999; Wu & Lin, 2014). Several scholars define CSR as an unobstructed accountability of the company, which consider its activity for the advancement of the society as a return (Carroll & Shabana, 2010) Furthermore, the legal and economic requirement has to be fulfilled by any organisation, which is involve with CSR activities for the societal development (Carroll & Buchholtz, 2011). Corporate social responsibility has huge influence on the ethical or moral standards of an organisation and also implementation of corporate social responsibility often, obtain valuable transformations or changes in a company (SANZO, et al., 2012) . In addition, in order to meet the expectancies of the consumers and stakeholder, it is significant for an organisation to practice activities related to CSR. The market value and competitive advantage of the organisation can also be increased by corporate social responsibility (Porter & Kramer, 2006).

Moreover, according to Fredrick (2006), the balance and social stability among stakeholders of the organisation can be maintain by instigating activities related to corporate social responsibility (Palihawadana, et al., 2016). Several investigators have brought up the light on the basic role of the CSR is to contest to minimize the destitution among the people of any country. Any company executing the activities related to CSR, can make its brand image strong with good sales and productivity and also intensify the association with society. Financial performance of any organisation is one of the things, which can have great impact of CSR activities (Neville, et al., 2005). Corporate social responsibility has four distinct elements, which includes legal, ethical, economic and philanthropic responsibilities (Carroll, 1999). Carroll (1991), acknowledged that it is advantageous for any company to maintain the balance among these responsibilities which is to fulfil them equivalently (Harzing & Pinnington , 2015). Several organisations invest to initiate CSR such as charity and programs for enhancement of customers and employees benefit (Sprinkle & Maines, 2010; Lee, et al., 2018). Additionally, reduced cost and enhanced operational process can be achieved by an organisation involved with societal activities (Sprinkle & Maines, 2010).

Moreover, balancing the existing stakeholder and social prerequisites with those of future became indispensable for the businesses (Hildebrand, et al., 2011). Stakeholders are the part of the organisation's network and relationship; therefore, it is important to communicate the corporate social responsibility activities of the organisation. (Lindgreen, et al., 2009). Legal and economic responsibilities are not the only obligations for an organisation but also ethical which consist of range of cultural norms (Carroll, 2000).

In contrast, corporate social responsibility is also comprehended as a strategic apparatus to attain the economic purposes and enhance the financial performance (Garriga & Melé, 2004). Furthermore, it can be possible for an organisation to upset stakeholders by engendering less profit whilst engaging with social activities (Blowfield & Frynas, 2005).

Moreover, financial impact of CSR is one of the aspects which is famous amongst financial economists. The literature of CSR presents three assertions related to the impact of CSR activities on the financial performance of companies. The first group of scholars have found the negative impact of CSR on CFP (Friedman, 2005). From his perspective the only accountability of a businessman is to utilise his resources and participate in activities which can increase profit. The second group of scholars disagree with the negative impact of CSR on FP and supported the positive impact which is established on stakeholder theory by Freeman (1984) (Orlitzky, et al., 2003; Preston & O'Bannon, 1997; Waddock & Graves, 1997; Aragon-Correa, et al., 2008). The third group claimed no specific relationship between CSR and FP (Alexander & Buchholz, 1978; Aupperle, et al., 1985). These scholars to some extent contending for the presence of too many impenetrable aspects for scholars to reveal a particular impact of CSR on CFP.

There is a contradiction in the stakeholder perspective and Friedman's (1970) perspective. Nevertheless, stakeholder theory was presented by Jensen (2001) which was an attempt to resolve the possible divergence amongst these two perspectives (Pour, et al., 2014). It was suggested by Post et al. (2002), that the capability of an organisation which produces maintainable profit and create long standing value are established by the association with internal and external stakeholders (Pour, et al., 2014). Though, different method of practicing CSR includes philanthropy and sponsorship. This investigation enriches and contributes to the knowledge and literature of CSR. The study is important in terms of presenting different

theories of CSR and its impact on financial performance and it provides practitioners guidance particularly in context of Pakistani banks.

For the purpose of this investigation CSR is viewed as an umbrella concept. There are different theories of CSR are included in this study. Nevertheless, the framework is created by using CSR pyramid by Carroll (1991). Thus, it is essential to comprehend the concept of CSR by definition and theories which are included in the following section of the study.

2.1.3.1 The Definition of CSR

It is observed by many scholars that corporate social responsibility has no specific and common definition (Longo, et al., 2005; Blowfield & Frynas, 2005; De George, 2010). Corporate social responsibility (CSR) has been define as the level of ethical accountability that possibly will be endorsed organisations ahead of uncomplicated compliance to the rules and regulation of the government (Kilcullen & Kooistra , 1999). One of the recognised descriptions of CSR is

“Corporate social responsibility refers to a corporation’s concern for society or for the impact its actions make on society (De George, 2006, p. 198)”

Another definition of CSR by a famous scholar is that CSR is

“concerned with treating the stakeholders of the firm ethically or in a responsible manner’ noting that the term ‘stake- holders’ includes the natural environment as well as ‘peoples both within and outside of the corporation” (Hopkins, 2003, p. 10).

Hemingway and Maclagan (2004), for instance, argue that the social responsibility of firms is one that is voluntary and goes beyond the law.

Additionally, CSR is defined as a notion in which organisations assimilate societal apprehensions on their corporate operations and in their dealing with their stakeholders with intent (European Commission, 2001; Crowther & Jatana, 2005; Neal, 2008; Prieto-Carron, et al., 2006). The concept of CRS is considered not only as the response to societal and environmental concerns but also as a technique to prevail over obstacles to additional world-wide progress (Clement-Jones, 2004).

McWilliams and Siegel (2001) describe Corporate Social Responsibility as “Doing all those activities which are not forced by law of those countries in which they are running their business and which are not for the primary benefits of the business but for the benefits of the society.”

The survey in Europe of CSR education has observed that there are fifty diverse descriptions of CSR modules, forty different classifications for CSR programmes and a number of alternative expressions that includes business ethics, stakeholder management and corporate citizenship (Visser, 2005). Similarly, variety of associated term was concluded in reviews of corporate social responsibility literature by Garriga & Mele (2003) and Carroll (1999).

Moreover, Bowen (1953) suggested that the notion of CSR emphasizes that the operation and activities of an organisation should fall within the guidelines set by the society and a firm should act morally. Nevertheless, Friedman (1970), claimed that the effective functioning of the society is determined by role specialization of its institution. He also considered firms as a financial institution and consequently should concentrate in the financial area which will become a cause for rectification of socially responsible behaviour by the market via profit (Pour, et al., 2014). On other hand, the opponent of this perspective claimed that the model presented by Friedman are not effective.

This arises the separation of ownership and management. If an organisation does not participate in societal activities the government of the country may compel to get involved. The legal perception of Friedman’s theory confines an organisation’s participation merely to financial responsibility, it can be argued that they are wide enough to permit parting from this constricted route. Moreover, societal accountability is also perceived as a result of and responsibility succeeding from exceptional growth of organisation’s societal potential (Davis, 1975). A firm can loss its power and move towards deterioration, if fails to maintain the equilibrium amongst social power with societal accountabilities (Davis, 1975).

Another group of scholars perceive societal accountabilities as a predetermined commitment organisation have for society (Donaldson, 1983). It was also suggested by him that an organisation can attain its power status because society has consented it to utilise both natural and human resources. It means that any society has a contained convention with an organisation and therefore in response for the claim to utilise sources in the process of production, it has right on the company (Pour, et al., 2014).

Numerous researchers consider the perspective that organisation should be perceived societal institute instead solely as private body (Frederick, et al., 1992; Freeman, 1984). This thesis has included the stakeholder model and the researcher of the study agrees with Freeman (1984), that an organisation have to focus on of its all stakeholders which also comprises customers and employees.

The study main focus is on CSR model presented by Carroll (1991), but with the involvement of stakeholders in it. Carroll's CSR pyramid has four responsibilities (economical, legal, ethical and philanthropic). Correspondingly, corporate social responsibility is hypothesised as the level of fit amongst the expectancy of society of business and business ethics as claimed by Zanies (Pour, et al., 2014). It was also suggested that corporate social responsibility is an additional layer to the managerial accountabilities which are outcome of progression of capitalism. On other hand, it was contended by Tuzzolino and Armandi (1981), and presented motivational theory of organisational social response (Tuzzolino & Armandi, 1981).

CSR and business ethics were assimilated differently in strategic procedure as suggested by Epstein (1987) (Pour, et al., 2014). Moreover, the notion of corporate social responsibility is also defined as firm's societal deeds whose rationale is to fulfil social requirements (Angelidis & Ibrahim, 1993).

One of the shortcomings of above mention perspectives of corporate social responsibility is that they are not successful in differentiating amongst past, contemporary and consequent CSR financial performance and therefore to create probable consistent assumptions related to direction of causativeness. A number of researches contained or focused on previous five years of financial performances of companies. Nevertheless, McGuire et al. (1988) was the first one to detached financial performance in past, concurrent and subsequent to CSR performance (Pour, et al., 2014).

In consequence, there are diverse definition of CSR and academic debate continues which provide the insight of the notion with different perspective. Numerous scholars defined CSR with different approaches although some researchers have noticed distinct common constituent to deal with corporate social responsibility (Blowfield & Frynas, 2005). It is also described as

an assortment of organisational goals and the analysis of consequences not merely by the decisive factors of productivity and organisational well-being but by moral values or verdicts of societal needs (Boatright, 2007, p. 368). CSR indicates as a responsibility of an organisation ahead of that prerequisite by the legal, financial, to engage in enduring ambitions that are beneficial for community or society (Papasolomou-Doukakis, et al., 2005). Consequently, it is observed by above mention definition of corporate social responsibility that it comprises fortification of the environment and corporate governance. CSR can also embrace deeds related to donation to education and healthcare (known as philanthropic activities), engagement with stakeholders, fair trade, waste management, moral investment, control of pollution, honourable and receptive dealing with suppliers and consumers, environmental improvement. CSR is a perception which varies according to the place and time of the operation for example the CSR activities in Asia are going to be different from the CSR action in Western countries (Sethi, 1975). The above mention CSR activities are represented in this particular research in context of Pakistani banks.

The concern arises in these all above-mentioned definitions of CSR is lack the global aspect. The researcher of the study believes that there is a requirement of ‘cultural’ view point in CSR. Political situation and overall economic situation of the country in which a firm operates does play essential role in any strategic implementation.

2.1.3.2 Evolution of CSR

The concept of corporate social responsibility has evolved in last few decades (Carroll, 1999) and also has been interest for business communities (Carroll, 1979; Schwartz & Carroll, 2003). The developed concept of CSR has influenced by equivalent progress in all spheres that includes development in business, society and environment. The formal and recognized publication of corporate social responsibility was presented in 1950 where Europe and United States had few parts in the world discussing and focusing on CSR literature (Hamid, et al., 2007). Bowen (1953), is considered as the father of corporate social responsibility (Carroll, 1999) has defined CSR in early ages. The CSR is the responsibility of a businessperson to always consider values of the society and its benefits whilst making any organisational decision or policies. Additionally, the consequences of the actions taken by an executive, is accountability of a businessperson. In 1950s, many organisations used to provide charity or donations, according to Murphy (1978), that was philanthropic era (Carroll, 2008).

On contrary, other researchers appraised the approach of corporate social responsibility mentioned by Bowen. A scholar, Davis has indicated the probability of creating value of any business through societal activities (Davis, 1960). It is also described by him that the decision and action of an organisation has not necessary just emphasis on the economic and technical benefits of the company but also little but a businessperson has to think little bit further (Davis, 1960; Malik & Nadeem, 2014). Some organisations have good management and an accountable business person always makes good decision which provide long-term benefits to the company with giving advantages to the society. It is also stated by Davis that the impact of corporate social responsibility is strong and long lasting, particularly on financial performance of an organisation. This new concept related to corporate social responsibility became popular in the era of 80s, and got recognition of a number of organisations.

After a decade, the notion of corporate social responsibility became well-defined and precise (Carroll, 1999; Falck & Heblich, 2007). One of the definitions of corporate social responsibility by a famous scholar Walton is mentioned as follow:

“The notion of CSR acknowledges the understanding of the association among organisation and society recognises that this relationship must be consider by top management whilst pursuing any goals (Walton, 1967, p. 18)”

Corporate social responsiveness and corporate social performance are the other two terminologies established in the era of 70s. Although, there was a need of positive and active approach of the organisations toward the implication of activates related to corporate social responsibility. In the following decade the notion ‘stakeholders, which was introduced in 60s (Mele, 2008), was encouraged by business communities. The term stakeholders were become the point of discussion and turned into eminent concept after it was mentioned in Freeman’s book in 1984 (Valor, 2005).The notion corporate social responsibility has progressed and developed persistently after the above mention ages. It has also become the preferred topic of communal dialog with the proliferation of societal issues, which includes environmental concerns and indigence of society (Boatright, 1993). Additionally, human rights, customers’ rights, environmental protection, human resource management, reporting of finances are related aspect covered by corporate social responsibility.

Although, Davis and Walton but Johnson intensified the different concept of corporate social responsibility is the first scholar to clear the idea and state it explicitly (Johnson, 1971). There are different components of corporate social responsibility, which was also mentioned by this scholar. Conventional wisdom and financial performance of an organisation are distinct aspects of corporate social responsibility noticed by Johnson. He also acknowledged that any business executing corporate social responsibility can have extra turnovers and revenues. He also identifies the notion of stakeholder in an organisation. The definition of corporate social responsibility given by him is mentioned as follow:

“An accountable organisation will not only emphasis on the long-term benefits for the company but also take into consideration about employee, clients, customers, suppliers and the society. Any organisation, which is socially responsible, is the one whose management create stability and balance a multiplicity of interest” (Johnson, 1971, p. 50).

The notion of corporate social responsibility, which was evolved after the research of years. It is mentioned in mid of 60s and early of 70s that the corporate social responsibility has some impact on the financial performance of an organisation (Walton, 1967; Johnson, 1971). Furthermore, some scholars had done intense research on the concept later and became more confident in their writing about the corporate social responsibility. Eells and Walton in the middle of 70s, also stated bit different definition of corporate social responsibility. They mentioned that ‘corporate social responsibility is a broad concept and it focuses on the concerns of the society and assist to society; these aspects are just more than any economic goals. Any organisation in this age can persist efficiently in any functioning free society and CSR is the concept which help organisation in recuperating and enriching the society’ (Eells, 1974).

Moreover, western countries, which are also known as the first world, started executing corporate social responsibility and researching about it. There are numerous research and studies undertaken by European researcher or scholars. Several organisations in developed countries are engage with societal activities for decades but developing countries are still lacking behind in the lead. Some of the developing countries have started taking interest and giving some importance to activities related to corporate social responsibility (Carroll, 2008). In today’s world, the businesses are growing fast and globalisation became the link among countries and their organisational activities and business communities. Many organisations are

taking part in executing societal activities globally and helping other communities as well. A number of rich countries organisations or multinationals are running campaigns to help poor countries and indigent people.

In the end of 70s, one of the famous scholar Carroll (1979) had intense research on corporate social responsibility and provided different definitions and models, which are still working in many organisations and for modern research (Crane & Matten, 2004).

2.1.3.3 Previous Conceptualisation in the CSR Area

Different scholars have explored CSR themes associated to the concepts originated from several distinct perceptions for instance social obligation, integrated strategy, stakeholder relation themes. The terms of CSR have predominantly derived from management areas. The following paragraphs are the review of CSR conceptual views originated from management area.

Social Obligation Driven.

According to Bowen (1953), corporate social responsibility is also described as the social obligation to practice those guidelines or follow rules which are anticipated in context of intention and moral of the society (Wang, 2015). Carroll's CSR pyramid, which includes four stages is also social obligation driven (Carroll, 1979).

Marketing Driven.

In 1960's, many scholars started focusing on relating CSR with the marketing instead of social obligations. Marketing-driven CSR emphasis on aspects of marketing for instance environmental marketing, dealing concerns with consumers, social sponsorship and reputation of business (Simmons & Becker-Olsen,, 2006; Crouch, 2006; Caruana & Crane, 2008). The perception of CSR with marketing aspect emphasize on stakeholders and customers. Employee satisfaction and environmental management are considered by managers in this aspect of CSR.

Stakeholder Driven.

Organisations depend on the stakeholders for the constant support and offering recourses the management has to care about the rights and requirements of stakeholders (Barney, 1991). There are two reasons behind the company's CSR activities related to stakeholders which are instrumental approach and moral perspective (Maignan & Ferrell, 2004). Researchers investigate about CSR concerns from stakeholders' relation aspects and emphasize on interaction with them (Basu & Palazzo, 2008). It is acknowledged by scholars that awareness of CSR amongst stakeholders has association with organisational performance and devotion of employees (Sen, et al., 2006).

Integrated Strategy Driven.

Organisations perform in a societal accountable way when they support their actions with the standards and requirements encompassed by their core stakeholders (Maignan & Ferrell, 2004). They demonstrate a structure to investigate the experience and consequences of a firm activities related to CSR with the perspective of stakeholders-relation. A number of scholars examine the notion of CSR from the integrated strategy aspects (Baron, 1995). Strategic CSR is a term used by few researchers as they perceived that CSR is embedded in an integrated strategy (McWilliams & Siegel, 2001).

Leadership Driven.

Various scholars attempted to relate CSR with leadership theories (Bass & Steidlmeier, 1999; Waldman & Galvin, 2011; Maak & Pless, 2006). It is described that the ability includes in creating and sustaining trust and strong relationship with stakeholders to attain common business vision is because of responsible leader. There is some argument on this concept that it is not confirm that responsible leaders are economic driven or moral driven, will they increase the financial performance of the organisation (Waldman & Siegel, 2008).

The above-mentioned are the previous conceptualisation of CSR however, the theory of CSR has remained debatable and vague. It is argued by some researchers that there is a positive relationship amongst corporate social performance and financial performance (Aupperle, et al.,

1985 ; Waddock & Graves, 1997) whilst some suggest it is neutral (McWilliams & Siegel, 2001). This demonstrates that the definition of CSR is still unclear, however, the theory of CSR has made development in previous decades. The researcher has summarised the concept of CSR used by previous scholars with different aspects in the following table.

Figure 5 Summary of CSR Definitions with References

Figure redacted for copyright reasons

(Wang, 2015)

2.1.3.4 Benefits of CSR.

It is the believe of CSR to create balance the interests of stakeholders and creating the sustainable progress. Although the presumptions of corporate social responsibility that need organisations to come forward are greatly argued. Scholars and business entities presented several views about corporate abilities to be involved in societal activities. On contrary, organisations are very strong and their participation in societal activities can enhance their impact on society and increase the probability of misusing their power. Many organisations work to resolve social issues related to poverty and education that can become a cause of improved organisational performance (Sprague, 2008). Companies may prefer to provide support to government and international firms to build trust and relationship. Although, regardless of access to enormous finances and existence in various topographical areas, companies specialize in fundamental capabilities confronting rivalry on international market and possibly will not have sufficient experience and knowledge to organise and implement programs resolving societal concerns (Aluchna, 2017). Moreover, in many cases, it is observed, that CSR has improved the performance of organisation (Abreu & Carreira, 2007).

The researcher of the study also believes that CSR is beneficial for Pakistani banks and can increase their reputation and financial performance. However, the banks have to consider time and cost of CSR activities like budget for charity and NGOs. Additionally, it is also the fact that Pakistani banks can get benefits from practicing CSR. Cost saving in term saving energy, using less packaging and less paper are also part of engaging with CSR. In long-term it can become cause behind brand differentiation (Epstein-Reeves, 2012). Moreover, by using CSR Pakistani banks can engage with their customers and it can activate employees in community and will become more engage. CSR will also increase employee satisfaction.

Above discussion demonstrates that there are various pros and cons of CSR, some of them are elucidated in the following table:

Figure 6 Pros and Cons of CSR

Pros of CSR	Cons of CSR
Responsibility of being a partner of social and economic reality	Business of business is business—corporate social responsibility refers to generating profits
Responsibility for current problems and challenges	Corporations are legally responsible only towards their owners (shareholders)—using corporate funds for other goals that increase shareholder value means violating the law (fiduciary duty)
Huge power and impact possibility (55 % of production generated by big global players)	CSR leads to increasing corporation role—corporations may abuse their power and influence possibility
Huge budget and assets for CSR programs	Corporations do not have necessary knowledge and experience in solving social problems
Access to different regions and information on current local challenges	
Attracting people's attention and involving them in CSR initiatives	
Know-how and possibility to support and cooperate with NGOs	

(Adapted from Aluchna, 2017)

Corporate social responsibility is also considered as an activity which is responsive, reputation driven with restricted reach in main business emphasizing predominantly in existing concerns. From the practical perception of CSR presents an extensive collection of internal and external advantages for organisations that making mission reliable, improving creativity, enhancing dedication of consumers, creating effectual system for motivation and make strong reputation (Asongu, 2007; Crouch & Maclean, 2011). The following table demonstrates the internal and external advantages of CSR.

Figure 7 External and Internal Advantages of CSR.

(Adapted from Aluchna, 2017)

2.1.3.5 The Limitations of CSR

The notion of corporate social responsibility being extensively used by many organisations may have various limitations. In the market environment, CSR is identified as a competitive approach aligned with organisational strategies and value of stakeholders. However, the drawbacks indicate to the hierarchy of stakeholders and to the role of corporate social responsibility in the structure of strategic management. CSR presumes the actions started by an organisation to fulfil the hope or expectations of stakeholders. Although, in relation to the legitimized hierarchy of aim of an organisation the importance of shareholders and economic performance come first.

The awareness of CSR and responsible management is growing (Mayer, 2012) but there are few drawbacks or challenges for equalizing the interests of stakeholders. The accountability

of an organisation is to connect with the activities to increase profit and enhance the value of shareholders (Friedman, 2005). Any divergence of a firm from this goal is seen as needless expenditure that can impact the value of shareholders. Moreover, it is also noticed by scholars that the association amongst managers and stakeholders are merely contrary not that accurately places in the controlling sequence which means that if there is breach of the contract, there will be no legal action against managers (Dobos, 2014). The challenge of spreading corporate governance presumptions in organisational strategy indicate to the actual level of responsibility and level of reliability. It is suggested in previous researchers that for organisations the strategic approach of corporate social responsibility possibly will result in consuming CSR as a resource of innovation, cost saving and competitive advantage (Yuan, et al., 2011). The practical perspective of corporate social responsibility displays few queries related to the implementation of CSR in organisations.

Moreover, one of the challenges of CSR is indicated to the immediate awareness of the notion in the structure of strategic management. It is essential for Pakistani banks' management to identify the new trends in the market. The concept of CSR may be considered as a modification in the anticipations to that organisations should react in a strategic manner and amend their strategy correspondingly. Hence, CSR is considered not as basic new concept but only as an environmental influence organisation require to locate. However, it is not substantial mistreat of the notion but possibly comprehend it superficially without giving it sufficient concentration and encouragement (Aluchna, 2017). If an organisation is going through financial crisis it may be challenging to implement CSR. Some scholars suggests that there is positive impact of CSR participation (Mia & Al-Mamun, 2011; Srchova & Dvorakova, 2010) but some researchers do not agree with the positive impact of CSR of an organisation (Souto, 2010; Selvi, et al., 2010). Additionally, potential organisational challenges of CSR include the deficiency of recognition from financial market, lack of skills, different perception of definition of CSR, resistance from employees and lack of encouragement from board members of an organisation (Lacey, et al., 2010).

Above-mention discussion demonstrates that Pakistani banks have to consider different concerns when implementing CSR. The researcher believes that Pakistani banks have to create a CSR team and selection of strong and potential team leader is essential to deal with all the challenges.

2.1.3.6 Motivation behind CSR Activities.

The pressure on organisations are increasing continuously to practice CSR because the standards of community are evolving to assess the societal performance of a firm and the outrage related with big organisations (Pirsch, et al., 2007). When an organisation chooses to participate in corporate social responsibility, has distinct motivations behind it. Successful companies contribute and spend considerable funds in accomplishing their societal accountabilities (Doukakis, et al., 2005). Organisations with good corporate social responsibility engender better revenue than companies without CSR activities (Arjoon, 2000; Marshall, 2005). Additionally, several scholars claimed that if organisation embraces CSR activities can develop good repute and also intensification in earnings (Joyner & Payne, 2002; Brammer & Millington, 2005). Good reputation gained by any CSR activity can provide competitive advantage over other companies.

Development or enhancement in marketing of a company can be generated by societal accountabilities which can attract consumers and lead to the propitious kindness towards organisation (Acuff, 2005). It is also being signified by a number of researchers that loyalty of consumers and image of a brand is often associates with company's corporate social responsibility (Kroll, 1996; Miller, 2002). One of the studies showed that 9 out of 10 customers consider corporate social responsibility repute of a firm to make decision of purchasing (Mackiewicz, 1993). A number of consumers enthusiastically encourage organisations with CSR and also share positive review about the firm to others which can improve the brand image and repute (Maignan, 2001; Berens, et al., 2005; Davis, 2005).

Another persuasive motivation for an organisation to participate in corporate social activities is culture of the country in which a firm operates. Any individual works under the boundaries and pressure of culture and similarly an organisation has to operates within limitation (Davis, 1973). Consequently, if there are any changes in the culture, the organisation has to make modifications accordingly. According to the researchers, in few emergent countries, dedication of the people towards religion put forth an effect on the approach and comportment of corporations to implement societal accountability activities (Nelson, 2004; Renato & Fiume, 2004).

Retention of employees and fascination of exclusive job candidates are also motivation behind practicing corporate social responsibility (Barnett & Vaicys, 2000; Backhaus, et al., 2002). Perception of workforce to the societal guidelines will affect their motivation to take part in CSR activities (Aguilera, et al., 2007). A research indicated that perception of candidates towards a CSR activity of a company impact applicants' aspiration to work for the company (Greening & Turban, 2000). When employees observe their company is devoted towards the CSR activities, they work hard and also participate in engendering innovative ideas to safeguard the environment (Ramus & Steger, 2000).

It is also signified by previous studies that an organisation participates in societal accountabilities activities to balance the government's rules and regulations (Moon & Vogel, 2008). Any innovation can be an additional cost to the company and can confine the flexibility in company's decisions. Therefore, organisations would rather obtain resolution to societal issues by presenting their own strategies and also to avoid involvement of authorities. It is essential for businesses to comprehend the framework of motivation of corporate social responsibility because it can assist organisations to operate efficiently. Additionally, it will add value in the strategy of an organisation and also to improve environmental managing activities. The following figure illustrates different motivations behind CSR.

Figure 8. Motivations behind CSR.

(Author's work)

2.1.4 Part three: Different theories of corporate social responsibilities.

There are a number of researchers and scholars presented different theories related to corporate social responsibilities in last few decades (Gray, et al., 1995). Many business communities are working or practicing corporate social responsibility by using those theories. With the passage of time and with the evolving concept of corporate social responsibility the complexity has also increased (Deegan & Gordon, 1996). This is the fact that there is no particular theory of corporate social responsibility and a number of alternative concepts are available in literature.

There was a discernment by Milton Friedman (1970) that the main purpose of an organisation is to increase their finance and gain profit by enhancing its performance and also to become a good corporate citizen. It is not necessary that every stakeholder do agree to the investment on other activities, which is not mandatory for businesses. Moreover, he discussed that it is essential for business to stay focused on the economics of the company and increase the value of the organisation by making profits. The only compulsory act which any organisation has to follow is the legal framework (Falck & Heblich, 2007). Furthermore, it is also possible that if a corporation implement any activity related to corporate social responsibility, can indignant the stakeholder of the company. A corporation always have to provide importance and priority to the fundamental commitment, which it has with stakeholders (Blowfield & Frynas, 2005). There is no particular moral accountability of any business towards society but it can be done on individual bases with personal expenses. This argument was also one of the famous among different scholars and researchers. Many scholars' emphasis that businesses have to focus on the profit maximisation whilst for the societal activities and improvement if the society the accountable authority is the government of the country (Klonoski, 1991).

Additionally, different argument on corporate social responsibility like Friedman's concepts was of great attention for researchers. A number of researchers have separated economic and non-economics goals and also stated that activities related to corporate social responsibility can become one of the reasons behind gaining long-term profits. In last few decades, researchers have focused on empirical studies related to corporate social responsibilities and financial performances of organisations. Many studies had found that there is a positive association among the financial performance and corporate social responsibility (Fussler, 2004).

The above discussion has demonstrated that business communities are following different theories and every theory or concept of corporate social responsibility have distinct assumptions. In order to achieve the research objectives, the researcher has also included some of the theories in this study, discussing diverse notion to understand the CSR literature.

2.1.4.1 CSR Pyramid by Carroll.

In the end of 70s era, a famous scholar Carroll established the three dimensions model of corporate social responsibility, in which it explained the aspects which was not discussed in early ages by any researcher. This model of corporate social responsibility presents different standard and distinct features of businesses. According to the three-dimension model, corporate social responsibility has three different elements, which are: the first element or dimension mentioned in the model is purely economic, on the second is purely ethical and the last dimension is purely legal (Schwartz, 2011). These all dimensions are sovereign and can constituted unconnectedly. Although they are independent but they have their own identity and these dimensions are come together to provide the complete structure to the cube constructed by Carroll in this three-dimension model. However, some theorist raised some criticism and concerns in the model that all three dimensions are interwoven and inseparable (Schwartz, 2011). The very first dimension of the model is the basic or fundamental notion, which is divided into further four classifications. Social responsibility categories include moral, licit and flexible prospects that any society provided by a company in a particular time (Carroll, 1979). According to Carroll (1979), there are four features or categories of it, which are elucidated as: Philanthropic, ethical, legal and economic responsibilities (Malik & Nadeem, 2014).

There responsibilities are constructed and linked with each other. Each responsibility in a CSR pyramid is giving support to other responsibility. There is a hierarchy in the pyramid of corporate social responsibility and it also express comprehension of imminence dependency. The structure of pyramid demonstrates that the factors or elements of corporate social responsibility are in ascending order and have great importance. It is essential for an organisation to fulfil the economic responsibility first and then focus on the licit accountabilities of the corporation. After completing these responsibilities, it is also advantaging to complete ethical and philanthropic one. Several scholars have used these domains of corporate social responsibility presented by Carroll (Aupperle, et al., 1985 ;

Aupperle, 1984; Burton & Hegarty, 1999 ; Clarkson, 1995; O'Neill, et al., 1989; Smith, et al., 2004; Pinkston & Carroll, 1996; Strong & Meyer, 1992).

The CSR pyramid has been the most cited and durable model in the literature (Crane & Matten, 2004). Therefore, the framework of this investigation is created on CSR pyramid model and evaluated in context of Pakistani banks. The pyramid has four elements or responsibilities which are elucidated as follow.

According to the pyramid of corporate social responsibility presented by Carroll, the very first responsibility of a corporation is economic responsibility. It is essential for a company to give priority to their financial performances for the survival and development. Fulfilment of this responsibility is a must and great requirement in this competitive business world.

The next element in the CSR pyramid is legal or licit responsibilities. After focusing on the financial aspects of the corporation it is also important to emphasis on the implementation of the laws provided by the country, on which company operates. Rules and regulations of the business and country are essential to be considered by an organisation whilst making any decisions.

The second last component in the pyramid is ethical accountabilities of a corporation. There are particular norms and values of each society, which is considered to be followed by business. These norms and values of the society are often part of the legal framework, but few things are not mentioned in laws and has to be comprehend by businesses. Every society has expectations form the businesses and it is responsibility of a corporation to fulfil these expectations, after completing their economic and legal accountabilities.

Last but not the least; philanthropic responsibilities are also the important element of the pyramid. A number of organisations prefer to engage with societal activities because of different reasons. There are several social activities, which can be chosen by an organisation for example some corporations give charity, and some prefer to help society by providing support to health or education sectors. These all the fundamental elements or components of the pyramid of corporate social responsibility, which an organisation has to consider.

The second dimension of the 3D model is social issues which an organisation has to consider when executing activities related to corporate social responsibility. Every society has different social issues and any organisation has to keep in mind that it can change with the passage of time. Moreover, if a corporation operates in different countries, must have to confront with distinct problems of the society, which includes health, and safety of employees, safety of products and issues like discrimination. In developing countries many organisations are dealing with societal problems for example, many poor countries even do not have clean water to drink and several people have health issues because of having dirty water. Some organisations focus on the resolution of these big problems.

The third dimension of the Carroll's 3-D model is the philosophy of social responsiveness. This element of the model is related with the concern that if an organisation completes the expectation of a society and help in resolving societal problems. Social responsiveness is the main word here which was of great importance (Davis & Blomstrom, 1975). Corporate social responsibility can have good reaction or it can also have a proactive response, this statement was being in debate among scholars. Although, this model of corporate social responsibility is not new but it still has benefits and this study is all about corporate social responsibility, therefore it was important to cover it. The following figure illustrates the CSR pyramid by Carroll (1991).

Figure 9 CSR Pyramid Carroll (1991)

Figure redacted for copyright reasons

The above illustrated CSR pyramid is most durable and widely cited in CSR literature (Crane & Matten, 2007) and therefore, the researcher of this investigation created framework of the study by using this model. Some of the reasons behind the popularity of models includes that it is simple and easy to comprehend, the model was presented by Carroll over 30 years ago and it has been empirically tested largely (Carroll, 1991; Visser, 2005). The model has been assimilated by Carroll in different competitive themes as well.

The CSR pyramid was first empirically tested by Aupperle, Hatfield and Carroll in 1985 and 1983. The analysis was supported the model that there are four elements of corporate social responsibility which are related to each other but they are independent (Visser, 2005). This attempt of empirically testing of the CSR model was expanded by Pinkston and Carroll in 1994 by using similar survey in American divisions of international organisations with headquarters

in different countries like France and Sweden. The result of that investigation also established Carroll's CSR model, although in Germany and Sweden legal accountabilities were at the first priority. Moreover, other survey tested the CSR pyramid in USA for black owned firms and argued the crucial aspect of culture in the model (Edmondson & Carroll, 1999). The result demonstrated that ethical accountabilities are the first one in place than legal.

Most of the researches and empirical tested of CSR pyramid was conducted in USA and in western countries context. Although, there are only few studies have done investigation in developing countries and this research will fill the gap by testing CSR pyramid and the impact of CSR on financial performance in Pakistani banks.

2.1.4.2 Criticism on the model.

The above model and concept of corporate social responsibility is one of the most popular models in the research history. However, there is nothing in the business research or theories, which is away from criticism. The Carroll's model was also being criticized by many different scholars because of its limitations which are less precision, less transparency, less expressive and also less explanatory precision (Visser, 2005). The model has lack of theoretical or conceptual transparency and it is also not clear that corporate social responsibility is portrayed has hierarchy. Moreover, the scholar also criticized the model it is blending everything, it means one cannot fit all notions like stakeholder and ethics in one pyramid. These concepts are wide and have details in it, which an organisation has to consider while making any decisions.

Additional, when it comes to the descriptive precision, a number of researchers have argued about it and criticized the model. The CSR pyramid is striving for universality as it was empirically tested in context of United States of America (Nalband & Al Kelabi, 2014). Every country is diverse with distinct priorities, culture which not only give different nuances to the meaning of every element, but possibly will also give different relative significance (Burton, et al., 2000; Crane, 2000). An organisation cannot use one model in each society. For example, western society is different from the third world or developing countries and have entirely diverse societal norms and values. Every layer in the model have dissimilar significance, which can assign in distinctive framework.

2.1.4.3 Conceptual Clarity of the model.

It was criticised by scholars that CSR pyramid is in hierarchy but Carroll is not constant in his clarification (Visser, 2005). Sometimes he claimed that is the manner corporate social responsibility has progressed in times gone by (Carroll, 1979). And other hand he suggests that it portrays a succession of requirement (Carroll, 1991). Additionally, he also suggests that every accountability of the CSR model should be accomplished at the same time by an organisation (Carroll, 2000).

Moreover, Carroll at one-point associated corporate citizenship with philanthropy than he claimed it effectively as equivalent as corporate social responsibility (Carroll, 1991). And this was criticised by scholars that he conflates a number of affiliated notions to CSR pyramid (Visser, 2005). Scholars who supported corporate citizenship like Matten & Crane (2005) and McIntosh, Thomas, Leipziger, & Coleman, (2002) undoubtedly do not share this clarification or explanation presented by Carroll (Visser, 2005).

The above discussion demonstrates that Carroll was attempting to present the model as a whole and some scholars appreciate this inclusive or comprehensive attribute of the model (Aupperle, et al., 1985). However, there is a separate discipline of environmental management available. It is also unclear that he is utilised model as an explanatory or normative (Visser, 2005). The CSR pyramid is also criticised because it is very simple and static (Visser, 2005).

2.1.4.4 Critique of prioritisation of economic responsibilities

The economic responsibilities of an organisation are the first or prior one in CSR pyramid by Carroll. It is considered by Carroll (1999), that if an organisation does not generate profit, it will not survive. It makes the position of other elements in pyramid arguable (Baden, 2016). In a competitive world businesses are dependent on various desires to generate profits rather than law and several researches exhibits in what manner this give escalation to illicit and immoral corporate practices (Bennett, et al., 2013; Baden, 2016; Cai & Liu, 2009; Shleifer, 2004). The extreme approach generated from the law and social norm which are supported by a number of business models is criticised by researchers (Goodpaster, 2007). It was also claimed that there

is a risk in organisation's decision-making against ethical norms that provides security (Goodpaster, 2007). Many other scholars also supported the claim that the organisations have to give importance or prioritization to ethical responsibilities and create value for shareholders of the company (Goodpaster, 2007; Greider, 2003; Friedman, et al., 2008; Kolp & Rea, 2006). According to Kang and Wood (1995), the criticism on the hierarchy of CSR pyramid is that it appears social welfare will be lost for financial purposes because it places economic responsibilities before ethical and legal (Goodpaster, 2007). Moreover, there is a debate about the responsibilities in CSR pyramid which has incessant vigorous conflict with one another and the greatest tension possible to be found amongst economic and legal responsibilities. This dispute is defended by a scholar that there is opposite or negative association amongst economic and ethical responsibilities (Aupperle, 1984). This increases the concern for welfare of the society and environment in the CSR model.

2.1.4.5 Carroll's global pyramid of CSR

The model of CSR pyramid was proposed by Carroll in 1979 and he worked later on it in 1991 in United States of America. At that time CSR was widespread in western societies. Since that time, it was suggested by a number of scholars that CSR pyramid requires restructuring to fulfil the situation of different countries (Carroll, 2016). The level of pyramid plays role in western countries; however, they have diverse importance and are interconnected to a certain extent in dissimilar way (Crane & Matten, 2007). In today's world, businesses have become global which is challenging. Similarly, the model was re-evaluated in context of developing country by one of the famous scholars and it was claimed that the arrangement of elements of CSR in Africa contrast from the classic pyramid (Visser, 2011). Additionally, he also argued that CSR is not same in all over the world (Visser, 2011). He continues to claim that every country has distinctive set of CSR drivers.

Moreover, the concern being raised up regarding the applicability of corporate social responsibility and thus, the pyramid in dissimilar places, the same possibly will be said for its applicability in different organisational perspective and it also include large and small companies, private or public sector (Crane, et al., 2008).

The above criticism demonstrates that the Carroll's theoretical model of corporate social responsibility has criticised by various scholars. There are a number of models and theories related to corporate social responsibility are available, from which, some are included in this study. However, the main model used in this study to build a framework is of CSR pyramid as it is one of the famous models and it is also a fact that researchers will continue to explore and investigate about the applicability of CSR pyramid in organisational, international and situational framework. This is how theory and practice develop (Carroll, 2016).

2.1.4.6 Stakeholder Theory.

It is difficult to describe areas of literature in discipline of business in a society because they are mostly interlinked. Consequently, CSR literature is moderately constructed on stakeholder literature (Kakabadse, et al., 2005). This study is related to CSR and the researcher believes that it is important to include stakeholder theory in the literature. It is understandable from the name of the theory that it focuses on the stakeholders. This theory identifies the accountability of an organisation towards stakeholders. The theory also elucidates that the organisations are the element or ingredient of a wider societal system (Islam & Deegan, 2008). It also claims that a corporation has to be responsive to the requirement of stakeholder and always consider them before making any decisions because any wrong decision can affect stakeholders of the company. In the 1960s Eric Rhenman and Bengt Stymne, unambiguously delineated the stakeholder approach (Kakabadse, et al., 2005) and their research precipitously became popular in Scandinavia and the framework became famous amongst researchers. The revival era of the stakeholder approach was also renowned and became a landmark which was presented by Freeman in 1984.

One of the famous definitions of stakeholders is mention as follow:

‘it is group of entities or persons which can have impact of the decisions made by an organisation and also have effect of the achievement of organisational goals’ (Freeman, 1984).

There are several rights of a stakeholder of an organisation and has to be considered by a corporation. One of the ways of demonstrating social behaviour is that the company should focus on the multiplication of the interest and fulfilment of the requirement of stakeholders.

The terminology of stakeholder theory was presented by Ansoff, in mid of 60s (Ansoff, 1965). There are two categories of stakeholders, which is primary and secondary. The stakeholders, which have direct relation to the company and have access to all the legitimate entitlements are considered to be primary. On other hand, the group, which is less recognised and have less legal claims, are secondary stakeholders.

Moreover, the notion of stakeholder provide platform to the management of an organisation and it assists an organisation to think beyond the finances of the company. According to this theory a person who is been affected by the decision and achievement of the company is a stakeholder. The management in any organisation has to manage its association with stakeholders and always has to analyse, evaluate and implement organisational strategies with consideration of stakeholders. It has been accepted by scholars that better relationship with stakeholders lead an organisation towards success and better performance (Barnett & Salomon, 2012; Galant & Cadez, 2017).

Additionally, the dynamics of stakeholders have great impact of the organisational decisions, which was discussed by Freeman in mid of 80s (Freeman, 1983). The scholar has separated the notion of stakeholder in two, the first one is, corporate planning and business policy model, and the second one is corporate social responsibility model of stakeholder management. The first model is corporate planning and business policy, which is related to the enhancement of strategic decisions by individuals, necessitated for the persistence of organisational success. Customers or consumers, suppliers, public groups and suppliers are the part of stakeholder group. These stakeholders are often not argumentative in their nature. Contrary, the exterior inspirations and effects on organisation, which may have combative opinion, is related to the corporate social responsibility model of stakeholder management (Roberts, 1992). In challenging situation of organisational planning to embrace changes in corporate and communal atmosphere, the above model is believed to be effectual. The following figure shows the stakeholders of an organisation.

Figure 10 Stakeholders of a Firm

(Author's work)

Furthermore, the requirements of stakeholders will increase automatically, if an organisation encourage the power of stakeholder (Freeman, 1983). The stakeholder theory postulates apposite rationalisation for integrating strategic or premeditated decision making in researches of activities related to corporate social responsibility. Conversely, the challenge for organisations is to manage the equilibrium among stakeholders because every stakeholder is different from other and have distinct requirements (Mele, 2008).

The management in any organisation have several jobs and one of the important duties is to encourage attentiveness of stakeholders according to the level of stakeholder. A few stakeholders are more important to the organisation than others are and it is essential for the success of the organisation to always consider them before making any decision.

Moreover, some scholars have presented principles of stakeholder management and provided standards for the management of an organisation. The principle stated by Clarkson in 1999 are elucidated as follow:

- The management of the organisation has to be proactive in understanding and evaluating the issues and problems of primary stakeholders. These stakeholders have legal rights and their interest should be the priority of a corporation. The example of these stakeholders are the shareholders of the company.
- The second important thing, which a management of a company has to consider, is the transparency among stakeholders. The organisation has to communicate straightforwardly about the risks and investments, which can affect or have great impact on stakeholders.
- The third principle is that the management has to embrace procedure, methods, approaches and behaviours that are penetrating apprehensions of any stakeholder.
- The recognition of the determination and remuneration has to be done by the management of the organisation. The management must have to endeavour to attain impartial allocation of reimbursements between stakeholders.
- The management of the company has to be supportive with communal or public and private figures and should work hard to reduce the risk. The risk management is the essential practice which any organisation has to consider in every era.
- The activities, which create issues related to human rights and become cause of trouble by creating risk, should have to be avoided by the management. The organisational activities have to be under the legal framework so it will not create problems.
- The other principle is that management has to understand the prospective divergence among these two, first one is their own responsibility as a stakeholder and second one is the illicit and ethical accountability for other stakeholders' interests. The managers of the company have to create a balance among these two and of required can have appropriate guidance from experts.

Moreover, the stakeholder theory provides and discuss the rights of stakeholders, which become the cause of enhancement of value of stakeholders. However, the management of an organisation have many accountabilities and duties, which they have to complete. An executive in a business community works with aim and objectives and a community has different adherents, which have diverse privileges comprising right to articulate their concerns (Handy, 2002). The possible expectations of stakeholders are elucidated in Appendix 9.3.

The management in an organisation are accountable to make a particular task to a particular group of individuals. However, it is also stated by many researchers that the stakeholder theory has some theoretical ambiguousness (Clarkson, 1995). Additionally, many organisations have positive response of executing stakeholder theory and have long lasting consequences.

It is frequently contended that the stakeholder approach is not feasible as it indicates the sacrifice of a firm goals to ethically adequate social objectives (Vinten, 2000). Though, the stakeholder theory does not refuse success or productivity as an organisational objective, but rather broadens the stakeholder model. Moreover, it was claimed by Clarkson (1995) that a firm which does not include concerns of its primary stakeholders in organisational strategy challenge its long-term persistence. Companies must endeavour to attain their own business goals whilst at same time contenting in a reasonable way the legitimate demand of their stakeholders. The researcher accepts and believes that the stakeholder approach does not aim to stop companies to make profit or force a firm to shift its focus form market progress but its emphasis on the comprehension of business in which the objective and goals are linked with human (Jones & Wicks, 1999). There has been extensive research on the relationship between social accountabilities and financial performance and the conclusion supports mostly positive association amongst them (Margolis & Walsh, 2003; Orlitzky, et al., 2003). However, the challenge is always there of measuring CSR and CFP, which is complex.

Nevertheless, it is difficult to find any theory or concept in business without any criticism. The stakeholder theory also has some criticism from different researcher and scholars. One of the objections on the theory is that it does not give a company particular intention to work on because equalising the interest of stakeholders which becomes the cause of less attention toward business conducts (Mele, 2008). Although, stakeholders are mostly in favour of stakeholders and this criticism for some researchers is not convincing. Some scholars have discussed about this theory and mentioned that if an organisation only emphasis on creating the value of stakeholders can cause in risk in business and can create difficulty for management (Freeman, et al., 2004). It is also possible that the market price and share value of the company can have impact of the specific focus of the corporation toward stakeholders.

Furthermore, managerial unscrupulousness can be developed in an organisation, which is also one of the limitations of stakeholder theory (Sternberg, 2000). It is also argued by the scholar that stakeholder theory can effectually rescind the responsibility of businesses, as it is difficult for all organisations to satisfy or complete the necessity of all stakeholders. Some researcher argued the above-mentioned criticism and stated that the ability of management to give authority to self-serving behaviour is not a valid objection (Phillips, et al., 2003).

It is also suggested by some scholars that the stakeholder theory mostly emphasis on the dissemination of the productivities of the organisation (Marcoux, 2000). Although this objection is rejected by several other authors and researchers. As other scholars stated that the stakeholder theory support the people who have rights and their contribution in the organisation. Therefore, it is a right of stakeholder to have information about the decisions of the organisation because it can have great impact on them. According to the scholar, (Phillips, et al., 2003), the procedures or methods in which company operates are equally imperative for a stakeholder as the concluding dissemination and benefits.

Hence, the researcher of the study believes that Pakistani banks have to be enthusiastic about the business and achieve their objectives with the consideration of stakeholders. The stakeholder theory is not without criticism but it is practice by many successful corporations. The stakeholders are part of an organisation as they can have great impact of the decision made by the management. The priority of a bank is to enhance the financial performances but also consider people associated with the decisions. Several organisations implementing corporate social responsibility also encourage their response towards stakeholders' requirements. However, criticism of the stakeholder theory also lies in its moderately inadequate managerial practicality (Kakabadse, et al., 2005). As the theory remains vague when it comes to help managers who specifically deals with stakeholders. Therefore, Pakistani banks should consider some stakeholder analysis tools to deal with this concern.

2.1.4.7 Agency Theory.

One of the popular and oldest theories of management and economics literature is Agency theory (Panda & Leepsa, 2017; Wasserman, 2006) and therefore, it is an important theory to include it in this study. This theory is related with the conditions in which an individual desire to persuade others to accomplish certain assignment of the person's interest but not essentially the interest of an agent (Heath & Norman, 2004). According to the agency theory there are two main elements in an organisation, the first one is the shareholder who are the principals and the other one is managers of the company who are the agents (Fama & Jensen, 1983). This theory focuses on the association of these two components of an organisation. It is not essential that stakeholders have all the information about the decisions making by an organisation. Moreover, it is also not compulsory that an agent will always take actions in benefit of the principal. The theory focus is on that it is possible for an agent to be deceitful and therefore the theory states that an agent has to consider principal interest. An agent has to obey the rules and do the right thing by keeping the objective of maximising the welfare of principal. An agent of the organisation has to be transparent and must exhibit the financial information in the market for example the financial statement in the annual report. Publishing of annual report can have great effects on the share prices and reputation of the organisation in the market.

Moreover, there is agency association as between a one ingredient relates with another which is principal with agent. There are some rights of principals toward the agent and it can have impact of the management decisions. The agency theory become popular in mid of 80s and many researchers made changes and development in the concept. Some researchers have discussed the division among ownership and control. An agent has all the knowledge about the organisational activities but the principal is not necessarily aware of every activity or decision. Sometimes agent or management makes decisions for the company's or their own benefit instead of principal's interest (Salazar & Husted, 2008).

It is essential for Pakistani banks to encourage an agent and motivate them to act morally and make right decisions with consideration of principal's interests. It is also the part of corporate social responsibility that an agent act within societal norms, and should take care of people who have impact of organisational activities. It is entirely unethical of a management to not to follow its duty and practice activities without taking principals into account. Although it is important for banks to increase their profit but corporate social responsibility can also enhance

the image and reputation of an organisation and it is a part of CSR activity to support principal by creating value of shareholders. However, the major concern in this theory is the form of legal association present to the principal is the require to have an incessant inspection on every phase undertaken by agents. Thus, it is necessary for principal to update economical information regularly to help in scrutinizing the benefits attained from assigning accountability to the agent (Hendriksen & Breda, 1992). It is also indicated in this theory that agents know more of an organisation than the principal. Because of this view some agents can sometimes implement their preference to make the most of their service at the expenditure of the principal (Salazar & Husted, 2008). To make sure acquiescence with the principal's instruction there should be an anticipation for bonding cost and agency cost.

Criticism on the theory has made because it mostly concentrates on agent side of the 'principal and agent problem' (Perrow, 1986). It was also observed that the theory is less concerned about principals. Even though, the agency theory is very pragmatic and famous, it has some drawbacks or constraints. The theory presumes a predetermined contract amongst agent and principal for limited or unlimited future period, where the future is ambiguous (Panda & Leepsa, 2017). The researcher of this study believes that in practical situation this theory may find some difficulties or obstructions which includes irregularity of information, deception and transaction cost. The main attraction of shareholders of Pakistani banks, is in their profit and they have limited role in the organisation. This theory looks through the capabilities and proficiencies of managers and only considers the managers as opportunistic.

2.1.4.8 Legitimacy Theory.

Another important theory related to corporate social responsibility is Legitimacy theory, which focuses on the legitimacy of an organisation. It can be described as, a situation which happens when individual's value system is compatible to the societal structure. There is a risk to value of an individual's rightfulness when there is a difference endures among two values systems (Dowling & Pfeffer, 1975, p. 122). Moreover, the theory states that there is a societal agreement between the organisation and the society of the country in which the company functions (Reverte, 2009).

This theory focuses on the reality that an organisation has several distinct resources and it is also important for a corporation to operate according to the norms and values of the society. Legitimacy theory is emphasis on the management of legality, which is dependent on communications of the organisation. An organisation has to operate in society and it plays an essential role in decision of an organisation. It is also being discussed by researchers that in previous era the financial performances of the organisation were the greatest for measurement of legitimacy but in today's world a corporation has to make some investment for the welfare of the society.

The concept of legitimacy theory suggests that an organisation cannot operate without a society and therefore it is essential to consider the people of the society whilst making decisions. Some corporation emphasis on the charity or donations that is philanthropy to attain legitimacy. Many scholars have argued about the legitimacy gap, which an organisation may have to confront with (Lindblom, 1993). According to some scholar, it happens when an organisation's performance does not fulfil the anticipation or expectancy of significant community or primary stakeholders.

It is necessary for Pakistani banks to provide proper education or information about the intention of the company to stakeholders. Moreover, stagnant position of a bank is not beneficial so it has to adopt the change and must make alterations according to the contemporary environment. This theory also demonstrates that it can become one of the reasons for organisations to implement activities related to corporate social responsibility. The disclosure of societal activities is also the part of ethical activity, which can shelter the corporation's legitimacy (Hackston & Milner, 1996). A number of researchers have found positive association between CSR disclosure and legitimacy of organisations. Organisations involve with CSR activities to obtain legitimacy (Du & Vieira, 2012), encouraged purchase intent (Lee, et al., 2013) and restore brand image (Vanhamme & Grobbsen, 2009; Lee, et al., 2018).

Moreover, it was observed that there is argued that legitimacy theory is form of social contact that exists amongst organisations and stakeholders (Moir, 2001). The researcher of this study believes that fulfilment of this approach establishes the survival of Pakistani banks (Palazzo & Scherer, 2006).

2.1.4.9 Institutional Theory.

This is observed that in many management journals the literature on corporate social responsibility have ignored the societal aspects of CSR on the whole. Numerous researchers have considered societal constituent as a black box, as an array of peripheral necessity that are interpreted into functionalist, influential and corporate case reasoning for societal commitment by organisations (Margolis & Walsh, 2003; Brammer, et al., 2012). It is undoubtedly revealed by various meta studies of inferred literature of corporate social responsibility and also analytical evaluation of CSR as a subfield of management (Bakker, et al., 2005; Lockett, et al., 2006; Banerjee, 2007; Hanlon, 2008). Moreover, it is indicated that the CSR literature is generally descriptive and normative (Campbell, 2007).

This particular research is related to the impact of CSR on financial performance of Pakistani banks. Social science would be able to determine the presence of advantages of market and therefore, the persuasive attraction with the corporate case for CSR is an important fact (Vogel, 2006). There are many researchers have studied the association amongst corporate social responsibility and economic performance of the organisation (Orlitzky, et al., 2003). The emphasis of an organisation as the fundamental player in commencing communally anticipated comportment on the part of business has been entrenched into the approach of intellectualising corporate social responsibility. Whereas familiar delineation of corporate social responsibility embraces obligatory accountabilities which are legal, economical, philanthropic and ethical (Carroll, 1999). Similarly, CSR is also described as the exercise or practice which develop the firm and provide advantages to the society in way that exceed what organisations are legitimately necessitated to do (Vogel, 2006). This prospect shows the supremacy of the agency theory by means of considering the disposition of an organisation in corporate learning and the demotion of corporate integrity to the side-lines (Garriga & Melé, 2004; Khurana, 2007). The strategy and guiding principle documents of corporate organisations are recurred by the same prominence on voluntarism (Kinderman, 2012). As a matter of fact, yet foremost communal guideline programmes have not contested this fundamental conjecture. For instance, there is a Green Paper in European Commission, which describes societal accountabilities as a notion that organisations assimilate with the societal and conservational apprehensions in their action

of business and in their dealings with stakeholders with intent (European Commission, 2001). In previous few years, the intellectual deliberation on corporate social responsibility has gradually revealed a developing turbulence about this instead restricted approach to comprehending the societal accountabilities of corporation. The basic reluctance is related to the inadequate value of corporate-focused approach to research of CSR. Since many researches have indicated that outcome of this element of study are unsatisfying (Orlitzky, 2008). The reason that organisations participate in activities related to CSR as one of the techniques to increase the financial performance of the organisation look as if manifestly inadequate to defend why firms participate in societal anticipated consequences.

Another aspect which have impact on research of business is advent of globalisation. If corporate social responsibility is an alternative technique to proliferation proceeds or profits, the question arises of why methods of corporate social responsibility diverge so immensely amid constituencies and countries internationally. In addition, it is also point at issue that CSR as ordinarily North American or Anglo-Saxon conception has lone moderately expanse to other parts of the international market. In order to rationalise this with a rather restricted array of reasons about effectiveness and proceeds intensification seems to have rather imperfect leverage, as several extremely prosperous firms in Japan and Western Europe maintain to flourish without significantly severe explicit concentration to `CSR and correlated notions (Matten & Moon, 2008).

The analysis of the role of private organisations in community realm is one of the aspects emerging over previous few years. The fascination towards CSR has been generated by questions about the effects of organisations on aboriginal individuals, the environment, the working circumstances in emergent countries, and political movements in industrialized democratic system (Banerjee, 2000; Radin & Calkins, 2006; Jermier, et al., 2006; Crouch, 2004). The private corporations are rather far beyond than just earnings obsessed or profit-driven money-making players in the society, is determined by these concerns. Organisations are not only unreceptive actors in international market whose societal effects go along a straightforward profit maximisation justification with slight significance ahead of the limitations of the business area. The government of any country concede the organisations the

advantages of restricted obligation to smooth the progress of accretion of capital which shows that firms always have been a political formation. In primitive era organisations obtained restricted liability originally to follow the communal attraction although gradually expand all over the financial system (Roy, 1997). This augmentation of restricted liability generated a basic concern of corporate governance. Nevertheless, this is not a merely concern of how management persons are responsible to the more disseminated shareholders as indicated by agency theory, but further indispensable concerns of what accountabilities society takes on the organisation itself in substitute for the lawful honour of restricted responsibility. Organisations have an influential or pivotal effect on the consequences of occupation, eminence of environment, expenditure and other problems that demonstrates organisational power and accountabilities are subject of communal concerns. The effort to develop the perception of behaviour of business is not restrained to the study of corporate social responsibility. The literature of business management on the whole has still to take comprehensive awareness of the association amongst business and its PEST environment genuinely (Barley, 2007).

Several researchers had investigated and established theories about CSR and focused on the impact of environment on corporations. However, now corporate researchers have to pay more consideration that how firms modify and make their environment. Consequently, the interest in institutional theory between researchers of CSR has concurred with a developing encouragement of institutional theory on business studies. It is also observed by investigators that multinationals have established extreme upsurge in embracing institutional theory to comprehending the method multinational organisations manage with their business internationally (Westney & Zaheer, 2001; Geppert, et al., 2006; Jackson & Deeg, 2008). There are scholars of business management are developing interest in institutional theory which shows it has some advantages to the research of CSR.

In the year 1970s, institutional theory established from organisational theory and considers organisations as element of comprehensive societal structure and also utilised in literature of environmental disclosure (DiMaggio & Powell, 1983; Meyer & Rowan, 1977; Amran & Devi, 2008; Amran & Haniffa, 2011; Matten & Moon, 2008; Joseph & Taplin, 2011; Sobhani, et al., 2011; Jamali & Neville, 2011). The institutional theory concentrates on the difference of operations of organisations in identical industry. There are three distinct institutions in the

theory which are regulatory, normative and cognitive institutions. These elements can give coercive, normative or mimetic pressure on organisation to turn into compatible like other organisations of the same industry. Different organisations confront with distinct types of pressures from the society. Institutions are created by society and represented as recognised regulations, culture, rational and customary practices which restrained a firm to embrace certain practices like corporate social responsibility.

Institutions are defined as

“formal rules and taken-for-granted cultural frameworks, cognitive schema, and routinized processes of reproduction; and assumes that actors are motivated more by a logic of appropriateness whereby action is constrained and enabled by cultural frames, schema, and routines” (Campbell, 2006, p. 926).

There are three categories of institutions regulatory, normative and cognitive, which present the rationality of appositeness for a specific comportment of an organisation (Scott, 2014). When it comes to the rules and regulations of an organisation, it comprises of two diverse rules that are soft rules (established by industry) and hard rules (set by the government of the country) (Marquis, et al., 2007; Campbell, 2007). If the rules of the country in which an organisation operates, are strict can make organisation to conform and operate conscientiously within society. Additionally, values (the act which is communally adequate) and norms (desired way of acting and being) are set by normative institutions (Bebbington, et al., 2009). These norms and values are the part of the rules which are establish by different entities of the society like media, proficient organisations and learning institutions (Muthuri & Gilbert, 2011). When it comes to cognitive institutions, very delicate and challenging to distinguish them (Bebbington, et al., 2009). Cultural values, beliefs and identities are components of cognitive institutions. It is subject to the knowledge of the manager of an organisation to comprehend these cognitive elements while practicing CSR. The collective or mutual meaning for socially accountable activities of an organisation is encompassed in cognitive structure. For instance, some organisations sponsored construction of mosques in Bangladesh since natives acknowledge religious creations (Sobhani, et al., 2009). These all institutions can generate difficulty and isomorphic pressure for an organisation to implement corporate social responsibility. A process in which a component of populace endeavours to become analogous to another component of the inhabitants functioning in the similar surroundings is isomorphism (DiMaggio & Powell, 1983). Correspondingly, modification of institutional practices by a firm is indicated as

isomorphism (Dillard, et al., 2004). There are three different types of isomorphic pressure generated by institutions, which are, coercive, normative and mimetic. These pressures can compel and convince an organisation to connect with the certain activity (DiMaggio & Powell, 1983).

“Coercive Isomorphism results from both formal and informal pressures exerted on organizations by other organizations upon which they are dependent and by cultural expectations in the society within which organizations function. Such pressures may be felt as force, as persuasive, or as invitations to join in collusion” (DiMaggio & Powell, 1983, p.150).

One of the examples of these intuitional pressures is when a Ghanaian firm name as Volta River Authority has disclose their CSR activity related to environment to obey the prerequisite of The World Bank (Rahaman, et al., 2004). Normative isomorphism indicates to firm’s implementation of method or practice by reason of the progression to socialise to obtain normative level (DiMaggio & Powell, 1983). The behaviour of managers is modelled by educational institutions, trade groups and proficient association which are three sources of normative isomorphism. Any corporation can adopt particular practice like transparency, training and development of workforce, charity and construction of educational institutes to achieve or maintain the normative status. Some organisations try to imitate the technique, system and methods of other profitable firms because of the improbability in the institutional environment is mimetic isomorphism. The aspects of memetic isomorphism are conventional in which a firm imitate practices of another. It happens when there is a scarcity or deficiency of some ambiguity in a firm like proper vision, aim and lack of comprehension of technology (DiMaggio & Powell, 1983). It is also possible that the pressure of competitors makes managers to imitate the practices including corporate social responsibility. Attraction of employees and good reput are some advantages generated by isomorphism. Corporations ordinarily embrace different practices for legality commitments instead for their definite effectiveness of practices (Carpenter & Feroz, 2001).

Moreover, it is difficult to differentiate amongst these pressures and can take place one or more at the similar time (DiMaggio & Powell, 1983; Unerman, 2000; Deegan & Unerman, 2011). In consequence, distinct intuitional situations can have impact on the association amongst organisations and its stakeholders (Marquis, et al., 2007; Oh, et al., 2011; DiMaggio & Powell,

1983). The approach and behaviour of a firm towards stakeholders is determined by the existence of efficient institution in the surroundings in which an organisation is functioning. Furthermore, institutional theory establishes standpoint of decoupling which represents to the circumstances in which the definite practices of a firm hold a different view from the formal practice of the same organisation (Dillard, et al., 2004). When a firm is decoupling, the definite practice of the organisation can establish imprecise objectives and show ritualistic examination of a firm to portray consistency with legal criterions (Kury, 2007). The notion of legitimacy theory in which an organisation practises societal activities for the modification of community to be recognised as accountable firm, is interconnected with decoupling. The discussion demonstrates that institutional theory is connexions with legitimacy theory. Although, the focus of investigation is not on decoupling of an organisation, therefore further details are not essential.

National level, issue level and industry level are the three level on which an institutional theory can be applied (DiMaggio & Powell, 1983; Matten & Moon, 2008; Jamali & Neville, 2011; Mezias, 1990). The environment of the institution which comprises education, political, economic system that can influence a firm to embrace societal activities, comes under national level. The industry field is indicated as the discipline of a corporation which includes all corporations which have comparable products and services with further elements like competitors, resources contributors and occupational collaborators (DiMaggio & Powell, 1983). The last one is level of issues which can be found instead industry (Bebbington, et al., 2009; Jamali & Neville, 2011). As occasionally, organisations embrace certain practices for charity or workforce because of societal pressure rather than because of predominant exercise in the corporation (Mezias, 1990). This particular investigation is related to a nation which is Pakistan and the CSR activities of the banks.

Hence, the institutional theory perspective give concentration to the association amongst a corporation and its surroundings. Regulatory, normative and cognitive are three types of institutions which can produce distinct pressures on an organisation to embrace certain exercise to be known as lawful corporation. Pakistani banks can adopt CSR activities, to retort to these pressures.

2.1.5 Part four: CSR and Financial Performance.

In order to achieve the objectives of this investigation it is essential to understand the concept of CSR and CFP. This section of the literature is including theories related to CSR and CFP, which provides better understanding of the concepts. Corporate social responsibility is mostly considered as an ethical and societal activity but it is also related to the FP of a firm. Many businesses in today's world are executing activities related to corporate social responsibility as organisational strategy to maximise the profits and to successful (Porter & Kramer, 2006). The notion is also famous among business communities and capitalists. One of the famous scholar Adam Smith presented the notion of invisible land, in early 70s. Moreover, the researcher has already have discussed in the above-mentioned section about the introduction and evolution of concept of corporate social responsibility. Any organisation makes decisions and practice on particular actions to achieve the financial goals. The idea of relationship between CSR and financial performance was clearly presented by Johnson in early 70s (Johnson, 1971.)

Furthermore, the organisations, which implements the deeds related to corporate social responsibility, can have additional benefits by increasing their profit. A number of researchers have discussed and argued about the association FP of the firm and between corporate social responsibilities. There are several models and theories, which shows the relationship between these two notions (Margolis and Walsh, 2001).

Some scholars have traditional view and consider that the societal activities are costly. For instance, an organisation has to take supplementary expenditure of charity, workforce benefits and environmental programs in consideration. These superfluous costs can decline or depreciate profitability and can give rise to competitive disadvantage (Alexander & Buchholz, 1978). The notion of corporate social responsibility is also supported Freeman (1984) stakeholder theory. However, the disgruntlement of stakeholders can possibly influence financial performance and can become a risk for the future of an organisation (Clarkson, 1995; Svendsen, 1998). Nevertheless, one of the main requirements for the fortification of bottom line is the corporate societal activities (Epstein & Rejc-Buhovac, 2014). Managers of an organisation has to consider individual and groups which means consider not only shareholders but with stake (Ruf, et al., 2001; Mele, 2008). If an organisation is engaged with CSR activities and able to manage it appropriately, it will become cause of satisfied stakeholders and will lead

to the increased financial performance (Galant & Cadez, 2017). For instance, repeat purchase of product will be increased if the customers are pleased. Similarly, motivation can make employees to work hard with dedication and for the enhancement of their performance; an organisation has to satisfy employees.

It is demonstrated in literature that there is both positive and negative association between CSR and financial performance. The foremost outcomes from the literature about the relationship of CSR and CFP is summarized as follow:

Table 2 The nature of CSR and CFP.

The nature of CSR and CFP relationship	References
Positive	<p>Al-Tuwaijri et al., 2004; Burnett & Hansen, 2008; Erhemjamts et al., 2013; Rodgers et al., 2013, Moskowitz,1972 Bragdon and Marlin, 1972 Moskowitz,1975 Paret and Eilbert, 1975 Belkaoui,1976 Heinze, 1976 Sturdivant and Ginter, 1977 Bowman, 1978 Ingram, 1978</p> <p>Fry, Keim, and Meiners,1982 Newgren et al., 1985 Rockness, Schlachter, and Rockness, 1986 Cowen, Ferreri, and Parker, 1987 Spencer and Taylor, 1987 Wokutch and Spencer, 1987 Morris, Rehbein, Hosseini, and Armacost,1990 Riahi-Belkaoui, 1992 Hart and Ahuja, 1994 Johnson and Greening, 1994</p>
Negative	<p>Baird, Geylani, & Roberts, 2012; Peng & Yang, 2014 Vance, 1975 Shane and Spicer, 1983 Wier, 1983 Jarrell and Peltzman, 1985 Pruitt and Peterson, 1986 Cross,1987, Davidson, Chandy, and Eckbo,1983 Shane and Spicer, 1983 Strachan, Smith, and Beedles, 1983 Davidson and Worrell,1988 Hoffer, Pruitt, and Reilly, 1988 Bromiley and Marcus, 1989</p>
No relationship	<p>Alexander & Buchholz, 1978; Aupperle et al., 1985; Soana, 2011; Sun, Salama, Hussainey, & Habbash, 2010; McWilliams & Siegel, 2000, Ingram and Frazier, 1983</p>

	Aupperle, Carroll, and Hatfield, 1985 Freedman and Jaggi, 1986, Alexander and Buchholz, 1978 Abbott and Monsen, 1979 Ingram and Frazier, 1983
U-shaped/inverted U-shaped	Barnett & Salomon, 2012; Bowman & Haire, 1975

(Galant & Cadez, 2017; Griffin & Mahon, 1997)

The table shows that some scholars accept that CSR can increase the financial performance and have positive impact on profitability. Corporate social responsibility is auspicious for shareholders because socially responsible investments have positive impact on shareholder value (Moser & Martin, 2012). In last few years, shareholders have started considering non-financial norms to make investment decisions. Investing in socially responsible investments can result in increased financial performance compared to other firms. Although, some scholars argue that these outstanding consequences vanish in long run. (Derwall, et al., 2011). One of the justifications is that organisations with socially responsible investment are less vulnerable to societal situations that often cause supplementary cost and damage organisation's reputation. For instance, the share prices of one of the famous clothing retailer H&M slumped because they exploited child labour in the production of their garments (Bengtsson, 2008; Butler, 2016; Tang, 2015; Pitel, 2016; Chamberlain, 2017).

On the other hand, some researchers indicated the negative association between CSR and CFP. The main outcomes argument pointed by scholars is that the societal accountabilities can increase the costs and deteriorate profitability. According to Friedman (1970), the main responsibility of a businessperson or an organisation is to increase profit (Zimmerli, et al., 2007; Robins, 2008; Galant & Cadez, 2017). Nevertheless, the conception of negative connexion amongst CSR and financial performance does not suggest the comprehensive relinquishment of societal accountable corporate deed. It is believed by a number of executives

to be a good corporate citizen but at the expenditure of shareholders (Moser & Martin, 2012; Galant & Cadez, 2017). Additionally, shareholders of a firm can also be moral and possibly necessitate activities related to societal deeds even at the detriment decreased economic performance (Mackey, et al., 2007).

Some intellectuals imply that there is no relationship between CSR and CFP and being socially accountable does not increase or decrease the profitability of an organisation. It indicates that both impact of CSR cancels each other. The final identified association amongst corporate social responsibility and financial performance is U-shaped. This conception explains if a firm has reasonable or moderate level of corporate social responsibility it will have lower financial performance whilst companies with less CSR will have high-level financial performance (Barnett & Salomon, 2012). Bowman and Haire (1975) also supported the notion of U-shaped association between CSR and CFP. It shows that firms with less and more CSR are linked with low financial performance but companies with unexceptional CSR is related to high CFP.

Moreover, the researcher has found that the nature of association between CSR and CFP has less evidence in literature. Several scholars have provided justification for these inconclusive definitions of relationship of corporate social responsibility and financial performance (Surroca, et al., 2010). One of the explanations of the questionable notion is the inadequate theoretic foundation (Ruf, et al., 2001). It also has the deficiency of clear path of connection and there is no focus on the measurement of the relationship (Waddock & Graves, 1997; Davidson & Worrell, 1990; Griffin & Mahon, 1997). Moreover, in specification of the model there is sampling inadequacies and the absence of appropriate variables (McWilliams & Siegel, 2001; Beurden & Gössling, 2008). The following figure illustrates the criticism on relationship between CSR and CFP.

Figure 11 CSR and FP Criticism

(Author's work.)

The detailed discussion of relationship between corporate social responsibility and financial performance is elucidated in the following sections of the research.

2.1.5.1 The Trade-off Hypothesis.

This concept or theory presents the adverse effects of corporate social responsibility on financial performance of an organisation (Preston & O'Bannon, 1997; Aupperle, et al., 1985 ; Ullmann, 1985). A number of authors and scholars have discussed this assumption that all the societal activities like charity, donations and investment on environmental issues can increase the cost of an organisation and it can become disadvantageous for a success of a corporation (Aupperle, et al., 1985). Henceforth, the organisations, which are proactive in activities related to corporate social responsibility, can have less or low financial performance than others.

Several scholars researched about this notion and claimed that organisations confront with trade-off between societal accountabilities and economic performance (McGuire, et al., 1990). Similarly, the corporation executing societal deeds adds the cost up by doing different investments. Sometime it seems to be disadvantageous for a business to implement social activity because it is not a responsibility of a businessperson to work for the betterment of

society. The main purpose to run a business is to increase the finances and gain the profits. Social responsibility may have negative effects on the finance of a corporation. For instance, if an organisation has invested on the charity for education in a country whilst their competitors do not add this cost to their finances. In the situation, the profit of the corporation involves with the activities related to corporate social responsibility will be less than others.

Moreover, it is also claimed by many researchers that the societal performance is sovereign variable and societal activities are comprising of expenditure (Friedman, 1962; Balabanis, et al., 1998; Barnea & Rubin, 2006). The additional expense, which can decrease the profits and it, is also possible that the share prices of an organisation goes down because of the wrong investment of the corporation (Preston & O'Bannon, 1997).

Furthermore, some scholars explain the relation of corporate social responsibility and finances as a burden and additional cost whilst some researchers argue about the deficiency of relationship between expenses and revenues of a corporation. It is also discussed that often it is not easy to identify the effects of corporate social responsibility on finances (Ullmann, 1985). The scholar also augmented that even if there are any changes in the revenue of the organisation, it is difficult to measure the association of that change with the corporate social responsibility. It is also possible that corporate social responsibility will have some impact of the finance of an organisation. However, to prove the impact of societal activities on profit gain by the company seems to be difficult (McWilliams & Siegel , 2001). The activities related to corporate social responsibility are intangible like the attention of consumer, which is incomprehensible to measure. It is very challenging for an organisation to relate social deeds with bottom-line benefits. The brand image and reputation of a corporation may have some impact, as consumers will notice it. Nevertheless, it is problematic to demonstrate the exact linkage between social activities and profit. Direct return and revenue generated by executing these activities is convoluted to recognise.

The researcher believes that it is important for Pakistani banks to generate profit, but CSR can be advantageous and will increase their repute. This study investigates about the CSR impact on CFP in Pakistani banks. Does CSR have positive or negative impact on CFP of Pakistani banks? Therefore, it was important to use the above-mentioned approach as results can be negative or positive.

2.1.5.2 Social Impact Hypothesis.

Social impact hypothesis is related to stakeholder theory and argues that if an organisation does not fulfil the expectations of the shareholders, it may have to confront with the risk of increase of anxiety in the share market and can cause higher cost to the organisation (Cornell & Shapiro, 1987). Therefore, it is important for Pakistani banks to recognise the responsibility of stakeholder group, which can have great impact on financial performance. Stakeholders can enhance the image and reputation of an organisation. The hypothesis focuses on the concern related to the societal activities. The stakeholder theory and social impact hypothesis emphasize on the same thing, which is the positive effect of stakeholders on company's finances (Preston & O'Bannon, 1997). Moreover, organisations engaged with corporate social responsibility can have better expert employees and can attract more consumers.

The positive social impact on the financial performance can be achieved by Pakistani banks by promoting positive attitude towards stakeholders. Different mechanisms are presented for the positive connexion between CSR and CFP (Ferrell, et al., 2002).

- **Investors:** When it comes to investment in any firm, the one of the key elements noticed by investors is CSR. Pakistani banks who are engaged with CSR have great access to the financial markets and it can fascinate investors.
- **Regulatory agencies:** Pakistani banks who are practicing CSR can attain better circumstances to manage to work as a part of a community. There is a possibility of restriction and resistance confronted by the organisation, if the company is not involving with CSR. The resistance from the community can make work environment difficult for the organisation, which can affect the financial performances.
- **Customers:** Moreover, product differentiation in customers' perception is one of the impacts of engaging with CSR. Some customers are precise about the environmental and societal problems; their decision of buying any product can have great effect of CSR practicing by the company. Market position of the bank and the sales of products can proliferate through CSR.
- **Employees:** The high participation of corporate social responsibility can attract proficient workforces with high level of dedication and devotion towards the

organisation. This loyalty of the employees can result in the better organisational performance and productivity, which leads to the enhanced financial performance.

2.1.5.3 Non-linear Relationship.

The correlation amongst cost and benefit is challenging to establish and it is always indistinct that the similar association embraces throughout the scale (Bowman & Haire, 1975). Many scholars have indicated that the association amongst societal and financial performance are not straightforward monotonic plot but an inverted U-shaped curve that means change in one entity cannot ensure the persistent change in another (Bowman & Haire, 1975; Sturdivant & Ginter, 1977; Nollet, et al., 2016; Moore, 2001).

It is also noticed by Bowman and Haire, (1975) that the financial performance of an organisation is related to two opposite forces which are the expense of engaging with societal activities and the advantages of it. One of the challenging tasks is to empirically measure the relationship of profit and the social activities of an organisation.

Bowman and Haire indicated about the opposing forces:

"That it is challenging to assess the volume and value of an organisation's actions in the field of societal accountabilities. A specified analysis of what percentage of a societal action have to be indicted to accountable deeds and what, in any case, is the marginal cost and advantage of such action is hard to find." (Bowman & Haire, 1975, p. 49)

Many other scholars have also found that the financial performances and societal accountabilities are in inverted U-shaped curve (Sturdivant & Ginter, 1977). It is not essential that if an organisation is more active in societal actions will certainly achieve better financial performance.

These previous studies were reviewed by many other scholars like Ullmann (1985) and he reaffirmed Bowman and Haire (1975) indicated that some of the findings were vague. He

observed that generally all earlier studies were obscure and leading towards U-shaped association (Ullmann, 1985).

Several intellectuals have depicted different notions depending on the outcome of U-shaped correlation. Moore (2001) presented a theory, which was recommended to endorse the non-linear model and which will endorse the negative and positive impact theories and their effect (Moore, 2001). Similarly, Mc Williams and Siegel (2001) proposed another theory on the foundation of supply and demand theory. It explains that the companies produce social performance put puts will be in direct proportion with the demands by company shareholders to reach to the high level of profit (McWilliams & Siegel, 2001).

2.1.5.4 The Unified Theory.

One of the theories, which explicates a non-linear association amongst CSR and financial performance, is the unified theory (Marom, 2006). This theory presents a structure for explaining the inverted U-shaped relation between financial performance and CSR. The Unified theory is a development of Sturdivant and Ginter (1977) and Bowman and Haire (1975) theory. An organisation operates in domain of business and CSR equally to attain the profit. Social output also known as social products are comparable to the fundamental product of corporate domain. The utility of stakeholders increases with the level of societal productivity obtained. The main belief of the unified theory is that CSR can be examined as a source of products that are presented indirectly to stakeholders by an organisation. Societal products concentrate the requirement and anticipations of different stakeholder communities (Donaldson & Preston, 1995). It is also being affirmed by scholars that social products are particular output which has intention to fulfil requirement of stakeholders (McWilliams & Siegel, 2001). Consequently, stakeholders are considered as a category of customers gaining advantages from the social products generated by an organisation.

Nevertheless, an organisation has to invest in different resources to participate in activities related to CSR, which are considered as the cost of expenses (Vance, 1975; McGuire, et al., 1988; Barnea & Rubin, 2006). A cost benefit analysis is one of the appropriate methods to analyse the outcomes of expenditure on the social activities (McWilliams & Siegel, 2001). Societal responsibilities, which have intention to gratify the stakeholders, will be revised with numerous advantages to the final total of an accounts sheet of an organisation (Donaldson &

Preston, 1995; Preble, 2005). Moreover, McWilliam and Siegel, (2001) presented a delineate supply and demand model of corporate social responsibility in which they utilised cost benefit analysis. It is also indicated by them that an organisation can achieve maximum profit by both, main company's product and societal products. The production of social products is dependent on the distinctive demand for corporate social performance of an organisation's experience. The profit can be maximised by an organisation, when producing optimal level of CSR.

The unified theory considered stakeholders as equal to consumers and the outcomes of societal activities as social products (Marom, 2006). The cost of the consequences of social activities and benefits attained by an organisation from contented stakeholders are also addressed by the unified theory. The reward gained by an organisation and the cost on CSR, both are addressed by unified theory. Consequently, the theory brings together two preceding philosophies, which are the social impact hypothesis (emphasis on meeting stakeholder requirements) and the trade hypothesis (focuses on the cost of societal deeds). The unified theory describes all probable associations amongst corporate social responsibility and financial performance. The theory consists of two elements 'M' which represents the number of stakeholders and 'N' which represents number of societal outcomes. Barnea and Rubin (2005) presented a decreased marginal utility notion, which indicates that the relationship can be positive, negative or neutral varying on the cost, which can be higher or lower than rewards. Consequently, the association is complicated and can fluctuate between positive and negative.

2.1.5.5 Resource-Based View.

The belief that an organisation has different resources, abilities and proficiencies which allows them to attain success and provide competitive advantage is named as resource-based view (Barney, 1991; Greening & Turban, 2000). The resources of an organisation can be tangible and intangible that include human resource, assets, competences, organizational processes, organisation's qualities, intelligence and knowledge. If Pakistani banks have capability to safeguard their resources from replication or replacement, it can sustain competitive advantage for the long term (Barney, 1991; Peteraf, 1993). This is the vital managerial task to identify the potential of the organisation and to analyse that all the resources are completing the criteria, which is usually named as VRIO -valuable, rare, non- imitable and organisational orientation (Barney, 1991; Moorhead & Griffin, 1997; Zanoni, 2011).

In resource-based view, the valuable means that the organisation's resources are indispensable and assist organisation to implement strategies for effective performance. The second element, rare indicates that resources are not communal by competitors. The third element elucidates that resources cannot replicated by competitors and the not easy to substituted. The last one in VRIO is the organisational orientation, which implies the capabilities in organisation. These skills or abilities can make all other resource productive (Zott, 2003). It suggests that resources of an organisation are value, which enable a firm to achieve an opportunity by reducing the cost and threats by competitors (Newbert, 2008; Barney, 1991). Barney (1986) argues that the competitive position of an organisation is directly connected to the ownership of the resources (Zanoni, 2011). CSR can influence the financial performance of Pakistani banks, is often explained by many scholars with the assistance of resource-based view. The theoretical perspective of RBV emanates from the corporate domain, unlike the social impact hypothesis and stakeholder management, which developed from the societal domain.

The resource based view of an organisation presents theoretical prospect to explicate that participating in CSR can enhance the financial performance of the firm as it identifies the significance of the intangible resources for instance organisational culture, repute (Teece, 1980; Barney, 1986; Hall, 1992). Additionally, intangible resources of an organisation can be influenced by the deeds or actions of societal accountabilities (Husted & Allen, 2001). An organisation can develop intangible proficiencies by using societal accountabilities acts and one of the best examples is human resources (Greening & Turban, 2000; Orlitzky, et al., 2003). If the human resource of Pakistani banks is active, it can take numerous forms under societal accountability comprising employees training, development, employees' benefits, societal benefits and safe working environment. The human resource competences can have great effect of actions concerned with environmental deeds. Higher corporate reputation of an organisation becomes one of the reasons of increased workforces' motivation, which contributes to the CFP (Waddock & Graves, 1997).

Moreover, corporate reputation is one of the societal accountability actions by which an organisation can develop intangible proficiencies (Russo & Fouts, 1997). Pakistani banks can reduce their vulnerability to coercions or threats by reducing societal gap and CSR activities can assists firms to minimize the distance between community and organisation (Carroll, 2016). If an organisation can manage to build the reputational capital, it can influence

company's profit and corporate reputation can provide competitive advantage, which ensures the growth or development of an organisation (Olmedo-Cifuentes & Martínez-León, 2014; Roberts & Dowling, 2002; Sabate & de Quevedo Puente, 2003; Srivastava, et al., 1997; Cravens & Oliver, 2006). CSR programs can create positive repute or esteem for an organisation and have ability of offering extensive fortification to company's corporate reputation (Carroll, 2016). Positive repute can be built with stakeholders (customers, suppliers, investors, creditors, employees and community) by societal engagements. Skilled employees and access to capital can be attain by Pakistani banks by involvement of high CSR (Greening & Turban, 2000; Carroll, 2016).

2.1.5.6 CSR and Net Profit.

Revenues excluding all the expenses is net profit of any organisation. Any firm displays its net profit after subtracting taxes and interest on the profit. The motivations for contributing in corporate social responsibility are explained by utilising Carroll's pyramid of CSR (Miles & Munilla, 2005). The pyramid consists four diverse levels of devotion towards corporate social responsibility. According to Carroll (1991), the first stage of the pyramid is legal, that an organisation participates in corporate social responsibility to obligate the rule and regulation of a certain state or country. The second stage is economic, CSR being use by company to gain competitive advantage and enhance financial performance. The last two stages are ethical and philanthropic that a firm use CSR to maintain the equilibrium amongst the profit and community. This demonstrates that the philosophy behind using CSR can be compliance driven, profit driven, driven by the caring. Numerous researchers argue that an organisation can attain advantages by engaging with societal activities (Idowu & Pappasolomou, 2007). There are several reasons and motivations behind an organisation participating in CSR. Some organisations engage with societal activities to have good impression in perception of customers, investors and suppliers. Improvement of reputation and brand management are also one of the intentions of firms engaging in CSR. Moral obligations, reputation, and sustainability are the benefits, which becomes inspiration for an organisation (Kotler & Lee, 2005; Kramer & Porter, 2006)

Additionally, the reputation of an organisation is associated and has great impact on the financial performance (McGuire, et al., 1988; Sarbutts, 2003). It is also accepted and explicated by other scholars that if a firm participates in corporate social as a result of enlightened self-

regard while CSR is considered to heighten the brand image thus increase the financial performance (Malik & Nadeem, 2014; Balabanis, et al., 1998). Nevertheless, every scholar has different understanding and belief; therefore, there are distinct outcomes from the earlier studies of CSR impact on financial performance. McGurie et al. (1988) have divided the association amongst CSR and CFP into three different perceptions, summarised from earlier studies. The first perspective is that the organisations with more CSR investment have more economic impairment than the less accountable one. The next view is that cost of precise CSR activities is marginal and organisations engaging with corporate social responsibility gain advantages for instance increase in workforce efficiency and production. The last notion is that the expenditure on societal activities are substantial but it is compensated by reduction in other organisation expenses. Previous studies show that an organisation has to gratify not only shareholders but also all stakeholders. Several researchers imply the positive connection between corporate social responsibility and financial performance. The progress in employees and willingness of customers towards product purchase are other effects of CSR (Davis, 1973). Any organisation with high societal activities confronts with less issues relate to employees or labour and have positive inclination of customers to the products. If company decidedly engage with CSR, the reputation of a company gets stronger with crucial constituencies as government bureaucrats, shareholders, financiers and bankers. The developed or enhanced association with these constituencies can be lucrative for the company. The researcher agrees with observations by different scholars indicates that the investors do consider societal activities in making the decision of financing (Spicer, 1978; Malik & Nadeem, 2014).

2.1.5.7 Measuring Corporate Social Responsibility.

Every organisation has different societal activities including environmental pollution, charity, child labour, health, and safety, which often comprehended as beyond the conventional limitations of business. Consequently, measuring the economic performance of an organisation is straightforward and uncomplicated process whilst measuring social performance is challenging (Balch, 2011; Mellahi, 2013). There are different ways of measuring corporate social responsibility and two of them are used in this research are elucidated below.

2.1.5.8 Accounting-Based Performance Measures.

The first measure in this research to measure CSR is ‘accounting based measure’. It is indicated by the name that this measure is established on accounting practice of economic reporting of a firm. Every organisation presents annual report that includes the accounting based financial reporting. An annual report of an organisation gives historical perception of financial accomplishment of the firm.

It is explicated in the above literature that a number of scholars and researchers have presented different models and theories to explore the association amongst CSR and financial performance (Griffin & Mahon, 1997; Orlitzky, et al., 2003; Preston & O’Bannon, 1997; Margolis & Walsh, 2003; McGuire, et al., 1988; McWilliams & Siegel, 2001).

Moreover, return on equity (ROE), return on assets (ROA), return on net income (earning), return on sale (ROS) and return on investment (ROI) are the core indicators to measure economic performance through accounting-based measure. These indicators are used by organisations to evaluate the financial performance of a year or for multi-year performance. Return on Equity (ROE) is assessed by net income and it indicates the productivity of a company by determining the return of investors. Return on assets (ROA) contemplates the assets consumption of an organisation and it is evaluated by using the net assets of a company. The next measuring gauge is return on sales (ROS) which reflects the profit margin of a company that achieved by collection commodities and it is assessed by the net sales of the company. Accounting based measure signifies preceding financial performance of an organisation and consequently procedures must be utilised if the research design implies the previous or history of financial performance of an organisation. Several previous studies noticed that many researchers used accounting-based measure in justification of association amongst corporate social responsibility and financial performance (Griffin & Mahon, 1997; Margolis & Walsh, 2003). A number of researchers in business discipline when investigating at the precedent ages to evaluate the association between corporate social responsibility and financial performance, it is expected that they decided on accounting-based measure. Additionally, the extensively exercised or implemented measures to assess the key aspects of economic performance are return on assets (ROA) and return on equity (ROE) (Moore, 2001; Margolis & Walsh, 2003).

For instance, Preston and O'Bannon (1997) used numerous accounting-based measure for financial performance embracing of ROA and ROE. Similarly, Griffin and Mahon (1997), also utilised six different measures to evaluate the economic performance which was comprised of return of sales ROA and ROE. In the same way, six different measures for financial performance including asset ratio, total sale and return on consumed by scholars (Waddock & Graves, 1997).

However, many researchers in their studies use accounting-based measure, which includes the admired and straightforward measures ROE and ROA. Nevertheless, some scholars used supplementary measures, which were precise to framework of their investigation.

2.1.5.9 Market-Based Measures of Financial Performance.

The second instrument to measure the financial performance is market-based measure. As it is understood by, the name that market based measure is established on the market index (Amit & Livant, 1988). One of the expectations of the shareholders is the prices of stock market to the forthcoming value of the organisation. Consequently, the approach of market-based measure is progressive and future orientated (Baysinger & Hoskisson, 1989; Rowe & Morrow, 1999). The prices of shares, earnings' prices that is called P/E ratio are the highly commonly utilised financial measure (Griffin & Mahon, 1997). The price to earnings ratio is price of a share of the organisation, which depends on the profit gain by the company per share. If any company has high price to earnings ratio it means that the financers are giving additional for every part of revenue. The P/E ratio is also known as "earnings multiple" and many analysts utilised this ratio. The earning yield is a reciprocal for P/E ratio.

$$\text{P/E ratio} = \text{Price per Share} / \text{Earning per Share}$$

The explanation of above mentioned is that price per earnings ratio is equal to price of the particular market share divided by the earning of the company per share, which is the net income.

Additionally, it has been observed that in previous few years, many organisations are using different and contemporary measure of financial performance, which are market value added and economic value added. The divergence amongst the market value of the debt and equity

and capital employed in the organisation is market value added. It is the total of the all capital demanded together with the market value of debt and equity. Economic value added is explained as the net profit of a firm excluding a suitable rate for the opportunity cost of all capital. It is the evaluation accurate financial performance. On other hand, market value added is the distinction amongst the entire capital engaged in the corporation and the market value of the debt and equity.

Several scholars have concentrated to provide the reasons behind the use of market-based measure (Griffin & Mahon, 1997; Margolis & Walsh, 2003). The market-based measure of financial performance is forward contemplating and therefore if the study relates to the anticipations of imminent performances of an organisation, it is one of the appropriate measures to utilise (Margolis & Walsh, 2003). Consequently, the measure of financial performance has to be future orientated to look ahead and correspond to the anticipation of the stakeholders established on the acquaintance that the company is presently involve with high level corporate social responsibilities.

Market based measures are used by researchers to measure the financial performance like McGuire et al. (1988) supported them and specified that market-based measures are less vulnerable. In addition, they indicated that market-based measures are consistent because they signify the combined perception of financiers' assessment of the capability of an organisation to produce future financial profits.

Less accuracy and lack of trust are the foremost denunciation on the utilisation of market-based measures (Vance, 1975; Ullmann, 1985; Shane & Spicer, 1983). It has also been demonstrated by researchers that the use of market-based measures generates distinct outcomes (Vance, 1975). The market base measure is not suitable to utilise because they may be evaluating further than the economic results of a firm (Shane & Spicer, 1983). It is also argued to criticise the market-based measure that the use of it can only focus on the valuations of financiers towards the organisation which is not objective (Ullmann, 1985).

To counterbalance the downsides of the market-based measures, it is proposed by researchers to consume them alongside another accounting-based measures (Griffin & Mahon, 1997). A number of researchers used market-based measure with accounting-based measure of financial performance in their research (Verschoor, 1998). Hence, if numerous different measures are

utilised, they balance the weakness of every separate measure and becomes a cause of relevant and trustworthy results (Griffin & Mahon, 1997). A number of researchers used combined measure for the financial performance that is contemporary market-based measures with accounting-based measures (Verschoor, 1998; Hillman & Keim, 2001; Webley & More, 2003; Firer & Williams, 2003). The analysis amongst the association between the moral accountability of an organisation to its economic performance was discussed by Verschoor in 1988. Similarly, Webley and More (2003), utilised blend of different measures in their investigation to measure financial performance which includes price earnings ratio, market value added and return on capital.

2.1.6 Part five: Banking and CSR.

This section of the literature includes banking and CSR which provides understanding of the activities related to CSR in banking sector. Finances are the most crucial part in an organisation and can have great influence on the financial sustainability of the firm and corporate social responsibility (Scholtens, 2006). Banks are economic agents that offer financial amenities including transformation of assets and keeping an eye on the debtors alongside vast effect on society (Coulson & Monks, 1999; Allen & Santomero, 2001). In economic development of a country banks plays imperative role and have huge effect on the sustainable progression of organisation and society (Stubbs & Cocklin, 2007). Almost, every bank in today's era in engage with corporate social responsibility and helps with the development of society. The World Bank enthusiastically participate in CSR and also promotes it by providing trainings (Jenkins, 2005).

Moreover, it has been analysed by researchers that many international banks have policies on corporate social responsibility. For instance, a research shows that in North America and Europe most of banks have CSR policies and the reporting of CSR has surged between 2000 and 2005. (Scholtens, 2009). The investigation by Scholtens 2009, elucidated that the banks in United Kingdom and France have the greatest involvement of CSR. He provided four categories of gauges of societal accountability of bank which are:

- (1) Codes of ethics, sustainability reporting, and environmental management systems*
- (2) Environmental management*
- (3) Responsible financial products*
- (4) Social conduct (Scholtens, 2009; Bryson, et al., 2016).*

The banks economic products which are accountable in societal context, are the main indicator in sustainable advancement and therefore, it is important for banks to create cognizance of environmental policies which can assist to resolve environmental concerns. Thus, consumers can consider the environmental performance of the bank and can value the effort of protecting environment. It is proclaimed by numerous researchers that one of the gradually emergent concern in transnational banking industry is corporate social responsibility. It seems that CSR is implanted in the business strategy of banks (Stulz & Williamson, 2003). However, the banking sector act quite late to challenges of corporate social responsibility by taking account of environmental then the societal concerns.

The stakeholders of banks are employees, investors, customers, shareholders, supervisors and the owner. In contrast to other sectors, banks have foremost quality of attracting and huge number of individuals and can have great impact on them. Therefore, it is categorised by extremely rigorous guideline and regulations to ensure the steadiness of the banks (Yamak & Sürer, 2005). The CSR practises of banking sectors are unlike other financial sectors which includes investment, borrowing money, anti-corruption efforts and resolution of issues related to money laundering. Although, banks do not have direct effect on the environment but if they provide grant to a firm which becomes the cause of increased pollution or harm humans, can result in serious destructions (Idowu & Filho, 2009; Thompson & Cowton, 2004). Banks are an intermediary entity and their decisions can have great effects on the consumers and suppliers.

The CSR pyramid by Carroll (1991), is the widely acceptable definition of CSR. The application of the pyramid in terms of Pakistani banking sector are elucidated as follow:

Economic Responsibility. It is the responsibility of the Pakistani bank to increase the profitability and growth. Banks create different prospects to manage the risk as the interests of people and organisations performance changes on constant basis. Pakistani Banks should also focus on innovation of the products and maintains the relationship with the stakeholders.

Legal responsibility. Pakistani Banks should always endeavour to minimise the risk by completing all the legal responsibilities. All the regulations are defined by statutes and there are several acts to conform for instance, accounts tax compliance act and consumer protection act.

Ethical responsibility. The morality of individual are the ethical norms which also embraces the anticipation of the stakeholders. Pakistani banks have to create the transparency and emphasis on the fundamental principle of integrity. In stakeholder dialogue, moral and virtuous values are the highly noticeable.

Philanthropic responsibility. This responsibility is one of the voluntary societal activity by Banks. It has become highly practiced activity by banks to conserve the repute of the economic sector. The stakeholders of Pakistani banks expect secure products, apposite communication, safe work environment, admiration of human dignity and transparency. The banks have to consider their direct and indirect decisions’ impacts on environment (Thompson & Cowton, 2004)

There are different activities related to societal accountabilities practices by numerous banks for instance through low income banking, many banks offer micro-loan programme (Chiu, 2014). Some of the business and non-business activities of banks are elucidated in the following table.

Table 3 CSR Activities of Bank

Business Activities	Non-business Activities
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evolving economic learning and understanding, risk management, cautious lending • Transparent services • Ethical behaviour with stakeholders • Providing finances for Environment protection • Preventing corruption • Providing assistance to special clients • Offering student loans 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Funding NGOs • Charities • Providing assistance to special social group • Encouragement of sports and arts • Providing equal job opportunities • Supporting local communities • Offering apposite work environment

(Author’s work)

Although the above table demonstrates the business and non-business CSR activities of banks, but the researcher believes that these all activities are interconnected and it is important for an organisation to consider them. Several researchers agree that the decisions of any business should be under consideration of economic and societal interest because it is a moral accountability of an organisation (Barclift, 2012). The researcher believes that for Pakistani banks CSR is an extensive conception that depicts corporate accountability to interact with society in a collectively responsible manner (Vogel, 2006; Werther & Chandler, 2010). CSR is acknowledged internationally and many organisations are using CSR as their business strategy. For instance, United Nations and World Business Council on sustainable development encompass CSR and offer assistance to organisations for the establishment of CSR (Mintzberg, et al., 2002; Boeger, et al., 2008).

Moreover, CSR can contribute to a competitiveness of Pakistani banks through different modes. The legitimacy of Pakistani banks is embedded not only in their economic performance but also in their decent repute amongst stakeholders. It includes general impression that stakeholders have established about the features, values and behaviour of the bank. The researcher of the study believes that in banking sector reputation of the bank plays an important role. Once bank has lost its trust of community, it will be difficult to manage. The reputational risk can have adverse impacts on the ability of banks. As it indicated that

“reputational risk depends on the —negative perception on the part of customers, counterparties, shareholders, investors or regulators that can adversely affect a bank's ability to maintain existing, establish new, business relationships and continue access to sources of funding [..]” (Basel Committee , 2017. , p. 19).

From the strategic perspectives, act in accordance with CSR does not eliminate banks from their financial role (Porter & Kramer, 2006). CSR can help Pakistani banks to be different from their competitors and improve perception of their customers. Particularly, when socially oriented stakeholders assess the CSR participation of banks (Pérez & del Bosque, 2015). Additional factor of competitiveness for Pakistani banks related to CSR can be found in motivation (Asrar-ul-Haq, et al., 2017). However, CSR is expensive and it can put banks into disadvantage compared to others who are not involved in CSR (McWilliams & Siegel , 2001).

2.1.6.1 CSR and Bank Lending Decisions.

The above discussion demonstrates that banks are accountable for managing risk and they increase value by providing economic services to borrowers and depositors (Scholtens, 2006; Merton, 1995). Banks consider the environmental effects as part of their risk management practice and decisions of investments (Coulson & Monks, 1999; Weber, et al., 2008). Banks are more concerned for the lending risk and evasion of payment by borrowers. Therefore, they prefer to reject lending money in uncertain conditions. According to the study by US banks in 1994, to preclude the lending for environmental accountabilities banks had modified their policies and that industrial credit businesses were enduring environmental evaluation (Coulson & Monks, 1999). A number of banks decline to finance companies which cause harm to the environment by increasing pollution.

Additionally, study by Salmon Brothers (1995), demonstrated that banks are using environmental loan evaluation methods and embraced conservational controlling practices (Weber, et al., 2008). Previous inaccuracies by banks have made them realise and they started considering environmental risk as an important element of financing evaluation procedure (Dasgupta S, et al., 2002; Coulson & Monks, 1999). Lender liability, constrictions on deeds of borrower and liability of borrower are the most affected areas by conservational guidelines (Mazzocco, 1991).

In credit risk assessment, the International Finance Corporation and World Bank have issued the comprehensive regulations for assimilating environmental evaluation which focus on the responsibility of the sponsor to determine an adequate process of financing (IFC, 1998). Several banks are embracing environmental programmes for instance more than 200 financial institutions have partnership with United Nations Environment Programme-finance Initiative to encourage a sustainable world (Kulkarni, 2010; UNEP, 2018).

2.1.6.2 CSR in Developing Countries.

The concept of corporate social responsibility is extensively practiced in developed countries and a number of organisations are encouraging societal activities. For instance, Lego has

recently introduced its first plant based plastic toy pieces to contribute to the environment as the material of the product is sustainable and safe for children (Smithers, 2018). Corporate social responsibility has obtained a lot of attention from scholars and researchers have worked on its awareness and reactions. However, maximum number of researches are conducted in perspective of developed countries. It is being observed that in contrast of developed countries, the recognition and implementation of corporate social responsibility is of reduced amount in emerging countries (Sriramesh, et al., 2007). In Asian countries, the emphasis of CSR literature is growing including China, India and Pakistan. Asia has heterogeneous approaches towards participation and implementation of CSR because of diverse socio-economic conditions and cultural norms (Chapple & Moon, 2005; Sriramesh, et al., 2007).

Consequently, different countries have diverse techniques and methods of executing corporate social responsibilities (Bronn & Vrioni, 2001). Since perception of corporate social responsibility is distinctive, a revised version of Carroll's model of CSR pyramid is presented by scholar Visser (2006). The emerging countries has given Philanthropic element second main precedence after economic, legal and ethical accountabilities. There is a direct association amongst encouragement of societal activities and religion for customers (Ramasamy, et al., 2010). Moreover, the purpose of concentrating on studies related to corporate social responsibilities in emerging countries are presented by Visser (2008)

- In emerging countries, societal and conservational calamities are generally intensely experienced in the world (UNDP, 2006)
- These countries have intense societal and environmental influence on corporation's actions, monetary progress, investments and globalisation.
- Emerging countries have the most productive growth market and they signify the escalating economy (IMF, 2006).
- They have distinguishing list of challenges relate to corporate social responsibility which are dissimilar to the developing countries' challenges.

Scholars have contended that one of the most imperative drivers for corporate social responsibility in emerging countries is globalisation (Chambers, et al., 2003). According to Khanna (2004), many multinational organisations have indicated the strain to develop their

criteria of CSR to evaluate the expectancy of their stakeholders, in order to remain competitive (May, et al., 2007).

In Asia, there have been a number of ventures have specific guidelines and strategies to finance or invest only in organisations with good implement of corporate social responsibility (Cheung, et al., 2010). Furthermore, it is also contended that to attain the return on investment and to maintain the portfolio of financing, many financiers are focusing on ethical insinuations that comprehend religious, conservational and societal elements. The market of Asian countries has established as an extraordinary intensification in financing in societal accountabilities (Laufer, 2003). It is indicated by researchers that Asian organisations are struggling and fall behind in executing CSR unlike developed countries (Ang, 2000; Low, 2004). However, Asian organisations do have focus on some CSR policies like concerns related to labour and union but have less concentration on other issues (Welford & Frost, 2006). In contrast, western countries organisations also give importance to transparency and equal opportunity to employees (Welford, 2004).

Some countries in Asia have less consciousness and implementation of CSR than others, for instance, Singapore have high level of appreciation and awareness of CSR as compare to Malaysia (Ramasamy & Ting, 2004). It is also suggested by scholars in their investigation related to dissimilarity of perception of corporate social responsibility between business students, that economic responsibilities are of great concern for Chinese whilst Indian gives more significance to philanthropic accountabilities (Wong, et al., 2009)

The implementation of CSR is growing slowly in Asian countries (Cheung, et al., 2010), but the investigation into literature of CSR is still limited. There is very smaller amount of work has done on the research of developing corporate social responsibility in developing countries. Although, the perception of corporate social responsibility is imperative for emerging countries than developed or progressed countries (Baughn, et al., 2007; Khan, et al., 2015). The societal good, which can be provided by strong constituencies and institutions, are appears to be insufficient in developing countries (Samy, et al., 2015). Furthermore, these countries, like Pakistan and Bangladesh, also lack in following the rules and regulations (for example paying taxes) assigned by the government (Sajjad & Eweje, 2014). It is categorically difficult to engage an organisation in activities related to social responsibilities when they do not even fulfil their licit accountabilities (Jamali & Mirshak , 2007; Khan & Lund-Thomsen, 2011).

Nevertheless, numerous companies are taking initiative and working hard to become a part of societal issues. One of the good example of these type of organisations is ‘Nyankamawu’ which created a solar power project to help farm, schools and hospitals with no electricity (Fleming, 2016). According to Chambers et al, 2003, more than half of Indian organisations whilst in Indonesia a quarter of organisations are involve with CSR activities (Brich & Moon, 2004). Hence, Asian organisations are taking part and becoming more active in CRS initiatives and the concept of CSR is escalating. It demonstrates that in new era, corporate social reponsibility plays eminent role in decision and choices made by any corporation (Baughn, et al., 2007; Hess, et al., 2002). It seems that the trend of involving or engaging with societal responsibilities are also increasing in developing countries, but a number of corporations in Pakistan are still lacking behind and need more attention and focus.

Pakistan is a democratic and one of the emergent countries but it has insubstantial economy and numerous complications within society. Therefore, there is a need of CSR implementation by distinct corporations in the country. According to Waheed 2005, the perception of CSR activities is still new to several companies within the country and a number of corporations pay less attention towards societal deeds (Sajjad & Eweje, 2014). It appears that the ignorance of CSR by organisations in Pakistan is high and they have less awareness of the concept. Often the concept of CSR is misunderstood by business entities, as they consider CSR as only philanthropic activities. The emphasis of CSR activities is not only making donations but it also requires the dedication of the corporation towards society, environment and the shared value offered to the stakeholders.

Corporations in Pakistan have pronounced aptitude, which can utilise efficiently to be a part of movements related to progress of the society (Ali, et al., 2010). Accountabilities, in relation to society and the consequences of CSR implementation are still disregarded by various successful business entities in Pakistan. Nevertheless, corporations do charity and offer money to resolve the concerns associated physical conditions and edification or education (Ali, et al., 2010). Additionally, the population of Pakistan as a consumer are also less aware of the eminent role played by CSR, plus the actual concept or philosophy of CSR is not fully comprehended by a number of corporations (Ehsan & Kaleem, 2012).

According to Naeem and Welford 2009, in Pakistani and Bangladeshi organisations, the concept of corporate social responsibility is not entirely established (Sajjad & Eweje, 2014).

Several corporations in these countries are not executing any movement related to CSR, even child labour and corruption are not considered to be solved instantaneously. However, multinationals in developing countries are established and have better understanding of activities related to societal responsibilities. For example, in Pakistan, Unilever has started Unilever Sustainable Living Plan, which emphasis on reduction of the effects of their products on environment for better physical conditions and good health (Shahid, 2012).

Scholars have compared developing countries with developed ones and investigated their CSR positions. It has also been noticed by many researchers that the position of Pakistan in executing CSR activities is less than British, American and European organisations (Baughn, et al., 2007). The progress of the country is dependent on the political and economic conditions which also have association with the practice of CSR in an organisation. The economic development of Pakistan is low which can be a factor of less awareness of activities related to society within organisations.

2.1.6.3 State of CSR in Pakistan.

The idea of corporate social responsibility is moderately fresh in Pakistan, however the fascination towards knowledge of CSR is gradually increasing. In emergent countries, for the determination of long-term persistence companies use CSR as a fundamental component of their business strategy. Nonetheless, in Pakistan many organisations pay no attention to corporate social responsibility and also unable to comprehend the true essence of it (Waheed, 2005). In various organisations of the country the notion of corporate social responsibility has been confused with philanthropic activities including rights and low of workforce and (Waheed, 2005; Khan, 2012). The business experts are mostly unaware about the actions, accountabilities and consequences of CSR on their businesses (Khan, 2012). Common people in the country are less cognisant about the role of commercial sector in society whilst businesses also have dearth of acquaintance about the exact conception of CSR (Ehsan & Kaleem, 2012). It is necessary to comprehend the corporate social responsibility is not only charity or philanthropic actions but the dedication to a comprehensive array of accountabilities throughout financial, societal, and conservational or environmental consequences to dispense mutual value to stakeholders of the company. CSR activities are diverse from philanthropy which does not contain any formulating and implementation of initiative for improvement and

advancement of the society (Mahapatra & Visalaksh, 2011). It is contended by scholars that CSR proffers ahead of the random act of munificence to embrace such conventional values as giving taxes, public disclosure, consumers compassion and values of workforce. Consequently, the lawfulness of philanthropic obligations by organisations may be condemned for the reason of ineffective responsibilities and pellucidity unambiguousness or transparency concerns at the implementation stage (Mahapatra & Visalaksh, 2011). It demonstrates that the concept of CSR has all-inclusive nature which contains determined strategy for all stakeholders of a company. An organisation has to consider internal policies while executing CSR like fortification of environment, power proficiency and improvement of environmental management system. In Pakistan, there are no particular rules and regulations related to corporate social responsibility which can safeguard the moral acquiescence and as an outcome CSR is merely implement on an intended and voluntary basis. It is indicated by researchers that the many organisations in Pakistan do not encourage corporate social responsibility and seems to be unsuccessful in engaging in various aspects like anticorruption and gender equality (Naeem & Welford, 2009). The conception of CSR is not very established in many developing countries including Bangladesh and Pakistan. Although, multinational organisations in Pakistan are practicing CSR and have advance level of CSR as compare to native organisations. Moreover, in the comparative study of CSR and other regions like Africa has discovered that the level corporate social responsibility in Pakistani organisations is lower than African and European countries (Baughn, et al., 2007). The association amongst CSR and economic, political and social framework of a country is substantial. The regions with less economic growth, displays low level of practicing corporation social responsibility. According to one research, the scholar categorised the performance of CSR into four groups indifferent, beginner, emerging and active (Jeswani, et al., 2008). It was also demonstrated by the research that around seventy five percent of organisations in Pakistan are at beginner and indifferent level which means there are deficiency of programs related to protection of the environment. A number of companies in Pakistan are having dearth of consciousness, inadequate economic resources, deficiency of guidelines, scarcity of proficiency, unavailability of technology because of which, it is challenging to deal with environmental concerns. There is indication of extensive implanted communally negligent practice and corruption in many organisations in Pakistan like banks and pharmaceuticals. A few banks in Pakistan claim to be exceedingly moral and socially accountable whereas others are apparently engaged in actions that deceive a disdain for corporate social responsibility. Providing misinformation to customers, deceiving through advertising and morally doubtful alterations to product are the few examples of unethical

practices (Jaffery, 1996; Dawn, 2006). Similar, one of the unethical practices by a National Bank of Pakistan (NBP) is that it has begun to deduct money, on monthly basis, from accounts of customers under life insurance scheme without any prior notice to customers (Raza, 2006). The level of corruption is also very high in the country. A number of pharmaceutical firms have been alleged of proposing gifts in return for doing favour and prescribing the manufactured goods of the firm (Ahmad, 2006). As the literacy rate of the country is low and the awareness of CSR is less, there is a substantial probability of manipulation of customers that seems not to be main point of concern to addressed.

In Pakistan, the concept of CSR was introduced predominantly because of collaboration or association with global non-profit firms (Khan & Nomani, 2002) . As an outcome is that global organisations responding to the issues upstretched in emergent countries regarding problems like child labour. The child labour issue in the sports industry of Pakistan and football stitching by children in Sialkot was well documented as well as its inadvertent consequences and impacts for the native labour force (Hussain-Khaliq, 2004; Naji, 1998; Husselbee, 2000; Bendell, 2005). The country became familiar with corporate social responsibility when this concern of child labour attained global attention (Winstanley, et al., 2002; Awan, et al., 2012).

On other hand, it is also observed by many scholars that as in different countries of Asia CSR is progressively growing, similarly, it is also on the rise in multinational and private sector in Pakistan (Khan & Nomani, 2002). There are various organisations executing CSR, predominantly donations and charity, aimed at diverse reasons. One of the investigations by Pakistan Centre for Philanthropy (PCB) showed that most of the organisations in Pakistan donate or charity mainly for public-spirited and belief-based intentions, marketing benefits, advantages of taxation and better-quality associations with community are other motivations (Ahmad, 2006; PCP, 2005). The research by PCB showed that the total donations of public listed companies had increased in past few years, it was Rs. 228 million in 2000 and had reached to Rs. 4.8 billion in year 2013 (PCP, 2013). According to a survey on CSR by The Securities and exchange Commission of Pakistan (SECP) 2005, organisations in Pakistan primarily emphasis on philanthropic and legal activities. Many organisations goals are short term and they work on the base of situation and not as a long-term strategic development. Corporate social responsibility is not an essential element of organisations in Pakistan. Additionally, large organisations and multinational companies are more receptive to embrace activities related to CSR. Some issues are also adopted by medium and small size enterprises

like protection of environment and preservation of energy but few crucial matters, for instance corruption control and employee engagement are not commonly concentrated upon.

Many organisations in Pakistan are engaged with CSR activities which leads to the emergent standard of the country. For example, Pakistan State Oil had received recognition with fitting or connecting traffic signs on different roads in Karachi and organising programmes related to creating awareness of running road for children (Dawn , 2002). Pakistan State oil is also engaged with education, healthcare, community building and natural disaster relief as a part of their CSR. The company stood with the people in Baluchistan (one of the provinces of Pakistan), at time of earthquake in 2013, by providing life supplies and relief to them (PSO, 2013). Correspondingly, Pakistan Tobacco Company is engaged with afforestation and planted more than 75 million trees since 1981 and also disseminated 3.5 million saplings without any charges (Pakistan Tobacco Company, 2018). The company is contributing to the society by providing water filtration plants and mobile doctor units (Pakistan Tobacco Company, 2018).

2.1.6.4 CSR in Pakistani Banks.

A number of banks in Pakistan have started executing corporate social responsibilities and creating awareness of the notion. Allied Bank limited (ABL) was the first bank to establish in Pakistan. Before independence the bank was named as Australian Bank in 1974 it became Allied Bank. In recent times, the bank has donated one million rupees to '*Rasst Welfare Society*', to assist underprivileged people of the society (Allied Bank, 2018). To fulfil their societal responsibility and to abide their CSR policy, the bank presented 100 KVA transformer to Bolan Cricket Stadium, Quetta in 2017 (Allied Bank, 2017). Financial awareness seminars and donating ambulances to hospitals are some other CSR activities by Allied Bank.

Standard Chartered Pakistan is one of the famous and big banks in Pakistan, is actively participating in CSR activities and also awarded a National CSR Award for child centric CSR (Standard Chartered, 2015). The bank was also acknowledged for its involvement formulated by its worldwide seeing is believing in Pakistan. Similarly, Muslim commercial bank commonly known as MCB also take part in activities related to corporate social responsibility. MCB has proper policy and guidelines which demonstrates the dedication of the bank towards society (MCB, 2018). The bank always abides the rules and regulation of good governance and

its strategy always look after the internal and external stakeholders. MCB is enthusiastic and actively participates in activities to assist the society by participating in distinct programs. Education, charity, sports and protection of the environment are the few areas in which MCB has contributed. When it comes to CSR the bank has accomplished an unremittingly increasing it abilities to engage with society. The Pakistan Centre of Philanthropy has also acknowledged and appreciated the CSR projects by MCB. Correspondingly, United Bank Limited (UBL) also raises its sprit for activities related to CSR and always endeavour to establish itself as an honest, hardworking and reliable organisation. UBL identifies its responsibilities towards society and always try to create value for community by providing good product and services. The bank participates in different programs which provide advantages to the society and always encourage CSR activities for the advancement of stakeholders. For example, UBL has supported education and given RS 20 million to the Forman Christian College (FCC) Lahore (The Express Tribune, 2015). In order to continue the spirit of supporting education, in year 2016, the bank also sponsored a computer laboratory to Lahore University Management Sciences (LUMS) (The Express Tribune, 2016). UBL has also introduced the project name “GO Green” that aims to protect environment by using less paper (UBL, 2018).

Furthermore, National bank of Pakistan (NBP), is a corporate citizen and always try to encourages activities related to CSR. NBP has supported different NGOs, health sectors and educational entities for the enhancement or improvement of the community. Recently the bank has organised a walk in Karachi, named as ‘Traffic rule awareness walk’ on 14 January 2018. The purpose of the walk was to create consciousness of traffic rules in the society (NBP, 2018). In year 2016, the bank has spent around Rs. 53 million on CSR activities which included education, health care, sports, special person support, women and child and cultural programs (NBP, 2016).

2.1.6.5 CSR and Islamic Banking.

The focus of corporate social responsibility is to develop benefits from business operations to the society. It ensures that the any firm may not pay no attention the human rights and provide the progression to the human right. In Islamic banking ‘Shariah’ is a preliminary stage for understanding of CSR in Islam. The basic parts of Shariah includes faith and morality and legal

rulings. Pakistan is concentrating on constructing a collectively and environmentally reactive business share and is taking responsibility in improvement of CSR in organisations.

Islamic banks are not behind in the race of contributing in CSR and managing its reputation. Under the concept of Quran (Holy book of Muslims), Islam is a complete Deen and any organisation has to comprehend CSR activities as an element of Shariah compliance. There are mandatory and non-mandatory compulsions in the religion. There is a clear differentiation between the permissible and unacceptable drawn by Shairah from Quran. Any Islamic organisation has to follow the rules and regulation provided in the Quran. According to Shariah, the government has the power to debarred the activities which are unethical and does not comes under the circle of Shariah. Consequently, Islamic financial institutions like banks have to encourage the essence of the Islam and should implement CSR as an element of Shariah Compliance. There are several scholars conducted investigation about it and previous literature demonstrates the presence of the conception of CSR in Islamic banks (Dusuki & Dar, 2007; Jusoh & Ibrahim, 2015; Adnan, 2012; Yusuf & Bahari, 2011; Hassan & Salma, 2009; Dusuki, 2008; Mallin, et al., 2014; Alamer, et al., 2015; Mosaid & Boutti, 2012). It is observed by preceding researches that corporate social responsibility is not a novel perception for Islamic banks and can be utilised to proliferation of the market share of the company and to attain competitive advantage. There are a number of Islamic banks exceedingly encourage CSR activities and motivated by the conception of satisfaction of consumers which comes under the Shariah guidelines. The purpose of deeds of any Islamic bank is to focus on the promotion of better environment and empowerment of the community unlike some commercial banks which emphasis on the profit maximisation (Durrani, 2016). These banks are determined to endorse in accordance with Shariah however they are generally pursuing traditional methods of CSR that are articulated in relation to western perspective and framework together with particular practices which are not supported by Shariah law (Hamdan, 2014).

Meezan bank is one of the famous banks in Pakistan also participating in corporate social responsibilities. The bank took initiative and worked together with other organisations to contribute in different areas of CSR like health and education. The bank proclaimed the efficacious accomplishment of its communal improvement CSR initiative commenced in 2016 in joint venture with Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit, a Dutch

company. The program was of technical and vocational education and training for under-privileged young girls and women in Sindh province (Business Recorder, 2017).

Al Baraka is established on the Islamic principles also trying to fulfilling its accountabilities by making sure the implementation of the guidelines of corporate social responsibilities. The bank has organised a CSR stall activity on 17 April 2018, in Indus Hospital Lahore with collaboration of the hospital (Baraka, 2018). The stall provides free and urgent health care facility to the people in need. In addition, the CSR unit of the bank arranged a blood donation drive in 2018 with Shaukat Khanum Memorial Cancer Hospital and Research Centre (SKMCH & RC) (Baraka, 2018).

2.1.6.6 Managerial Perception of CSR.

The role of manager is crucial in any decision or implementation of strategies in an organisation. It is argued in many previous studies that commitment of employees is essential to successful CSR. The communications amongst organisational culture and individual values of managers are perceived to be substantial. Managers can motivate employees to adopt CSR which will become one of the reasons behind the employee satisfaction. Firms are represented by their business societal devotions are encouraged, developed and progressed by person who manage them and quality of human resource (Wood, 1991; Ali, 2003). Hence, the socially responsible behaviour of a manager is important indicator of an organisation's CSR performance (Carroll, 1999).

The researcher of the study believes that it is important for Pakistani banks to provide required training to the managers related to CSR and create awareness amongst them. Because, for a successful firm, it is crucial to have efficient leaders. Pakistani banks managers should communicate with employees about the goals and CSR initiatives taking place by Pakistani banks. By making CSR a part of daily briefs and regular conversation, bank managers can generate mind-share for CSR. It is essential to understand the perception of Pakistani banks managers to understand the position of CSR in banks which can affect their CFP. Therefore, this study includes the perception of Pakistani bank managers about CSR and the impact of CSR on CFP.

2.1.7 Summary of the Chapter.

This chapter of the research presented the literature of CSR and about the country of research. It is difficult to define CSR from one perspective although some definitions by different scholars are elucidated in this chapter. There are different CSR theories for instance, stakeholder theory, agency theory and intuitional theory. One of the popular explanations of CSR was described by Carroll (1991). Corporate social responsibility divided into four elements which are philanthropic, ethical legal and economic accountabilities (Carroll, 1999). It is also suggested by Carroll (1999), that it is beneficial for an organisation to balance amongst these responsibilities which is to fulfil them equivalently (Harzing & Pinnington , 2015). There are various organisations participating in CSR activities like charity, enhancement of customers and employees benefits (Sprinkle & Maines, 2010; Lee, et al., 2018). The relationship between CSR and financial performance of organisation is argued by previous scholars. Some of them support the positive relation between CSR and FP while others support negative relationship. Moreover, it has suggested by few researchers the relationship between CSR and FP in u-shaped, which means it can be positive or negative.

The idea of CSR is commonly used by organisations in developed but the notion is moderately new in Pakistan. However, the fascination of participating in CSR is gradually growing in Pakistan. In various organisations of the country the notion of corporate social responsibility has been confused with philanthropic activities including rights and low of workforce and (Waheed, 2005; Khan, 2012). This research is focusing on Pakistani banks to investigate the current practice of CSR and the relationship of CSR with FP. The conceptual framework of this investigation constructed by researcher is presented in following chapter.

3 Chapter Three.

3.1 Conceptual Framework and Hypothesis Development.

3.2 Introduction.

The conceptual framework is described as has various roles which includes concept mapping and making a link between theory and practice. (Trafford & Leshem, 2008) This chapter presents the conceptual framework of the study which includes the explanation of the foremost aspects of the research. The conceptual framework was constructed by researcher on the foundation of the literature or theoretical perspective of corporate social responsibility. The hypotheses are developed in the end of this chapter which will be tested and analysed. In other chapters of the study.

3.3 Hypotheses Development.

The research objectives which are elucidated in chapter one is going to be attained by construction of hypotheses which are going to be tested. The research question has expressed the association amongst two variable which are CSR and financial performance of banks in Pakistan. It is the purpose of the study to evaluate these variables. A hypothesis is a statement about the association amongst variables. In this study, the research used positive hypotheses in which two distinct variables are independent of each other.

The following hypotheses are constructed to attain the research objectives.

H₁= There is a positive and significant correlation between philanthropic responsibilities and financial performance of Pakistani banks.

H₂= There is a positive and significant correlation between employees related CSR and financial performance of Pakistani banks.

H₃= There is a positive and significant correlation between environmental responsibilities and financial performance of Pakistani banks.

H₄= There is a positive and significant correlation between customers related responsibilities and financial performance of Pakistani banks.

H₅= There is a positive and significant correlation between legal responsibilities and financial performance of Pakistani banks.

H₆= There is a positive and significant correlation between CSR and financial performance of Pakistani banks.

H_n= There is no significant difference in the financial performance of Public and Private Pakistani banks.

H_n= There is no significant difference between financial performance and size of the Pakistani banks.

The above-mentioned hypotheses provide the precise concerns that need to be examine to obtain the research objectives. The hypotheses are assumptions about the association between CSR and financial performance in Pakistani bank. Therefore, testing and analysing these hypotheses are essential that will permit the researcher to answer the research question.

3.4 Mapping the Research.

CSR is a strategy which many organisations used to make alignment in their corporate operations with societal norms and necessities (Carroll, 1979). In precious few decades the anticipation from organisation has increased and people wants companies to implement CSR and be part of the society (Carroll, 2008). However, organisations in developing countries are less aware of the notion of CSR. The purpose of this investigation is to identify the current CSR practice and the impact of CSR in Pakistani banks. This study can grow awareness that social accountabilities can positive impact the financial performance (Carroll, 1999; Davis, 1960; Griffin & Mahon, 1997).

There are a number of theories on impact on corporate social responsibility and financial performance. Stakeholder theory give importance to the interests of stakeholder of the

company. If the stakeholders are satisfied with the social participation of organisation, can produce positive impact in the firm's financial performance. Moreover, another theory of social impact hypothesis which assumes that financial performance of an organisation can be increased by implementing corporate social responsibility. These theories support the argument that CSR has effects on stakeholders and it can enhance economic performance (Freeman, 1984; Porter & Kramer, 2006; Preble, 2005).

Although, the source which are used by a firm in implementation of CSR can cause the additional cost. It can affect the finances and this perspective is of the trade-off hypothesis which assumes that CSR has negative effects on financial performance (Aupperle, et al., 1985 ; Preston & O'Bannon, 1997; Ullmann, 1985; Ullmann, 1985). These theories provide both aspects of the CSR impact on financial performance which is positive and negative. Many researchers have supported the positive impact on financial performance (Orlitzky, et al., 2003). However, mostly previous researches were in context of developed countries, thus a gap has been created for an investigation in Pakistan.

The researcher believes that the role of manager in any organisation is very essential and manager's perception of CSR is essential to implement it. Most of the scholars argues that the commitment of employees in any decision taken by a firm is crucial to the successful CSR. When it comes to environment protection, less wastage of paper is the technique used by many firms. Similarly, other CSR trainings can motivate employees and become the reason of employee's satisfaction. This is the belief of the researcher of the study, therefore the investigation includes the managers perception on CSR in Pakistani banks.

3.5 The Conceptual Framework.

The conceptual framework is an assumption, expectation, beliefs and concept that becomes foundation of the investigation (Miles & Huberman, 1994). The definition of conceptual framework is elucidated as

A conceptual framework is defined as "it lays out the key factors, constructs, or variables, and presumes relationships among them (Miles & Huberman, 1994, p. 440)".

It provides an interpretative approach to the reality and presents theoretical explanation with comprehensions. Many scholars argue that conceptual framework gives knowledge of soft understanding of intents (Levering, 2002). The nature of conceptual frameworks is not determined and hence the results cannot be predicted by investigator. It generates theories and aims to produce concepts. It is a framework which selects study and then indicates main notions and association in each one. (Nelson, 2004; Noblit & Hare, 1988).

This section of the investigation will present a conceptual framework for the study. It explains the main aspects, variables and their associations. This section of the research elucidates the construction of conceptual framework from the theories presented in literature review (chapter 2). The researcher employed narrative approach to provide the clarification of construction of conceptual framework with illustration of figures. This is the alignment of the investigation from literature to hypothesis to build conceptual framework. The main purpose of the investigation is to study the current CSR practice and the impact of CSR on the financial performance of Pakistani banks. The definition and theories of corporate social responsibilities are presented in previous chapter of the study which is the foundation of this conceptual framework. The conceptual framework is developed by researcher inspired by Carroll's (1991) pyramid of CSR.

3.5.1 The Pyramid is a Sustainable Stakeholder Framework.

The CSR pyramid presented by Carroll (1991), has four elements and each element deal with distinct stakeholders. Philanthropic responsibility has most impact on community and non-profit organisations. Ethical accountabilities of an organisation affect the stakeholders of the firm and it involves customers, employees and environment. Legal responsibility is crucial for business person although nowadays in some controversial societies, there is a risk of lawsuit against organisations from stakeholders (Carroll, 2016). Finally, economic responsibilities which has great impact on shareholders. The researcher has explained the pyramid from philanthropic responsibilities, however economic responsibilities comes first in the pyramid in developing countries and philanthropic is given second, third is legal and then ethical (Visser, 2011).

Figure 12 The Adaptation of Conceptual Framework.

(Carroll, 1999)

Figure redacted for copyright reasons

The CSR pyramid presented by Carroll (1999), includes philanthropic, ethical, legal and economic responsibilities. The above figure illustrates the adaptation of conceptual framework from CSR pyramid. The researcher considered philanthropic responsibilities are important part of a community because these activities can assist to reduce issues in community. Concerns related with employees and customers are considered as ethical responsibilities by researcher. Legal responsibilities are also part of the framework. Financial performance comprises return on equity (ROE), return on assets (ROA) which are accounting based measures and earning per share (EPS) which is market-based measure. The researcher has constructed the following conceptual framework on the basis of the abovementioned discussion.

Figure 13 Conceptual Framework.

Inspired by Carroll’s (1999) CSR Pyramid.

This conceptual framework provides guidelines to be used in research methodology. It illustrates the relationship between CSR and financial performance. The research designs have to collect data related to both variables which are CSR and financial performance of Pakistani banks.

3.6 Summary of Chapter.

This chapter presents the development of hypotheses and conceptual framework. These both concepts are constructed on the foundation of the literature review presented in previous chapter. The study focuses on the current practice of CSR and its impact on financial performance of Pakistani banks. The conceptual framework leads to the research methodology which is presented in next chapter.

4 Chapter Four.

4.1 Research Methodology

4.2 Introduction

According to McGrath & Brinberg 1983, the immense effect on validity, generalizability and authenticity of the research is dependent on research methodology (Yang, et al., 2006). This chapter of thesis focus on the methods of research including research philosophy, design, sampling methods and techniques. The research methodology is a process and structure in which the investigation is carried out and the research design is a rational classification that determines the empirical data from research question to the result and conclusion of the investigation (Yin, 2003). In order to reveal the current CSR practices and the impact of CSR on financial performance in Pakistani banks which is the main objective of this study, it is important to have well-defined research methodology, methods and research design. Nevertheless, it is a challenging process for the researcher to decide on the suitable research methodology, design and research strategy. Research topic, questions, aim and objectives were considered by researcher before selecting appropriate research methodology. The personal experience of the investigator, capabilities, proficiency, resources, time frame and the above mention aspects has been outlined to conduct this study.

This chapter of the research begins with research paradigm followed with research philosophy, research approach, research design, research method and sampling. The purpose of the research and objectives of the study are considered by the researcher. Data collection method is also presented in this chapter and ethical consideration are also considered by the researcher.

4.3 Research Paradigm

Research paradigm is a philosophical framework, which provide assistance to conduct the research (Collis & Hussey, 2003). Research philosophy can have great impact on the management and practice of research, therefore, it is crucial to understand. The rationales behind the importance of comprehension of research philosophy are elucidated below (Smith, et al., 1991):

- It helps to explicate research design including data collection and analysis. Research philosophy gives the evidence of data collected and evidence of interpretation of answers.
- Research philosophy assists the researcher to identify research design. It also specifies the limitations of certain approaches and prevent the investigator from getting lost.
- It assists investigator to indicate and establish design that might be beyond experience of the researcher. It can provide encouragement to the researcher to modify research design in accordance with constrictions of diverse disciplines. An investigator gain confidence, while understanding different issues of knowledge structures to complete the process of research, and this confidence varies on the elucidation of ontological and epistemological assumptions.

The following figure illustrates the research onion from which the researcher has selected appropriate method for this investigation.

Figure 14 Research Onion Figure redacted for copyright reasons

(Saunders, et al., 2012)

4.3.1 Epistemology

Epistemological issues indicate to the question of what is related to the adequate knowledge in subject (Bryman & Bell, 2007). Epistemology is concerned with possibilities, nature, sources and limitations of knowledge in the field of study (Shand, 2003). It also provides a philosophical grounding to determine that what kind of knowledge is achievable and how a researcher can make sure it is adequate. Having discovered the nature of reality Pakistani banks in relation to their banking and CSR activities. This is in context of this research that “what is the truth?” Would it be possible to achieve the objectives of the study by taking interview managers? or would it be more suitable to achieve objectives by using survey to large number of employees of Pakistani banks? These are the epistemological issues considered by the research in this investigation.

4.4 Research Philosophy

Research philosophy is a productive and elementary aspect of the thesis, it is associated with collection or gathering of data including data assessment and evaluation (Galliers, 1991 cited in (Lehmann, 2010). In initiating a research and collecting appropriate data through distinct sources, the research philosophy is the main element, which provide support. The research philosophy is ordinarily apportioned into two terms. First term used, as research philosophy is epistemology also acknowledged as Positivism and another is Doxology also recognise as interpretivism. The positivism is associated with the pragmatic knowledge whereas the focus of interpretivism is on analysis of understanding the meaning of reality.

4.4.1 Positivism

Positivism is defined as “Positivism is an epistemological position that advocates the application of the methods of the natural sciences to the study of social reality and beyond.” (Bryman & Bell, 2003, p. 16).

Natural science that does not have any personal norms and values is correlated with positivism. The purpose of the research is to generate hypotheses, about the CSR practice and the impact of CSR on financial performance of Pakistani banks, and test these hypotheses. The knowledge is attained through the collection of primary data from the facts. However, it is challenging to extricate the natural science from the positivism. This is the criticism made by many scholars about the positivism related to the relevance of the natural science paradigm for the investigation related to people or society (Bryman & Bell, 2003).

Positivism is established on significance of reason, truth and validity and the emphasis is merely on reality or fact assembled via experience and observations. It can be measured by utilising quantitative methods like surveys or questionnaires (Bryman & Bell, 2003; Saunders, et al., 2012). It is the appropriate for this investigation because it can be utilised to attain the attitude, perception, behaviour and understanding of human being. It has scientific approach which is suitable for the study as it comprises dealing with numbers and statistical analysis. a

quantitative research search to explicate and envisage the social domain by investigating for certainties and casual association amongst its basic aspects (Burrell & Morgan, 1979). Consequently, this is extensively recognised that predictive models are developed by positivists by means of determining causal association amongst various social phenomena (Furlong & Marsh, 2010). Thus, it is observed that the fundamental advantage of utilising positivist approach comprises supporting managers to be capable to forecast related to the forthcoming happenings and consequences. However, it is been criticised for lack of ability to consider the human aspect in the firm and also argued as impracticable or unrealistic (Uduma & Sylva, 2015).

4.4.2 Interpretivism

On other hand, subjectivity, for instance understanding and opinion of researcher are linked with Interpretivism. The term is comparing epistemology to positivism. It is suggested by a number of scholars that interpretive paradigm permits an investigator to view world by means of experiences a perception of humans (Thanh & Thanh, 2015). In order to investigate and find the answers to the research questions, the researcher has followed the interpretivism approach and utilised experiences to create and explain or interpret the comprehension of researcher from collected data. An interpretation of understanding of an individual in particularly supported by this paradigm. Moreover, it is also considered by this approach that another critical aspect is the comprehension of the context in which an investigation is conducted to interpretation of collected data.

Additionally, this paradigm can be appropriate to attain great comprehension of behaviour of people related to bringing to light belief system and values (Cavana, et al., 2001). The reality is subjective and constantly changing is another believe of interpretivism (Collis & Hussey, 2003). Thus, this paradigm supports subjectivity and assisted the researcher in attaining better comprehension of Pakistani banks from the perspective of practical experience of manager level employees of the banks. The researcher of the study uses qualitative technique for the good understanding of the employees of the banks.

This paradigm is different from the positivisms in which the researcher only undertakes one suitable answer. In interpretivism, the researcher can agree to various perspectives of different

people from diverse groups. The researcher can attain better understanding of the situation by acknowledgement of several viewpoints by using interpretivism (Morehouse, 2011). Nevertheless, interpretivism has one of the crucial elements in social investigations, it has some critique. Many scholars criticise it because of dishonest or deceitful cognizance to relativism of the paradigm (Aliyu, et al., 2014). Deficiency of capability to generalise the results of interpretivist study to all-encompassing social framework is another critique of this paradigm (Furlong & Marsh, 2010).

The purpose of this particular study is to investigate the impact of corporate social responsibility on consumers' behaviour and financial performance of Pakistani Banks, which is not natural science but more about the perception of people. This research includes the factual data from questionnaires and the subjective perception (interviews). The following table illustrates the difference of positivism and interpretivism.

Interpretivism	Positivism
<i>It associates with Qualitative data</i>	<i>It associates with Quantitative data</i>
<i>It contains Small samples</i>	<i>It contains medium sample</i>
<i>It generates Theory</i>	<i>It generates hypothesis</i>
<i>Data rich and subjective in this philosophy</i>	<i>The data is objective</i>
<i>The Validity is high</i>	
<i>It can be hard to generalise from one situation to another</i>	

Table 4 Difference between Interpretivism and Positivism

These both paradigms have different perspectives with different strength and weaknesses. Positivism approach is faster and more can deal with extensive scale of the population with cost-effective way whilst gathering data method is not flexible (Amaratunga, et al., 2002). Conversely, in interpretivism it has been observed that the method of collecting data is more natural. Comprehension of human ideas, perspectives and opinions is supported by interpretivist paradigm. It is also claimed by scholars that positivism approach is easier to evaluate than interpretivist approach (Amaratunga, et al., 2002).

The main aim of this research is to investigate the current CSR practices and to test the empirically the impact of CSR on financial performance in Pakistani banks. The research questions and research objectives of this investigation requires appropriate selection of philosophical paradigm. The study involves testing of the CSR pyramid model and its impact of FP, therefore it is understandable to use positivism approach. Moreover, the research also elucidated in research objectives that the study is related the managerial perception and interpretivism approach can be suitable.

4.4.3 Post-Positivism.

The research questions and objectives of this investigation are considered by the researcher to make selection of philosophical paradigm. The sim of this study is to investigate about the current CSR practices and its impact on financial performance in Pakistani retail banking sector. It is obvious that the positivism is suitable for the research. Although, it is also the research questions contains identification and exploration of perspectives of managers of Pakistani banks. Therefore, the researcher selected the modified paradigm of post-positivism. It is one of the approaches which is commonly utilised in investigation related to social science. The researcher with this approach will recognise the value of the complex and interconnected association amongst the behaviour and viewpoints of individuals (Crossan, 2003). Consequently, it draws attention towards the requirement for the multiple measures to achieve enhanced insight of reality which is known as ‘triangulation’. It gives better comprehension of research question and assists to prevail over pragmatic restrain and certify the quality of results by double verifying the findings (Bryman & Bell, 2007). Moreover, it indicates to utilise multiple data gathering method to collect quantitative and qualitative data.

It has also been indicated by many scholars that post-positivism does not propose that positivism is not required but it is also effective to use another paradigm as well. It uses of combination for paradigms will provide the researcher get bigger picture and increase the possibilities or options for gathering data. It will highlight the pragmatic requirement to conduct investigation and assess the outcomes (Henderson, 2011). Additionally, post-positivism is defined as extensive which brings theory and practice together and makes researcher more committed to answer the research questions. Consequently, it provides deep insight to the researcher and thus this research selected post-positivism. The reason behind selection of this paradigm is that the researcher will test the CSR model presented by Carroll (1991), empirically in context of Pakistani banking sector. Therefore, the post-positivism is the suitable approach for this study which will give assist the researcher to attain all the objectives of the study.

4.5 Exploratory, Explanatory and Descriptive.

Explorative researches are conducted to find about the whole characteristics of the phenomenon and different aspects associated with it. It is also suggested this research is carried out when the research area is relatively new (Polit, et al., 2001). Exploratory study assists a researcher to understand the factors and obstacles of the concerns related to the situation and it will also recognise the variables which will be applicable to the investigation. This type of research comprises pursuing to comprehend further about the study has observed, often creates hypotheses for forthcoming study (Robson, 2011). Moreover, exploratory researches are specifically beneficial, if the intention of researcher is to establish extra awareness or comprehension of indistinct concerns, where the investigator is ambiguous about the essential features and connections and that theories are appropriate to a specified circumstance (Yin, 2003). Consequently, this type of research is commonly conducted when there is ambiguity about the topic or research area and the researcher has less knowledge about the research concerns (Polit, et al., 2001). It is also flexible approach in which a researcher can explore different perspectives of related to research problem which lead towards to generate new facts. By using qualitative and quantitative approach, in this research design, observation, literature review, interviews and case studies are utilised by investigator to gather data and to find the well-defined outlines (Saunders, et al., 2012).

On other hand, explanatory research is an effort to correlate perceptions to recognise the source and effect of the research problem. It is also suggested that it endeavours to focus on answering questions which includes 'why' and 'how' questions related to the research and the association of variables. (Collis & Hussey, 2003). The causative association amongst variables which have impact of the investigation is described as explanatory research. In this design the research data is explained in detail with new set of data and then evaluated by researcher. Thus, this investigation has selected the convergent parallel design. The researcher utilised existing theory of CSR pyramid presented by Carroll (1991), to construct framework and hypotheses and also about the impact of CSR on CFP. Qualitative and quantitative both approaches are used to obtain research data.

Furthermore, one more famous design used by researchers are of descriptive studies. In particular phenomenon features of crucial variables are defined by descriptive studies. The main reason of this type of study is to presents an image of a phenomenon as it naturally takes place (Burns & Grove, 2003). Questions like 'what, when, who, where and how' are included in descriptive researches which is ahead of other approaches including exploratory and explanatory. Moreover, descriptive study is utilised to validate existing practice and formulate a verdict and expand or develop theories. It is also described as a research that take place to achieve a particular situation is a descriptive study (Saunders, et al., 2012). A descriptive study has strong and distinct place in management or business research (Saunders, et al., 2012). It is different from other type of studies because it can use various variables, merely one variable is needed to carry out descriptive research. Descriptive studies can encompass portion of both data gathering techniques that are qualitative and quantitative.

The researcher of this investigation, stated with an exploratory stage that includes the procedure of exploration and construction of framework. In the second phase, the researcher test or analysed the data which was explanatory. In these stages, the post-positivist paradigm was considered and the approach utilised by researcher was mixed methods that comprises of qualitative and quantitative techniques. The rationale behind the utilisation of mixed methods is that this investigation comprises of various research questions and objectives. Therefore, the researcher believes that one method possibly will not be suitable for all other research objectives.

In this study, exploratory stage was the first one, in which the researcher explores about the current practices of CSR in Pakistani retail banking sector. Additionally, the literature review

of the study which is part of exploratory phase, is one of the crucial sections of this research. It provided better insight of research topic with different definitions of CSR, its impact on CFP, CSR in Pakistani banks and other theoretical perspectives.

4.6 Research Approach.

4.6.1 Inductive and deductive.

Inductive and deductive are the two fundamental research approaches use by any researcher. Scientific research is predominantly done by using deductive approach in which data is collected to scrutinise the hypothesis in relation to existing theory. The result of deductive approach is commonly the verification or falsification of the current theory. On contrary, when research is based on feelings, perception, opinion and experience of individuals, inductive appears apposite. Therefore, the research approach selected by researcher for this study is inductive and deductive, in which data is collected, evaluate and present with identification of process or technique concentrating on the specification of the theory (Newby, 2014). These approaches are connected to the research philosophies. The inductive approach is related to interpretivism and the deductive is associated with positivism (Bryman & Bell, 2007).

It depends on the nature, aims, objective and scope of the research and the investigator have to choose the most suitable approach together data (Saunders, et al., 2012). Deductive approach is usually utilised in researches in which investigator wants to test the existing data, theories, model or hypothesis in new context (Elo & Kyngäs, 2008). The deductive approach often leads to the construction of new strategies by developing hypothesis form existing theory. By using this approach, the researcher of the study has formulated a set of hypotheses and then tested them by means of collecting data from manager level of employees of Pakistani banks. The data was then analysed statistically and the hypotheses were accepted or rejected by the researcher. The role of existing theory, which is CSR pyramid by Carroll, in this study, is well recognized. The deductive approach is also indicated as a waterfall approach (Pelissier, 2008). It was also suggested that deductive approach begins from general to particular. The findings

in this approach are often presented in form of statistics or numerals and it generally depends on gauging and evaluating statistical data to acquire the nature of association between several sets of data (Eldabi, et al., 2002).

On other hand, any investigation with inductive approach begins with particular and move to generalisation. In this approach an idea is developed by investigator by observation and then a new idea is generated by gathering and evaluating data (Bryman & Bell, 2007). The researcher in this approach move step by step to explicate the concept that end at new or existing theory (Lodico, et al., 2010). In inductive approach the focus is on explaining a happening as a description by considering the significance of describing the framework and the perception. Consequently, inductive approach is the suitable one to attain comprehensive information about the issue and to bring light to essential purposes, belief, value and opinions. (Hair, et al., 2010). According to scholars in inductive approach, an investigator can develop ideas without restrictions, and can change the route of the research according to the observation and reflection (Bernard, 2013).

The above-mention discussion demonstrates that deductive approach is suitable if the topic is previously well investigated and theoretical framework can be developed and tested on the base of previous theories. On contrary, if the subject of the study moderately new then it is appropriate to use inductive approach. Nevertheless, any researcher can utilise both of the approaches at the different phases of the investigation (Creswell, 2014). It shows that these both approaches are crucial and beneficial and therefore the researcher of this study have taken these as they complement to each other (Creswell, 2014). The researcher believe that the combination of inductive and deductive approach can assists the researcher to attain the best outcomes to answer the research questions and achieve the research objectives.

In order to achieve the basic aim and objectives of this investigation the researcher used deductive approach to test the current CSR practices and its impact of financial performance in Pakistani banks. But due to the time limitation, the researcher believes that it was also appropriate to use inductive approach as well. If the researcher relied on one approach merely, it could have reduced the efficiency or effectiveness of the investigation. Inductive approach was used at different phase and deductive was used at different stage of the research. First approach used by researcher was deductive, data was gathered by conducting surveys from managerial employees of Pakistani banks. Then, in the second phase, the researcher used

inductive approach by gathering qualitative data form management level employees of Pakistani banks which strengthen the results.

Moreover, mixed method was selected by researcher because it also enhances, consolidate the credibility of the outcomes of the investigation (Hesse-Biber, 2010). This study used mixed method approach which helps to attain better comprehension of the research problem (Creswell, 2014) and it one of the famous methods used in management researches (Stanley, 2015). Thus, it was appropriate to adopt inductive and deductive approach in this investigation.

The following figure illustrates the difference between the deductive and inductive approach.

Figure 15 Deductive and Inductive

(Newby, 2014)

Figure redacted for copyright reasons

4.7 Research Design.

A plan to answer the research question is referred to as research design which embraces precisely demarcated research objectives (Saunders, et al., 2012). Research design is a collection of conjectures and consequences, which manages specific contextualised directives. Moreover, it is associated with theoretical concepts and features to perpetrate suitable tactic or strategy for the study encouraged by data collection methods (Jonker & Pennink, 2010).

Any researcher has to select distinct elements for investigation. It is very essential for researcher to select suitable strategy for exploration because it has huge effect on the time horizon (Saunders, et al., 2012). A research can be descriptive, explanatory, exploratory or a combination of these. Moreover, research method use in study can be qualitative, quantitative, or mixed.

Research design performs as a blue print of the research which includes the configuration of the strategy to support the study. It is a framework for the gathering and evolution of the research data (Bryman & Bell, 2003). The researcher has to be cautious in selection of the research design which reflects the decision of the researcher. Four types of research designs used by several other researchers are case study, cross sectional, longitudinal and experimental design.

4.7.1 Cross-sectional design.

In this particular investigation, the researcher has selected cross-sectional design which is commonly known as survey design. The cross-sectional design refers to an investigation which involves the gathering of data of more than one case at a particular time (Vaus, 2001). The researcher prefers to choose cross-sectional design because it is the suitable design to answer the research question. Cross-sectional design focuses on things happening at a specific time. The cross-sectional is closely related to social surveys and interviews. This research design entails researcher the collection of data in variation which can be in respect of people or organisation. The cross-sectional design is defined as

“A cross-sectional design entails the collection of data on more than one case (usually quite a lot more than one) and at a single point in time in order to collect a body of quantitative or qualitative data in connection with two or more variables (usually many more than two), which are then examined to detect patterns of association”. (Bryman & Bell, 2007, p. 55).

In researcher has collected data on the variable of interest more or less simultaneously. The questionnaire was completed by responded at the same time unlike experimental design which includes pre-testing and post testing of the experiments. In this investigation, the researcher has examined the relationship between two variables which are corporate social responsibility and financial performance.

4.8 Primary and Secondary Data.

In any research, the most important part is of data collection. Primary and secondary sources were used to gather the data of this investigation. Primary data is the data which is gathered by researcher first handed whilst secondary data is collected from existing source (Sekaran, 2003). Secondary data analysis represents the exploration prevailing facts or data accumulated by others and it save time and resources of the researcher (Donnellan & Richard, 2013). In spite of, the secondary data has great potential, it has some criticisms form different scholars like it is not extensively consumed by psychologist (Donnellan & Richard, 2013).

The literature on background of the country, CSR and Pakistani banks are collected by using secondary data. The researcher used various peer reviewed journals, articles, websites and books to gather the relevant information and data. Factual information about Pakistani banks are obtained from the websites of banks which contains annual reports.

The primary data collection is utilised by researcher to attain the empirical data. It includes the perception of managers working in Pakistani banks about the CSR and impact of CSR on financial performance. Surveys, interviews and observation are most commonly ways to collect

primary data. The researcher has adopted the appropriate techniques for this investigation which are surveys and interviews. The questionnaire was made by researcher and sent to the managers and upper management of Pakistani banks by using LinkedIn. The researcher believes that LinkedIn is a business and employment service used by many professionals to build network. Therefore, the researcher created new connections and built professional relationship from middle and top management working in Pakistani banks. A personalised message was sent to all respondents by researcher with a request of participating in the survey. The link of survey questionnaire which was created on Pollmill.com (a website used by researcher to create survey) was attached with the message. The questionnaire was designed with clear instruction and closed questions Likert scale. All the options of the question were on same page with all ethical considerations.

Moreover, the collection of primary data includes the interviews of the managers working in Pakistani banks. All the interviews were telephonic interviews. The details of the questionnaire and interview are presented in later sections of this chapter.

4.9 Mixed Methods.

4.9.1 Definitions of Mixed Methods.

In recent years, mixed methods have been defined in different ways by a number of scholars. These mixed methods scholars believe that qualitative and quantitative data and approaches will add insights as one considers most, if not all, research questions (Johnson, et al., 2007). Some of the definitions of mixed methods are elucidated as follow.

According to John Creswell, mixed methods research is research methodology in that an investigator gathers, evaluate and combine both qualitative and quantitative data in a solo or multistage procedure of investigation (Johnson, et al., 2007).

Mixed methods approach is also defined as

" the incorporation of one or more methodological strategies or techniques drawn from a second method, into a single research study, in order to access some part of the phenomena of interest that cannot be accessed by the use of the first method alone" (Morse, 1991, p. 9)

Burke Johnson and Anthony Onwuegbuzie defines mixed method as a method in which an investigator combines quantitative and qualitative method, approach and concept in a particular research (Johnson, et al., 2007).

Another scholar provided description of mixed methods approach as it is a set of processes that must utilised when assimilating qualitative and quantitative techniques reveals that research questions better than both can separately (Newman, et al., 2003). The combination of these two approaches can provide better understanding which enable the researcher to investigate and find the answer of the research question effectively. The mixed methods approach focuses on research question which call for real life contextual comprehensions, with multiple perception and cultural influences. Moreover, the utilisation of multiple methods strengthens each other and therefore, the researcher considered this approach as a suitable and appropriate one. Some definitions indicate that a researcher can combine there approaches at the data

collection and data analysis stage. However, some scholars claim that mixing can occur at any stage of the investigation (Johnson, et al., 2007).

Furthermore, it is also important to mention that there are three major research paradigm of mixed method approach (Johnson, et al., 2007). The first one is ‘qualitative dominant mixed methods’ research, in which any researcher who believes that it is crucial to involve qualitative data in his investigation. This type of research relies on a qualitative perspective whilst alongside adding together quantitative data. The second type of paradigm is of ‘quantitative dominant mixed research’ that depends on a quantitative perspective and along with identifying that the accumulation of qualitative data to add benefits to the study. The third one is ‘equal status’, in which an investigator believes that qualitative and quantitative data will provide strength and will give better comprehension to answer the research question. The researcher of this investigation selected ‘equal status mixed approach’ because it provides better insights and it is pure mixed method. The following figure illustrates the graphic of three major paradigms of mixed research methods.

Figure 16 Graphic of the Three major Research Paradigms of Mixed Methods Research (Johnson, et al., 2007)

Figure redacted for copyright reasons

Moreover, mixed methods approach is also referring as the combination of diverse qualitative and quantitative methods of data gathering and data evaluation in one empirical investigation as described by Udo Kelle (Johnson, et al., 2007). The researcher uses this combination of approaches in this investigation because it can assist to find and to deal with risks for validity appearing from the utilisation of qualitative or quantitative study by employing methods from another possible methodological practice and can therefore certify suitable scientific practice by enriching the validity of methods and research consequences. Another reason the researcher selected mixed methods approach because it can give richer picture and greater comprehension of researched phenomena by connecting corresponding results to each other that consequence from the utilisation of methods from the distinctive methodological practices of mixed method research.

The following section of the study provides more reasons behind the selection of mixed methods for this investigation.

4.9.2 Typical reasons for using Mixed methods.

Numeric data is related with quantitative whilst non-numeric is associated with qualitative data. Surveys and questionnaires come under quantitative unlike observations and interviews which is a part of qualitative. A fact, which is precise and justifiable, for instance numbers, are linked to quantitative and on contrary qualitative data is not scientific, and indistinct (Jonker & Pennink, 2010). This study comprises of mixed method, which means the primary data is collected by using questionnaires and interviews. Mixed research is a synthesis that includes ideas from qualitative and quantitative research (Johnson, et al., 2007).

The selection of data gathering method is influenced by different concerns which includes ability of the investigator, limitation of time and cost and more importantly to make sure the credibility (Frechtling & Sharp, 1997). Moreover, quantitative approach permits the investigator to determine the association between variables however, it fails to clarify or provide explanation of these associations. As a result of incapability to quantify selected phenomena utilising quantitative methods, there was a requirement of substitute approach has been raised, which direct towards the adaptation of qualitative approach (Streubert & Carpenter, 1999). Mixed methods approach in this study assists the researcher to gain more

advantaged from difference resources. It has strengthened the validity and reduced the weaknesses of the outcomes of the research of single approach (Yin, 2003). The quantitative approach gives the research validity, reliability and objectivity while the qualitative approach ensures the credibility, dependability and confirmability.

The following figure illustrates the difference between qualitative and quantitative approach.

Figure 17 Qualitative and Quantitative

(Newby, 2014)

Figure redacted for copyright reasons

The quantitative approach embodies a view societal reality as objective reality. It can be formed as a research strategy which entails a deductive approach put emphasis on quantification in gathering and data analysis (Bryman & Bell, 2007). On other hand, qualitative is a strategy which emphasis on words and embodies social reality as individual's property. It focuses on inductive approach and the manner in which a person understands their communal world. Qualitative approach is not concerned with testing of hypothesis but generating theories where quantitative has been utilised by many scholars to test the hypothesis. The researcher utilities mixed methods for this study and considered the factors of reliability and validity of quantitative and qualitative approaches.

Mixed methods research is becoming ever more interconnected with research practices and acknowledged as one of the most important approaches of research which is qualitative with

quantitative (Johnson, et al., 2007). The credit for the first to demonstrate unequivocally that in what manner a researcher can utilise multiple research method for authentication reasons, goes to Campbell and Fiske. (Campbell & Fiske, 1959). They also presented the notion of triangulation bring up to “multiple operationalism” in that a researcher can use more than one method to validate the process of research (Johnson, et al., 2007). However, the term triangulation was first summarised by Denzin and he defines it as follow:

“the combination of methodologies in the study of the same phenomenon” (Denzin, 2017, p. 291).

The researcher of this study selected to combine qualitative and quantitative approach because of several are reasons. Combination of both approaches can be effective for data collection and data evaluation (Sieber, 1973). At the stage of research design the qualitative data supported the qualitative element by recognising illustrative sample components along with outlying situations. On the contrary, at the stage of gathering data for the study, qualitative data can assist in facilitating the procedure of gathering data. When it comes to data evaluation phase, quantitative data can assist in evaluation and it will strengthen the outcomes of qualitative data. Moreover, qualitative data is plays crucial part at the phase of data evaluation by explaining and interpreting quantitative consequences as well as via supporting and modifying (Johnson, et al., 2007).

Thus, the main reasons to use the mixed methods approach in this study because it facilitates substantiation or confirmation of each other via triangulation and it also assists evaluation to present stronger and richer data (Rossman & Wilson, 1985). One of the several reasons for selecting mixed methods is that the researcher wants to view the research problems from multiple perspectives to achieve better understanding of research question and it will enhance the data. The researcher achieved macro visual of the Pakistani banking system and of employees as well.

4.9.3 The nature of Quantitative research.

Quantitative research is a method of study utilised mostly for deductive investigation, in which the objective is to assess theories or hypotheses. It also includes collecting data to examine the association amongst variables. The researcher then evaluated these variables are gauged and generate numeric data that can be scrutinised statistically. This type of data has the ability to present gaugeable verification, to support to determine cause and effect to produce effective data gathering processes and to create the probability of repetition and generality to a population. Quantitative data also has potential to enable the compare relationships of groups and to give comprehension of extensiveness of experiences. The researcher of the study has used surveys to collect quantitative data from the manager level employees of Pakistani banks.

4.9.4 The Criticism of Quantitative Research.

The criticism of quantitative research includes the argument that it fails to differentiate societal institutions and individuals from the world of nature (Bryman & Bell, 2007). Moreover, it is argued by scholars that the process of gauging has contrived and unauthentic view of accuracy and exactitude. The quantitative approach has critiques of assuming the concept instead of real. The dependence on instruments and techniques holds back the association amongst investigation and normal or everyday life. This criticism demonstrates that the gap between ideal type and actual practice can arise in any research. Therefore, the investigator of this study considered the pragmatic concern and had adopted to do the pilot test.

4.9.5 The nature of Qualitative research.

Qualitative research is inductive in nature and then the investigator discovers the meanings of the comprehension of the provided situation (Strauss & Corbin, 2008). The strong point of qualitative research is its concentration on the perspectives and meaning of lives of individual and knowledge for the objective of inductive research in which theory developed. The researcher has an opportunity to gather data directly from the participants and the data is used to develop theories (Hammersley & Atkinson, 1983). Qualitative research remains open to alternative explanations and provide better understanding of humans' thoughts and perceptions

(Mohajan, 2018). This is an organised and precise method of examination which utilises methods of gathering data for instance ethnographic observation and in-depth interviews. This investigation has used interviews of managers and upper management employees of Pakistani banks. The qualitative data has provided the researcher of this study understanding of the process and comprehensive information about the current situation of CSR in Pakistani banks. Qualitative data has enabled the gathering of data when measures do not exist and present intense comprehension of the notions. The researcher of this study was responsible for the achievement of true meaning and has considered ethical treatment of participants. However, in qualitative research the results are not objectively verifiable and the time requires for the process of data collection, evaluation and interpretation is lengthy.

4.9.6 The Critique of Qualitative Research.

There is some criticism by scholars on qualitative research method. Following are some of the most popular critiques which were considered by the researcher in this study.

- **Qualitative research is too subjective.** This method of research is mostly criticised by scholars of being too impressionistic and subjective. Qualitative method starts in a moderately open-ended way and involves an on-going focusing down to the objectives of an investigation (Bryman & Bell, 2007). This method often depends on the random perception of the investigator related to the importance of different elements.
- **Difficult to replicate.** A research with a qualitative approach is also criticised because it is complicated to replicate it. Because it is unstructured and mostly dependent on the inventiveness or creativity of the investigator. The researcher of qualitative research is the main instrument of collecting data therefore perception of researcher and decisions of concentrating on elements are of his or her preferences (Bryman & Bell, 2007).
- **Lack of Transparency.** It is challenging to determine research with a qualitative approach that how researcher attained the research findings. Sometimes it is unclear in qualitative research that how participants were selected for interviews or observation. It is criticised by researchers that qualitative data analysis is often vague and it lacks transparency. (Bryman & Bell, 2007).

The researcher considered the abovementioned criticism of qualitative and quantitative research approaches and selected to use mixed methods in this study.

4.9.7 The Convergent Parallel Design (Triangulation).

The convergent parallel design is one of the famous approaches to mixed methods and scholars began conferring this approach as early as the 1970s. This design was originally intellectualised as a 'triangulation'. The approach was also known by parallel study (Tashakkori & Teddlie, 1998), convergence model (Creswell, et al., 2003) and simultaneous triangulation (Morse, 1991). Triangulation involves utilising more than one technique or source of data in the investigation. It is one of the approaches proposed by Hammersley (1996) to mixed method research (Bryman & Bell, 2007). Triangulation indicates to utilisation of quantitative research to verify qualitative investigation results or vice versa (Bryman & Bell, 2007). The researcher employed method related with one strategy of research to cross-check the findings by using other method connected with other strategy of research. By combining survey and interviews the researcher was able cross-check the results and attain the accuracy of quantitative data. This approached is used to developed multiple measure to enhance the certainty in results. It provides the great opportunity of neutralizing the flaw of one method and intensification or strengthening the advantages of the other for the improved finding of investigation (Hussein, 2009). Moreover, triangulation also has been considered as a qualitative research strategy to assess the validity by means of merging of data from various sources (Carter, et al., 2014). There are three outcomes raise from triangulation convergence, inconsistency and contradiction (Denzin, 2017). Any of these effects predominate, the investigator can build better description or clarification of the phenomena. However, triangulation possibly will not be appropriate for all researches. The researcher of this investigation selected triangulation because it permits investigator to be more certain of the findings, it can lead to attain richer data and it can also find out inconsistencies.

Additionally, the researcher selected triangulation in this investigation because it is argued by many scholars that all methods individually are inconsistent and flawed but these drawbacks can be lessened by mixed method research (Turner, et al., 2017; Denzin, 2017).

4.9.7.1 The Purpose of the Convergent design.

The main reason behind the selection of the convergent design for this research was to attain diverse but complementary data on the same topic (Morse, 1991) of ‘CSR and its impact on financial performance of Pakistani banks’. The researcher used this design to compare and contrasting quantitative findings with qualitative results for validation and ratification. This design is the most suitable one because the researcher had time limitation to collect both type of data. The researcher believes that the value of qualitative and quantitative data is equal to comprehend the research problem. The researcher has managed both data collection and this mixed methods design is the most suitable one for the sole researcher. Moreover, triangulation comprises gathering, analysing and combining of quantitative and qualitative data. This mixed method design works from the paradigm which is pragmatism.

4.9.7.2 The Process of Convergent design.

The researcher of the study has adopted triangulation and the procedure of implementation this design has four major steps (Creswell & Clark, 2011). In first step the researcher has collected both quantitative and qualitative data based on the research question of the study. Both of these data are concurrent and independent of each other. However, both quantitative and qualitative data have equivalent significance. In the second step, the researcher has analysed both data sets individually. When the preliminary outcomes of both data were analysed by researcher than the researcher combined the results in the third step. In the last step the researcher has interpreted the convergence or divergence between both data sets to attain the objectives of this investigation. The following figure illustrates the process of convergent design.

Figure 18 Procedures in Implementing a Convergent Design

(Creswell & Clark, 2011)

Figure redacted for copyright reasons

4.9.7.3 Strengths of the convergent design.

There are few strong points or strengths of convergent designs which are elucidated as follow:

- The convergent design of mixed methods makes intuitive viewpoint. The researcher can select this design if they are novel to mixed methods. The researcher of this study was new to mixed methods research.
- This design is an effective approach that allows researcher to collect both quantitative and qualitative data at the same time in one phase. In this investigation, this design gave opportunity to researcher to collect both data at the same time as the researcher has limited time to complete the research.
- In this design, the researcher can gather and analysed both sets of data individually and separately. In this study the researcher has evaluated both data independently and then the researcher has interpreted the outcomes in later stage.

4.9.7.4 Challenges in Convergent design.

Even though the convergent design is one of the famous mixed methods designs, it has some challenges. The researcher of this investigation has confronted the following challenges in the in utilisation of convergent design.

- The researcher has to put a lot of determination and expertise because of concurrent data gathering and when the researcher has to ensure the equal weight has to be provided in both data. The researcher has addressed this by having training on both qualitative and quantitative research to increase expertise.
- The next challenge for the researcher was to consider the outcomes of having diverse samples and different sampling sizes when combining both sets of data.
- Another challenge for the researcher was the merging of both data and give meanings to the findings. The researcher has designed the study that both data address the same concepts of CSR and its impact on financial performance in Pakistani banks and

therefore, both data set findings were merged efficiently. There was no contradiction in quantitative and qualitative data sets.

4.9.8 Challenges in Mixed Methods Research.

There are a number of challenges considered by the researcher in mixed methods. The first challenge was of representation which indicates the fact that sampling concerns depicted both quantitative and qualitative research. In quantitative studies, several researches used sample size which are very small to identify statistical associations amongst variables (Schmidt, 1996; Sedlmeier & Gigerenzer, 1989). Similarly, in qualitative research the challenge of representation raises to the complications which an investigator encounters in attaining perceptions. In mixed methods study the concern of representation increased as both approaches carries different challenges. The researcher tried to improve representation challenge by selecting sampling decisions which are according to the research questions and research purpose. The researcher also enhanced representation by ensuring sample selected for every element of mixed methods is well-suited with research design (Collins, et al., 2007).

The second challenge in mixed methods study refer to validity or legitimisation. It is also suggested by scholars that the challenge of validity is higher in mixed methods than single method research (Collins, et al., 2007). The challenge for researcher is to obtain findings and making implications that are trustworthy and comprehensible (Onwuegbuzie & Johnson, 2006). The researcher of the study enhanced legitimation by making sure that inferences stem in a straight line from lie behind the sample of units. Moreover, it was also ensured by the researcher that the sampling design is suitable and will increase the validity of the research.

Another challenge in mixed methods research is the mixing or integration. It arises a question for researcher that how much weight should be given to each approach (qualitative and quantitative)? And was it appropriate to utilise triangulation in this study? This challenge was reduced by researcher by using appropriate sampling design which assists researcher to formulate meta-inference (Tashakkori & Teddlie, 1998).

4.10 Sampling

After the designing of questionnaire, the next step for this investigation was the process of sampling. The range of methods which assists researcher to bring down the quantity of data required is sampling (Saunders, et al., 2012). The data from the entire population is challenging to gather for researcher because there are different limitations and constrains for instance time limitation and finances. The researcher has to choose specific sampling method for reduction of data with the consideration of data from sub-group. The benefit of using apposite sampling technique is that a researcher can maintain budget and time. Probability and non-probability are the two sampling techniques. In probability sampling technique, each situation selected by people is acknowledged whereas in non-probability, to identify reply of every question is impossible. Scientific experiments are often connected with probability sampling technique whilst this study is under interpretivism, which is not established on statistical analysation and experiments (Collis & Hussey., 2014). The following figure illustrates different method of sampling from which the researcher has selected the appropriate one for this investigation.

Figure 19 Sampling

(Saunders, et al., 2012)

Figure redacted for copyright reasons

4.10.1 Identifying Population.

When a researcher, desires to study group of people, object or experiences the entire group of people is indicated as population. To attain the research objectives the researcher has selected to survey managers working in financial institution of Pakistan as a population. Public banks and private banks listed at the Pakistan stock exchange are identified as target population of the study.

4.10.2 Sampling Frame.

In this investigation, it was crucial for the researcher to complete or design the sampling frame. The real or definite list of sampling unit from which the sample is selected is known as sampling frame (Bryman & Bell, 2007). Imprecise sampling frame indicates that there are some items have rejected and it will be unachievable for population to have an opportunity of selection (Saunders, et al., 2012). In that case, the sample will not be illustrative of the whole population and can impact the results of the investigation. It is essential for a researcher to allows results to be comprehensive to the population (Sekaran, 2003). In this particular investigation, the sampling frame was the top and middle management of Pakistani banks. This enable researcher to use random sampling that can avoid research biasness.

Nevertheless, the collection of sampling frame for this investigation was challenging for the researcher. Different reliable sources were utilised by the researcher to attain information about Pakistani banks. Official websites of Pakistani banks were the main source for the researcher to accumulate the sampling frame. Moreover, LinkedIn was used to build connection with people working in upper and middle management in Pakistani banks.

4.10.3 Sampling Design.

Sampling design are divided into two different types which are probability sampling and non-probability sampling. Probability sampling is a type of sampling which shows that there is a probability of every variable being chosen from the population is acknowledged and is normally same for every situation. The purpose of probability sampling is holds sampling error to minimum level (Bryman & Bell, 2007). On other hand, the chance or probability of every element which is chosen from the whole population is unidentified in non-probability sampling (Saunders, et al., 2012). This approach of sampling does not select sample by utilising random selection method and some elements of the population are preferred than others. Sample selection are established on verdicts related to the nature of the target population (Fink, 2003). In this investigation, the researcher used probability sampling with stratified random sampling.

4.10.4 Stratified Random Sampling.

The stratified random sampling is select by researcher for this study. This type of sampling comprises a procedure of setting apart followed by random selection of subject from every division (Sekaran, 2003). Stratified sampling technique provides high level of representativeness and this became one of the reasons behind the selection of this sampling technique. The researcher divided population into sub group which were related to the objectives of the investigation. The sub group are public and private commercial banks. In the second step middle and top management was randomly selected by the researcher. The probability of sampling error will be reduced or minimised by using high degree of representativeness and therefore, stratified random sampling technique is the appropriate for this study.

4.10.5 Sample Size.

The sample size indicates the number of elements which need to be surveyed to attain the objectives of the investigation. The decision of sample size was affected by the consideration of time and cost. The researcher identified the total number of people working in Pakistan and then used sample calculator to make decision for sample size. It was challenging for the researcher to identify exact number of employees working in Pakistani banks. Therefore, the researcher used the number of employed people in Pakistan. The total population of employed person in Pakistan as stated in trading economics was 62230 in million (Trading economics, 2018). There are a number of people working in Pakistani retail banks. The number of employees in Pakistani banks are around 139,491 obtained from the financial statements of banks available in website of State bank of Pakistan (2017) . The name of banks and number of employees are listed below. The sample calculator is used by researcher with confidence level of 95% and confidence interval of 4%. It gauges the required sample size of 598. Therefore, the sample size of the study was 600, which was appropriate size. The following figure illustrates screen shot of sample size calculator.

Figure 20 Sample Size Calculator

Figure redacted for copyright reasons

Additionally, the following table demonstrates the name of Pakistani banks and number of employees which was taken from the authentic source of State bank of Pakistan.

Table 5 Number of Employees in Pakistani Banks.

(State Bank of Pakistan, 2017)

Figure redacted for copyright reasons

4.10.6 Sampling Issues.

There is different sampling issue involved in mixed methods research depending on the design. The researcher utilised convergent design and the main issue related to this design is that what sampling size is appropriate. Therefore, the researcher used sampling calculator to reduce the sampling error and determine the sampling size. Similarly, analytical and interpretive issue arises during evaluation of data. It was also a concern for the researcher that sampling technique used in this study should be ethical (Tashakkori & Teddlie, 2003).

4. 11 Research Instruments.

4.11.1 Questionnaire Development.

The process of developing questionnaire is based on what type of information is require in the investigation. This investigation is all about CSR and its impact on financial performance. Corporate social responsibility is one of the popular business strategies utilised by many organisations in developed country. Numerous scholars have studied CSR in context of developed world but there are only few investigations of emerging countries like Pakistan. The aim of this research is to study current CSR practice and its impact on financial performance in Pakistani banks. Therefore, the questionnaire was developed to achieve the research objectives which includes current CSR practice, managers perception and the impact of CSR on financial performance. The questionnaire was developed based on literature and modified by reviewing previously validated questionnaires. The researcher employed close-ended type questions in questionnaire to reduce the element of biasness. The reasons behind the selection of closed–ended questions are as follow, adopted from (Bryman & Bell, 2007).

- It is easy or uncomplicated to process the answer of close-ended questions.
- Close-ended questions increase the comparability of responses and simplifies to demonstrates the association amongst variables.
- It provides respondent, the clear meaning or sense of the question.

Nevertheless, there are some drawbacks of closed questions that it has fixed answers which does not allow respondent to make their choice. Also, there is a probability that respondents

have some interesting and informative response which is not included in closed-ended questions (Bryman & Bell, 2007).

The questionnaire was divided in two sections, the first section was about CSR and financial performance of the banks the second section was demographic profile of the respondents. Different types of data measuring scales were used in questionnaire such as nominal and interval Likert scale. All questions were developed by researcher and were constructed from the appropriate literature of CSR. One of the authentic and popular websites namely pollmill.com was employed to create questionnaire. The researcher sent the web link to the middle and upper management employees of the Pakistani banks. The questionnaire is presented in the appendix 9.1.

The questionnaire encompasses comprehensive guidelines or briefs with clear instructions, and was arranged to facilitate ease of response. The respondents are advised by the information message on LinkedIn about the nature of the investigation and why the study was being carried out with the background of the investigator. They were ensured of the privacy of the participants. Moreover, the researcher has considered to used appropriate wording in the questionnaire as it is one of the important principles in the process of designing questionnaire (Sekaran, 2003). As mentioned earlier, the measurement scale used by researcher in this questionnaire was Likert scale. The researcher selected this technique of measurement because it is one of the popular methods to measure attitudes (Miller & Brewer, 2003). A five-point Likert scale was the fundamental in the questionnaire to investigate the perception of participant, if they agree or disagree with the statements. Where '1' was 'strongly disagree' and '5' was 'strongly agree'.

4.11.1.1 LinkedIn use for Data collection.

LinkedIn is an employment-oriented service platform which is mainly used by professionals to build networks. It allows members to create profile and make connection in an online social network. The researcher of this study uses LinkedIn to make connections with upper and middle management of employees of Pakistani banks. The researcher sent personalised message to manager level employees working in Pakistani banks. The personalised message was comprising of brief introduction of the researcher, about the research topic and a request of accepting friend request to fill the survey questionnaire. The researcher sent link of the survey in personal message after the participant replied and accepted the request. The

researcher also informed all the participants that the survey is only for educational purpose and their name will not be included. Moreover, the researcher also informed all the participants that the results will be analysed as a group and their company name will not be included. It was a great experience of making professional connections.

4.12 Pilot Test

A pilot test was one of the instruments which was employed by researcher to ensure the relevance and appositeness of the questions. It also makes sure that the survey questions work well and research instrument as a whole operates well (Bryman & Bell, 2007). The researcher asked few open questions in the pilot test to generate the final questions. The reason of conducting pilot test is to inspect the consistency or regularity and quality of the questionnaire. It also provided the clarity to researcher to use the survey website. Reliability and validity of the questionnaire can also be enhanced by pilot test. The pilot test of the study was conducted in August 2017 and total number of respondents were 35. After the discussion on first draft of the questions with the director of studies, the questionnaire was sent to the employees of Pakistani banks. The questions were improved by the researcher by considering the response of some of the participants. A number of questions were added to the final draft of the questionnaire, which had the appropriate association with the purpose of the investigation.

There were various advantages of conducting pilot test in this investigation for instance, it provided ideas to make improvement and to ensure the clear results of the research. The investigator modified questions by rephrasing, reshaping and altering them to attain the objectives. It offers beneficial contributions in establishing the direction of the research. The final questionnaire constructed on the feedback of pilot test is presented in appendix.

4.13 Response Rate.

The researcher sent questionnaires to 600 different level of management employees working in Pakistani banks by means of social website LinkedIn. The researcher attained 250 responses out of 600 which were all anonymous. This provides the response rate of 45% which is noticeably adequate or sufficient for reliability of data (Stevens, 2002).

4.14 Data Management.

The process of data collection continued for three months from August 2017 until December 2017. This study adopted personal message approach by using LinkedIn as a method for data collection. During data collection, due process was followed such as sending reminders to respondents. However, respondents were not forced to participate in the survey. Moreover, primary data includes interviews of the managers working in Pakistani banks and the researcher employed telephonic interview technique. The details of interviews are elucidated in the later section.

Moreover, the data management is mainly based on statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) version 22 for data analysis. The researcher ensured to screen the data prior to conduct any analytical tests. Missing data can occur when any participants fails to answer any question in the questionnaire (Hair, et al., 2010). Form the 270 responses, the were 20 responses marked as incomplete, therefore 250 completed questionnaires were considered for data analysis by the researcher of this study.

SPSS program manages the quantitative data, although this investigation is based on mixed method. Therefore, the researcher used another program which was NVivo version 12, for qualitative data analysis. It is indicated that software packages like NVivo can accelerate the process of data analysis (Bergin, 2011). Although, the SPSS and NVivo are the programs or software tool which cannot be considered as substitute of thoughts, interpretation and reflection ability of the researcher (Basit, 2003).

4.15 Interviews.

One of the most popular techniques to collect primary data is interviews which provide knowledge and in-depth information. There are different ways of taking interviews including formal interviews through face-to face, online on social media and telephonic interviews. in comparison of questionnaire, interviews provide effective and in-depth data which permits the investigator to study individuals' opinions (Kvale, 2006). Moreover, it is accepted by various

scholars that interview is an advantageous technique for investigating the creation and discussion of meaning in natural setting. Interview is defined as

“an interview is an extendable conversation between partners that aims at having an ‘in-depth information’ about a certain topic or subject, and through which a phenomenon could be interpreted in terms of the meanings interviewees bring to it”. (Schostak, 2006, p. 54)

Interviews allows respondents to express their perception and opinion. The benefits of interview consist of the chance of gathering in-depth information in relation to the objective of the study. Additionally, this technique of gathering data allows researcher to manage the flow of the procedure and to make clear particular concerns, if required. The disadvantages of interview include complications related with organising a relevant time with sample group participants to conduct interview.

The researcher ensured to maintain the quality of the interview by considering two features of good interview which are “Good interview flows naturally and rich in detail” (Dörnyei, 2007, p. 140).

4.15.1 Critical evaluation of the Interviews.

Interview is a valuable instrument used by various researcher because it presents investigator the chance to discover information which is most likely not available utilising techniques for instance questionnaires and observations (Blaxter, et al., 2006). Interview is not only tool to gather data but a natural method or technique of communication which can occur in diverse circumstances. Moreover, it is argued by scholars that with the existence of interviewer, common perception can be ensured, because the respondent might rearticulate or make simpler questions that were not comprehended by interviewees (Dörnyei, 2007). The interview can be recorded by researcher to assist generating a precise report (Berg, 2007). This technique of collecting primary data is considered as cost-effective since expenses for person ‘utilising it for study purposes are decreased (Neuman, 2007).

On the other hand, there are few drawbacks of interviews argued by various scholars. Some intellectuals mention that interview is the highly essential or vital, disclosing and pleasant techniques of collecting primary data but it is disingenuously challenging (Hermanowicz, 2002; Alshenqeeti, 2014). Additionally, it is argued that

“what people say in an interview will indeed be shaped, to some degree, by the questions they are asked; the conventions about what can be spoken about;...[...]...by what time they think the interviewer wants; by what they believe he/she would approve or disapprove of” (Hammersley & Gomm, 2008, p. 100).

It demonstrates that interviewees will only provide limited information which they are willing to disclose. Interviews alone were not sufficient method to collect enough data for this investigation, therefore the researcher selected mixed research method. A number of scholars criticised interviews because they are time-consuming because the researcher has to make transcript, translate and code them (Alshenqeeti, 2014). The advantages and disadvantages of interviews are illustrated in the following table.

Table 6 Advantages and Disadvantages of Interviews

Advantages	Disadvantages
High return Rate	Time-consuming
Less unfinished answers	Small scale study
May comprise experience	Never fully anonymous
Precise answering order	Possibly for unintentional predisposition
Moderately flexible	Possibility of contradictions

(Brown, 2001; Alshenqeeti, 2014)

The above table demonstrates the advantages and disadvantages of interviews which was considered by the researcher of this study. Questionnaire was used as a supplement to interviews that allowed the researcher to obtain richer and valid data for this study. Smart phone application was used to record the interviews which helped the researcher to attain accuracy of participants words. Moreover, the researcher considered ethical aspect and only recorded few interviews after taking permission of the participants. The number of interviews were ten because after taking these interviews the researcher found the saturation point of interviews.

4.15.2 Data collection Process using Structured Interviews.

Structured interview was a technique or type of interview employed by the researcher in this study. It is also known as standardized interview (Bryman & Bell, 2007). This type of interviews contains a sequence of prearrange questions which were responded by all participants in the same succession. The purpose of this type of interview is to make sure that participants response can be aggregated and it can be attained if all replies are in response to equal cues. The analysis of data has tendency to be uncomplicated as the investigator can relate and differ various answers given to the same question. Structured interviews are commonly or generally utilised by researchers. The advantages of structured interviews include its accuracy and ease of data processing.

The investigator asked participants pre-determined questions that assists to be less deviated from the objective of the research. The list of questions was same for each participant with the effective input of the researcher, therefore, the gathered data was unintentionally bias. There are both types of questions included in the questionnaire, open-ended and closed-ended. A large number of closed-ended questions in interviews can reduce the interest of the respondent (Bryman & Bell, 2007). Thus, the number of open-ended questions were more than close-ended questions and all were very specific. Telephone interview was the method used in this study because it was cost effective and quicker to manage. It is easier to supervise a telephone interview rather than personal interview. However, there are some drawbacks of telephone interviewing that some people do not own the facility of phone which can create some of biasness (Bryman & Bell, 2007).

A selection criterion was used by the researcher of the study to select the participants so as to reduce bias and to attain richer information that can help to achieve research objectives. The sample size selected for interview by the researcher was based on two fundamental elements, the first one is the, extent of precision for the sample and the second one is, degree to that there is a distinction in the population related to main features of the research (Vaus, 2001). Moreover, time limitation and financial resources have great impact on the sample size. In this study the researcher has taken ten interviews of upper and top management employees of Pakistani banks.

The researcher started interviewing by introducing herself and providing the brief about the topic and research objectives. Then participants were free to express their selves and their perception about CSR in Pakistani banks. Both, the researcher and participants used combination of national language Urdu and English, which is widely used in Pakistan. All interviewees were assured about the confidentiality and have told by researcher that their name or their companies name would not be identified. The researcher also considered to make all the interview questions in coherent order and logical. The collected data were then transferred into transcripts and then the researcher used NVivo to code data and evaluate it.

4.15.3 Problem with Structured Interviewing.

One of the popular methods of collecting primary data in business research is structured interview. However, there are few drawbacks associated with structured interview which have been acknowledged by scholars over years. It was crucial for the researcher of this study to consider the following limitation of structured interview.

- **Attributes of interviewer.** The characteristics of the interviewer have an effect response of participants. These issues related to attributes includes difference of race, gender, ethnicity and socio-economic status (Bryman & Bell, 2007). This study is about the CSR impact in Pakistani banks and the researcher belongs to the same country, therefore, the attributes of interviewer and interviewees were almost similar.

- **Social desirability.** The social desirability indicates that some interviewees perceptions of the societal attractiveness have impact on their answers to questions. One of the objectives of this study is to attain the managers perception about CSR and this may include the social desirability. However, the research endeavoured to frame the questions in a way that enable the interviewees to detach themselves from their answers.
- **The challenge of meaning.** The problem with the meaning of answers given by respondents was considered by researcher. This critique revolves around that it is not necessary to share the same meaning of terms used by interviewer and respondent. But it was the priority to ensure the correct comprehension of the meaning of every term or answers by the investigator.

4.16 Ethical Issues

The issues with confidentiality and anonymity always raised in data collection and data analysis of any research. In this research, ethical concerns are considered by the researcher which are explicated as follow.

- **Anonymity of the Participants.** One of the most important ethical concern is invasion of privacy of the respondents. Protecting the anonymity of the respondents is anticipated to be an essential characteristic of an ethical research (Grinyer, 2002). The investigator of the study informed all respondents about the privacy and that their identity will never be documented. It also comprises the rights of the respondent to if the desire response to the particular question.
- **Confidentiality of Data.** It includes that when information given by participants which is considered to be confidential by the investigator. The investigator had to ensure that the information provided by participants are only for academic purpose. The respondents agreed and gave permission to include the information provided by them in this academic research.

- **Informed Consent.** The issue of informed consent is one of the most debated area in business research (Bryman & Bell, 2007). The bulk of discussion is related to the observation where true identity of researcher is unknown. However, in this study the researcher sent invitation to participants with the information of research aim and objectives. It was also informed by the investigator to all respondents that their participation is voluntary and they have right to withdraw.
- **Harm and Deception.** All the participants of this investigation were informed that data or information provided by them will manage carefully by researcher. It was also notified to all respondents that all data will be safeguarded and their identity will not be disclosed. It was also ensured by researcher that no one got harm which entails physical harm, stress, harm to respondents' self-esteem and harm to career prospects. The researcher had ensured the issue deception and had provided accurate explanation to participants.

4.17 Validity and Reliability of Research.

According to Lee (1999), reliability is the consistency of gauging a notion, utilising an equal procedure and replicability of results (Baumgarten, 2012). It is divided into two sections which are internal reliability and external reliability. the consistency of the indicators employed in research is related with internal reliability, where, external reliability refers if the results can be used widespread. Validity is divided into three sub section which are internal validity, external validity and construct validity. The researcher of the study considered the reliability and validity aspects of the investigation.

4.17.1 Reliability and validity of Cross-sectional Design.

The reliability and validity of cross-sectional design are important for the researcher which relates to the quality of the measures. Cross-sectional design creates correlations instead of

results from which unexpected assumptions can be unmistakably made. In this design, the external validity is strong, the data of this research is gathered from random sampling. This research design creates a good deal of utilising of different investigation instruments which includes structured interviews and questionnaire. The validity of this research design can be at risk as these instruments mess up with 'natural habitat' (Bryman & Bell, 2007). When it comes to internal validity, of the cross-sectional design, is usually not strong. It was challenging for the researcher to determine casual direction from the subsequent data.

4.17.2 Reliability of Quantitative research.

Reliability indicates to the dependability or uniformity of a measure of a notion. The factors which has to be consider when measuring reliability are elucidated below:

- **Stability.** The stability test of reliability is a related with measure of test one hypothesis and then test it again. It entails examining if the measure is stable over time. However, the researcher has selected the cross-sectional design for this investigation.
- **Inter-observer consistency.** The activities like recording of observations are involved in immense deal of subjective judgment, then there is a probability of deficiency of uniformity in their results. The researcher is not focusing on this factor because of the nature of this particular investigation.
- **Internal reliability.** This is the most appropriate factor which relates to this investigation. In this research, the main concern is of the consistency of the index or scale. The researcher had to ensure that the score of the respondent on any indicator has tendency to be associated to their score on other indicator. The questionnaire of this investigation was completed by many respondents and therefore this study has multiple-item measure. There is a chance of dearth of consistency or coherence. The researcher has ensured that all indicators are associated to each other. The research has used the following test for the internal reliability test.

4.17.3 Cronbach's Alpha.

Cronbach's alpha is the test for internal reliability used by many other investigators is selected by researcher for this study. All probable split-half reliability coefficient is effectively evaluated by this test. The coefficient will vary between the value of 1 and 0. In order to evaluate the internal consistency of measured items in the data of the study, the researchers carried out Cronbach Alpha test in IBM SPSS version 22. the following table demonstrates the inter- item statistics of Philanthropic responsibilities.

Philanthropic responsibilities.

Item-Total Statistics					
	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Squared Multiple Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
Funding scholarship programs or activities	12.26	9.077	.928	.948	.825
Sponsoring public health projects	12.28	9.078	.931	.961	.824
Donations of cash, products, or employee services to support community activities, events, arts, sports	12.25	8.968	.936	.932	.822
Sponsoring education conference, seminar, workshop or art exhibits Aiding disaster victims	12.27	9.072	.924	.932	.826
Supports and encourages the development of rural areas of the country	11.93	14.160	.075	.031	.987

Inter-Item Correlation Matrix

	Funding scholarship programs or activities	Sponsoring public health projects	Donations of cash, products, or employee services to support community activities, events, arts, sports	Sponsoring education conference, seminar, workshop or art exhibits Aiding disaster victims	Supports and encourages the development of rural areas of the country
Funding scholarship programs or activities	1.000	.972	.944	.939	.070
Sponsoring public health projects	.972	1.000	.950	.954	.053
Donations of cash, products, or employee services to support community activities, events, arts, sports	.944	.950	1.000	.953	.101
Sponsoring education conference, seminar, workshop or art exhibits Aiding disaster victims	.939	.954	.953	1.000	.068
Supports and encourages the development of rural areas of the country	.070	.053	.101	.068	1.000

The above table demonstrates the item total statistics and inter-item correlation matrix of philanthropic responsibilities. The correlation matrix displays the how each item correlates to all other items. As illustrated in table list of 1.000 across diagonal. This presents the perfect correlation of each item to another.

In item-total statistic there are two important things the corrected item and Cronbach's Alpha if item deleted. As it is indicated by the name the if the researcher removed each item from the questionnaire. The above table shows that all items are related and needed to be in questionnaire.

Employees.

Inter-Item Correlation Matrix

	Gives rewards to employees	Provides health care for the employees including health assistance, maternity leave	Provides finance or loan to the employees for their higher education	Provides Employees training	Complying with health and safety standards and regulations	Provides better working environment to employees	Has rules related to employee discrimination
Gives rewards to employees	1.000	.979	.962	.958	.144	.025	-.073
Provides health care for the employees including health assistance, maternity leave	.979	1.000	.966	.966	.131	.016	-.081
Provides finance or loan to the employees for their higher education	.962	.966	1.000	.962	.163	.016	-.051
Provides Employees training	.958	.966	.962	1.000	.142	-.024	-.071
Complying with health and safety standards and regulations	.144	.131	.163	.142	1.000	.114	.552
Provides better working environment to employees	.025	.016	.016	-.024	.114	1.000	.415
Has rules related to employee discrimination	-.073	-.081	-.051	-.071	.552	.415	1.000

Item-Total Statistics

	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Squared Multiple Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
Gives rewards to employees	19.21	12.497	.824	.963	.714
Provides health care for the employees including health assistance, maternity leave	19.23	12.530	.819	.971	.715
Provides finance or loan to the employees for their higher education	19.21	12.441	.829	.950	.713
Provides Employees training	19.22	12.614	.804	.948	.719
Complying with health and safety standards and regulations	18.86	16.549	.272	.363	.816
Provides better working environment to employees	18.64	17.379	.109	.228	.846
Has rules related to employee discrimination	18.54	17.583	.140	.458	.832

The above table demonstrates the interitem correlation matrix and item total statistics. It is indicated in the table that all the items in employees' sections of questionnaire are correlated and have internal consistency therefore the researcher included these in questionnaire.

Environment.

Inter-Item Correlation Matrix

	Has environmental policies	Gives importance to pollution reduction	Believes in conservation of natural resources (energy conservation)	Efficiency in waste management.	Engaged in eco-friendly products
Has environmental policies	1.000	.008	.579	.578	.678
Gives importance to pollution reduction	.008	1.000	-.014	-.007	.024
Believes in conservation of natural resources (energy conservation)	.579	-.014	1.000	.393	.479
Efficiency in waste management.	.578	-.007	.393	1.000	.763
Engaged in eco-friendly products	.678	.024	.479	.763	1.000

Item-Total Statistics

	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Squared Multiple Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
Has environmental policies	14.56	7.067	.663	.550	.569
Gives importance to pollution reduction	15.45	9.927	.004	.003	.847
Believes in conservation of natural resources (energy conservation)	14.86	7.979	.491	.350	.643
Efficiency in waste management.	14.41	7.239	.618	.590	.588
Engaged in eco-friendly products	14.42	6.574	.710	.672	.539

Customers.

Inter-Item Correlation Matrix

	Responds to the customer's complaints in a satisfactory manner	Has ethical standards and policies related to advising of the product and services	Provides Clear and accurate information to customers
Responds to the customer's complaints in a satisfactory manner	1.000	.961	.638
Has ethical standards and policies related to advising of the product and services	.961	1.000	.664
Provides Clear and accurate information to customers	.638	.664	1.000

Item-Total Statistics

	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Squared Multiple Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
Responds to the customer's complaints in a satisfactory manner	7.43	2.206	.885	.923	.795
Has ethical standards and policies related to advising of the product and services	7.38	2.172	.905	.927	.777
Provides Clear and accurate information to customers	7.46	2.868	.657	.440	.980

Legal.

Inter-Item Correlation Matrix

	Pays all the taxes on time	Complying with various federal, state, and local regulations.	Providing goods and services that at least meet minimal legal requirements.	Performing in a manner consistent with expectations of government and law.
Pays all the taxes on time	1.000	.720	.863	.847
Complying with various federal, state, and local regulations.	.720	1.000	.715	.816
Providing goods and services that at least meet minimal legal requirements.	.863	.715	1.000	.784
Performing in a manner consistent with expectations of government and law.	.847	.816	.784	1.000

Inter-Item Correlation Matrix

	Pays all the taxes on time	Complying with various federal, state, and local regulations.	Providing goods and services that at least meet minimal legal requirements.	Performing in a manner consistent with expectations of government and law.
Pays all the taxes on time	1.000	.720	.863	.847
Complying with various federal, state, and local regulations.	.720	1.000	.715	.816
Providing goods and services that at least meet minimal legal requirements.	.863	.715	1.000	.784
Performing in a manner consistent with expectations of government and law.	.847	.816	.784	1.000

Financial Performance

Inter-Item Correlation Matrix

	Net profit of your bank in previous five years was	EPS of your bank in previous five years was	ROA of your bank in previous five years was	ROE of your bank in previous five years was
Net profit of your bank in previous five years was	1.000	.237	.282	.164
EPS of your bank in previous five years was	.237	1.000	.260	.177
ROA of your bank in previous five years was	.282	.260	1.000	.152
ROE of your bank in previous five years was	.164	.177	.152	1.000

Item-Total Statistics

	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Squared Multiple Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
Net profit of your bank in previous five years was	9.98	3.686	.335	.118	.426
EPS of your bank in previous five years was	10.05	3.616	.330	.111	.430
ROA of your bank in previous five years was	9.66	3.719	.343	.126	.419
ROE of your bank in previous five years was	9.20	4.182	.232	.054	.512

The above all tables demonstrated the inter-item correlation and item total statistics of philanthropic responsibilities, employees, environment, customers, legal and financial performance. the summary of Cronbach Alpha is illustrated in following table.

Table 7 Summary of Cronbach's Alpha

Serial No.	Construct	No. of Items	Cronbach's Alpha	Comments
1	Philanthropic	5	.893	Accepted
2	Employees	7	.800	Accepted
3	Environment	5	.702	Accepted
4	Customers	3	.904	Accepted
5	Legal	4	.938	Accepted
6	Financial performance	4	.520	Rejected

The value of Cronbach's Alpha is above than 0.8 as illustrated in above table. It indicates that there is a high level of consistency of the scale of the research data (Nunnaly, 1978; Sekaran, 2003; Hair, et al., 2010; Field, 2009). Therefore, the researcher accepted all items. The Cronbach Alpha value of financial performance is 0.52 which is poor according to the rule of the test. However, the researcher believes that there is a high level of consistency in financial variables but the test is conducted on SPSS which will only read the data entered.

4.17.4 Normality test of Data.

This section of the study presents the normality test of the data obtained from the survey. Normality test used by researcher to ensure that the data is normally distributed. In statistics normally indicates the data distribution that is a basic assumption of gauging the dissimilarity of items or variable. The normality of data is often considered as myth (Elliott & Woodward, 2007; Das & Rahmatullah Imon, 2016) but some scholars suggested that it is assumed by scholars that data is better if it is distributed normally (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2013). Moreover, the normality of data can be seen by using plots and by significance tests. It is also indicated by scholars that instead of using test it is always easy to look at the shape of the plot (Trowler, 2014). However, the normality tests are sensitive to sample size and with the large sample size minor disruption of the distribution possibly will not become the foundation of main concerns (Field, 2009; Ghasemi & Zahediasl, 2012). The sample size of this research is $n=250$ which is large enough.

In this investigation the researcher has conducted normality test by using normality P-P-plot and histogram. The following figure illustrates the level of normality is acceptable and the bell shape curve of histogram also shows that the data of this investigation is approximately normally distribute.

Figure 21 Visual Indication of Normality.

Moreover, the researcher has conducted Skewness and Kurtosis test for normality. Skewness is used to measure of data symmetry while Kurtosis is used to measure peakedness of distribution. The following table illustrates the summary of Skewness and Kurtosis.

Skewness

The skewness value can be positive or negative, or even undefined.

If skewness is 0, the data are perfectly symmetrical.

As a general rule of thumb

If skewness is less than -1 or greater than 1, the distribution is highly skewed.

If skewness is between -1 and -0.5 or between 0.5 and 1, the distribution is moderately skewed.

If skewness is between -0.5 and 0.5, the distribution is approximately symmetric.

Kurtosis

Kurtosis was originally thought to be a measure the “peakedness” of a distribution.

If the kurtosis is close to 0, then a normal distribution is often assumed.

If the kurtosis is less than zero, then the distribution is light tails and is called a platykurtic distribution.

If the kurtosis is greater than zero, then the distribution has heavier tails and is called a leptokurtic distribution.

Table 8 Skewness and Kurtosis.

The following table demonstrates the descriptive statistics with Skewness and kurtosis of this research data. It shows that the data is approximately normally distributed.

	Descriptive Statistics				
	N	Skewness		Kurtosis	
	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Std. Error
Funding scholarship programs or activities	249	.016	.154	-.121	.307
Sponsoring public health projects	250	.008	.154	-.229	.307
Donations of cash, products, or employee services to support community activities, events, arts, sports	250	-.019	.154	-.307	.307
Sponsoring education conference, seminar, workshop or art exhibits	250	.013	.154	-.229	.307
Aiding disaster victims	250	-.276	.154	-.926	.307
Supports and encourages the development of rural areas of the country	250	-.037	.154	-.118	.307
Gives rewards to employees	250	-.032	.154	-.174	.307
Provides health care for the employees including health assistance, maternity leave	250	-.061	.154	-.218	.307
Provides finance or loan to the employees for their higher education	250	-.047	.154	-.177	.307
Provides Employees training	250	-.237	.154	-.957	.307
Complying with health and safety standards and regulations	250	-.708	.154	.275	.307
Provides better working environment to employees	250	-.502	.154	-.153	.307
Has rules related to employee discrimination	250	-.507	.154	-.475	.307
Has environmental policies	250				

Gives importance to pollution reduction	250	.159	.154	-.761	.307
Believes in conservation of natural resources (energy conservation)	250	-.406	.154	-.646	.307
Efficiency in waste management.	250	-.454	.154	-.946	.307
Engaged in eco-friendly products	250	-.477	.154	-.993	.307
Responds to the customer's complaints in a satisfactory manner	250	-.517	.154	-.268	.307
Has ethical standards and policies related to advising of the product and services	250	-.635	.154	-.088	.307
Provides Clear and accurate information to customers	250	-.473	.154	.245	.307
Pays all the taxes on time	250	-.585	.154	.572	.307
Complying with various federal, state, and local regulations.	250	-.737	.154	1.407	.307
Providing goods and services that at least meet minimal legal requirements.	250	-.458	.154	.298	.307
Performing in a manner consistent with expectations of government and law.	250	-.783	.154	1.281	.307
Net profit of your bank in previous five years was	250	.040	.154	-.128	.307
EPS of your bank in previous five years was	250	.026	.154	-.238	.307
ROA of your bank in previous five years was	250	-.193	.154	-.516	.307
ROE of your bank in previous five years was	250	-.311	.154	-.627	.307
Valid N (listwise)	249				

Table 9 Descriptive statistics

4.17.5 Validity of Quantitative data.

Validity represents to the concern of whether or not indicator which is created to measure a notion certainly determine that notion. There are various methods utilised by several scholars. The following are the types indicates distinctive techniques of assessing the validity of measures of a notion used by the investigator.

Face validity. The researcher has established face validity by requesting the director of studies, who has the expertise in the area of study. It was ensured by the researcher that all the measures reflect the concept of the investigation.

Concurrent validity. To gauge the validity of measure, it was the next technique used by researcher. The criterion was employed by researcher on which situations or paradigms are known to contrast and the other one is more appropriate to the research objectives.

Construct validity. Many scholars encourage that construct validity is an important technique to evaluate the validity of measures. The researcher was cautious and ensured that the deduction of the theory is not misguided and there is no invalid measure of the concept.

4.17.6 Reliability and Validity in Qualitative Research.

Reliability and validity are important criteria in establishing and assessing the quality of qualitative research. The validity and reliability are various kind of gauges of quality and extensive potential of the investigation (Bryman & Bell, 2007). The researcher had considered validity and reliability of the qualitative data of the study. External reliability which indicates the degree to which a research can be replicated, was considered by the investigator. Moreover, internal reliability indicates that if there is one more observer. This study includes interviews and the researcher make one more researcher to listen to the recording and verify the translation of the transcripts to ensure the internal reliability. Additionally, this study acknowledged emerging patterns from various data sources comprises secondary data gathering method. It presents data indicating to the investigation validity and reliability. The following table demonstrates the technique, methodology used in the research to ensure reliability and validity.

Table 10 Reliability and Validity methodology

Technique	Methodology	Application in the Research
Inclusive qualitative analysis	Study of numerous kinds of data sources for instance Documents and secondary data from official websites of banks, Interviews with all relevant persons; Presence of precise quotations to demonstrates societal perspective	Internal and external validity of the study has attained.
Data analysis	Analysis has done by using: Association amongst data obtained from primary sources; Assessing data gathered from secondary sources; Comparison with experts' evaluations; Association with theoretic results	Using Cronbach alpha in SPSS, Generating thematic review
Comparison of evidence for consistency	Analysing through techniques	Making of pattern- matching originated from pattern coding, which establishes the

	Authentication consequences used as detailed cases.	of used as	foundation for generalisations.
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Tests	Strategies	Methods/ Approaches
Internal validity	Mixed method	Associate and converge results obtained from primary and secondary data analyses
External validity	Includes distinct CSR theories in research	Study within distinguishing theories
Construct validity	Employing various sources Determining sequence of data Evaluating association amongst information gathered and their analysis.	Analysis of interviews and documentation Maintaining all collected information and their evaluation in sequential
Reliability	Utilisation of research procedure	Comprehended organised path of investigation.

4.18 Summary of the Chapter.

This chapter of the research was about the research methods and approaches were used in this study, to achieve the research objectives. Research paradigms, philosophy and research design are elucidated in this section. The researcher used mixed method with inductive and deductive approach. The researcher employed primary and secondary data to gather the relevant information. Secondary data was obtained by means of peer reviewed journals, articles and official websites of Pakistani banks. Moreover, instruments of research which includes survey and interview techniques are also discussed. Sample design used in this research was probability sampling with stratified sampling techniques. Population, sample size and sampling frame were also part of the discussion. In the end, reliability and validity of the research, which determines the quality of the research was explicated. These all techniques, methods and approaches of research methodology are elucidated in this chapter with consideration of their critical aspects. Moreover, the ethical issues were considered by investigator.

5 Chapter Five.

5.1 Data Analysis and Presentation of the Result

5.2 Introduction:

The factual information consumed as a base for analysing and discussing or any information in arithmetical form that can be managed digitally is recognised as data. This chapter of the research describes the finding or results of the study and analysis of the data through statistics tests. It is believed by scholars that data takes meaning when it is interpreted and turn into information. The demographic background of the respondents, who participated in this study, is the first part of this chapter. The main purpose of this chapter is to look at awareness of the middle and top management officials of Banks in Pakistan, related to the corporate social responsibility. Additionally, the chapter also presents the level of CSR and its association with financial performance in Pakistani banks. Moreover, the reason behind practicing CSR in banks are also evaluated in this chapter. As a result of assessing examining data the researcher can find pattern which will be the contribution to the knowledge of CSR.

5.3 Account based and Market based Analysis:

A number of organisations are using various and diverse ways to evaluate their financial performance which is mostly market based measure and economic based measure. The divergence amongst the market value of the debt and equity and capital employed in the organisation is market value added. It is the total of the all capital demanded together with the market value of debt and equity. Economic value added is explained as the net profit of a firm excluding a suitable rate for the opportunity cost of all capital. It is the evaluation accurate financial performance. On other hand, market value added is the distinction amongst the entire capital engaged in the corporation and the market value of the debt and equity.

It is indicated by the name that this measure is established on accounting practice of economic reporting of a firm. Every organisation presents annual report that includes the accounting based financial reporting. An annual report of an organisation gives historical perception of financial accomplishment of the firm.

Return on Equity (ROE) is assessed by net income and it indicates the productivity of a company by determining the return of investors. Return on assets (ROA) contemplates the assets consumption of an organisation and it is evaluated by using the net assets of a company. The second instrument to measure the financial performance is market-based measure. As it is understood by, the name that market based measure is established on the market index (Amit & Livant, 1988). One of the expectations of the shareholders is the prices of stock market to the forthcoming value of the organisation. Additionally, it has been observed that in previous few years, many organisations are using different and contemporary measure of financial performance, which are market value added and economic value added. The divergence amongst the market value of the debt and equity and capital employed in the organisation is market value added. It is the total of the all capital demanded together with the market value of debt and equity. Economic value added is explained as the net profit of a firm excluding a suitable rate for the opportunity cost of all capital. It is the evaluation accurate financial performance. On other hand, market value added is the distinction amongst the entire capital engaged in the corporation and the market value of the debt and equity. The following table shows the average of ROE, ROA, net profit, EPS growth rate of Pakistani banks of previous five years of banks in Pakistan.

Table 11 Average Profitability of Pakistani banks.

S.no	Name of banks	ROE 5years	ROA	Net profit	EPS Growth Rate
1.	Allied bank	17.35	1.59	35.46	1.76
2.	Habib bank	15.63	1.25	25.88	-19.17
3.	United bank	17.96	1.80	32.87	6.45
4.	Askari bank	10.83	0.56	14.54	24.01
5.	Bank Alfalah	14.30	0.87	20.03	9.35
6.	Bank Al Habib	21.51	1.21	27.46	12.41
7.	JS Bank	11.72	1.12	21.74	31.58
8.	MCB	17.26	2.35	38.79	0.39
9.	Faysal bank	12.06	0.86	19.14	26.03
10.	Standard Chartered	15.84	2.16	35.33	6.76
11.	Meezan bank	19.05	1.04	23.60	8.60
12.	Metropolitan bank	16.05	1.34	28.85	13.25
13.	The bank of Khyber	10.75	1.21	29.12	11.69
14.	Bank of Punjab	18.46	0.81	26.37	42.73
15.	Samba bank	3.05	0.58	14.17	7.38

(Reuters, 2018)

5.4 Investment on CSR of Commercial and Islamic Banks.

The following table demonstrates the overall contribution on activities related to corporate social responsibilities, of the commercial and Islamic banks in Pakistan. The commercial banks in Pakistan are investing more than Islamic banks as indicated in the table. Commercial banks are rich and contribute in various CSR activities whilst Islamic banks like Meezan bank, are still underdeveloped in their CSR practices. On contrary, many banks are rich and make a lot of investments on CSR; because of their size and stability in Pakistan for example, NBP is a bank that belongs to public sector are doing much better now a days. Moreover, the following table illustrates the investment of total investment on CSR by Pakistani banks in previous five years.

Table 12 CSR Investment by Pakistani banks in Previous Five years

Years	MCB	Faysal bank	Standards chartered	Metropolitan bank	The bank of Khyber	Bank of Punjab	Samba bank
2013	12500	46458	24540	35462	3270	19	1667
2014	5000	36998	263514	12540	3277	20117	23037
2015	20600	49539	17656	17840	1255	1447	25980
2016	2600	131621	24436	92450	235	533	153
2017	13200	154382	2941	82260	280	1125	4300

Years	Allied bank	Habib bank	United Bank	Askari bank	Bank Alfah	Bank Alhabib	JS bank	Meezan
2013	80	4093	77	2500	36000	21750	10000	130110
2014	76	38401	112	6140	32695	48800	32000	10850
2015	13915	38672	167	35000	57638	49100	63473	98294
2016	41878	38023	3098	4786	31960	184900	67800	37817
2017	54209	89059	1320	12688	9948	124229	32000	31050

(Allied Bank Limited, 2016; United Bank Limited, 2016; National Bank of Pakistan , 2017; Meezan Bank Limited, 2016; State Bank of Pakistan, 2017)

The investments on CSR by Pakistani banks are demonstrated in above table, this information of data is adopted from the secondary data (financial statements of banks). As indicated in literature that most of Pakistani banks are more inclined towards charity, healthcare and education. The above two tables demonstrate the most of Pakistani banks are increasing their investment in CSR. One of the famous banks in Pakistan like MCB, Habib bank and Askari banks had encouraged CSR activities and increased investment in previous five years.

5.5 Analysis of the Quantitative data (Questionnaire):

5.5.1 Section 1

5.5.2 Background of the Respondents:

The respondents are upper and middle management of the banks in Pakistan. This is the section one of the questionnaire which elucidates the detailed descriptive statistical analysis of the characteristics of the respondents. Demographic refers to the specific characteristics of the respondents of a particular research (Salkind, 2010). A comprehension of the background of the respondents may provide further understanding into the perception of the middle management working in Pakistani banks. The total number of respondents of this study is 250 out of the 600 distributed questionnaires.

5.5.2.1 Profile and Position of the respondents

		Position			Cumulative Percent
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	
Valid	Operation	16	6.4	6.4	6.4
	Supervisor	27	10.8	10.8	17.2
	Manager	96	38.4	38.4	55.6
	Senior Manager	69	27.6	27.6	83.2
	General Manager	35	14.0	14.0	97.2
	Director	7	2.8	2.8	100.0
	Total	250	100.0	100.0	

As this table depicts that most of the respondents were mostly managers. Approximately, half of the respondent which is 38.4 percent were managers. On other hand, the next highest number of respondents is of senior managers of Pakistani banks, as illustrates in the table 27.6 percent. Relatively, few were either of general manger position (14.0 percent), director position (2.8 percent), operation (6.4 percent) and supervisors (10.8 percent).

		Division			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Customer Services	45	18.0	18.0	18.0
	Treasury Management	15	6.0	6.0	24.0
	Marketing	97	38.8	38.8	62.8
	Human Resources	59	23.6	23.6	86.4
	Information Technology	13	5.2	5.2	91.6
	Revenue Management	7	2.8	2.8	94.4
	Other	14	5.6	5.6	100.0
	Total	250	100.0	100.0	

The above table demonstrates that the participants were from the diverse department of the banks. As illustrated in the table, most of the participants were from marketing department 38.8%. The other major department participated in research were form customer services 18.0% while human resource 23.6 % and another department came after that including information technology 5.2% , revenue management 2.8% and other departments were 5.6%.

		Education			Cumulative
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Percent
Valid	High School	5	2.0	2.0	2.0
	College	11	4.4	4.4	6.4
	Bachelors	50	20.0	20.0	26.4
	Masters	167	66.8	66.8	93.2
	Doctoral	7	2.8	2.8	96.0
	Other	10	4.0	4.0	100.0
	Total	250	100.0	100.0	

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Position	250	1	6	3.40	1.138
Division	250	1	7	3.23	1.526
Education	250	1	6	3.76	.830
Valid N (listwise)	250				

Additionally, the following tables illustrates the size and profile of the bank of respondents. 43.6% of participants are from large organisation while 40.4 percent are from medium size company. Only 16.% respondents belong to small banks in Pakistan.

		Size			Cumulative
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Percent
Valid	Large	109	43.6	43.6	43.6
	Medium	101	40.4	40.4	84.0
	Small	40	16.0	16.0	100.0
	Total	250	100.0	100.0	

		Profile			Cumulative
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Percent
Valid	Public	93	37.2	37.2	37.2
	Private	157	62.8	62.8	100.0
	Total	250	100.0	100.0	

The above table shows that 37.2% participants are working in public Pakistani banks while a large number of participants that is 62.8% belong to private Pakistani banks.

5.5.3 Section 2

5.5.4 Manager's Perception

The perception of upper and middle management of Pakistani banks are discussed in this section. The researcher has divided the perception of managers in following sub sections

- Meaning of CSR in Managers' Perception.
- The purpose behind the CSR practice by banks.
- CSR activities in Pakistani banks
- Reason behind Pakistani banks not participating in CSR activities.
- Perception of manager related to the CSR impact on financial performance.

The meaning of CSR in Managers' Perception

		Meaning			Cumulative
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Percent
Valid	Societal Activities	134	53.6	53.6	53.6
	Value for Stakeholders	22	8.8	8.8	62.4
	Paying Taxes	11	4.4	4.4	66.8
	Customer Services	32	12.8	12.8	79.6
	Abiding Law	13	5.2	5.2	84.8
	Safe working Environment	38	15.2	15.2	100.0
	Total	250	100.0	100.0	

The table demonstrates that most of the managers in Pakistani banks that is, 53.6% consider that corporate social responsibility means social activities. Only 12.8% related CSR to the customer services and 15.2% includes safe working environment to the CSR activity. While 8.8% believe that CSR can create value for stakeholders and only 5.2% associated CSR with abiding law. Paying taxes is ethical responsibility of every individual and every organisation, although managers in Pakistani banks do not consider it as a corporate social responsibility as demonstrated in the above table, 4.4% of managers relate CSR with paying taxes.

The purpose behind the CSR practice by banks

		Purpose			Cumulative
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Percent
Valid	Innovation	10	4.0	4.0	4.0
	Government Pressure	14	5.6	5.6	9.6
	Cost Saving	17	6.8	6.8	16.4
	Suppliers' Relations	15	6.0	6.0	22.4
	Increase Sales	83	33.2	33.2	55.6
	Consumers' Satisfaction	47	18.8	18.8	74.4
	Investors' Attention	25	10.0	10.0	84.4
	Competitive Advantage	39	15.6	15.6	100.0
	Total	250	100.0	100.0	

Figure 22 Purpose behind CSR

The frequency and the area chart show that most of the managers (33.2%) in Pakistani banks consider that the purpose of practicing CSR by Pakistani banks is increase in sales. Moreover, 18.8% managers believe that the banks practice CSR can satisfy consumers while 15.6% managers consider that CSR can provide competitive advantage. Only 6.8% managers believe that CSR can reduce the cost and 6.0% relates CSR to relations with suppliers. The researcher believes that CSR can reduce cost and attract investors. The banks in Pakistan should realise the importance of CSR and create awareness programs. Only 4% of managers related CSR with innovation and 5.6% believe that banks participate in CSR activities because of pressure from the government.

CSR activities in Pakistani banks

		Activities			Cumulative
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Percent
Valid	Charity	102	40.8	40.8	40.8
	Health and Safety	15	6.0	6.0	46.8
	Protection of Law	31	12.4	12.4	59.2
	Environmental Activities	55	22.0	22.0	81.2
	Employees Training	36	14.4	14.4	95.6
	Scholarship to Students	11	4.4	4.4	100.0
	Total	250	100.0	100.0	

The above frequency demonstrates that 40.8% of Pakistani banks focus on charities as a CSR activity. 22.0% of participants consider environmental activities are the part of CSR. Health and safety (6.0%) and scholarship to students (4.4%) are less popular activities by Pakistani banks. The following pie chart illustrates the better understanding of the frequencies.

Figure 23 CSR activities in Pakistani banks

Reason behind Pakistani banks not participating in CSR activities.

		Reason			Cumulative
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Percent
Valid	Expense	71	28.4	28.4	28.4
	Lack of interest	41	16.4	16.4	44.8
	Lack of Awareness of CSR	114	45.6	45.6	90.4
	Other	24	9.6	9.6	100.0
	Total	250	100.0	100.0	

Figure 24 Reason behind Lack of CSR

The above bar chart and frequency table illustrates that the most of organisations are not using corporate social responsibility because of lack of awareness. However, lack of interest and expenses are at second and third number as indicated by the result of the quantitative data. While some responded prefer to choose other reasons behind the organisation not executing corporate social responsibility.

CSR can enhance the profit.

The following frequencies shows the perception of managers working in Pakistani banks. 24.0% of managers believe that CSR can provide long term profit and 45.6% consider that CSR can attract customers. 30.4% managers think that CSR activities can sustain customers. These all activities can become the cause behind the increase profit.

		Promote			Cumulative
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Percent
Valid	Long term profit	60	24.0	24.0	24.0
	Attract investors	114	45.6	45.6	69.6
	Sustain customers	76	30.4	30.4	100.0
	Total	250	100.0	100.0	

Perception of manager related to the CSR impact on financial performance.

		Profit			Cumulative
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Percent
Valid	Yes	144	57.6	57.6	57.6
	No	52	20.8	20.8	78.4
	Not Sure	54	21.6	21.6	100.0
	Total	250	100.0	100.0	

The abovementioned frequency demonstrates that 57.6% of managers of Pakistani banks believes that corporate social responsibility can result in to increase financial performance. While 20.8% of managers disagree with the statement that CSR can raise the profit of bank. 21.6% of managers of Pakistani banks are unaware of relationship between corporate social responsibility and profit.

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Meaning	250	1	6	2.53	1.931
Purpose	250	1	8	5.33	1.836
Activity	250	1	6	2.76	1.685
Promote	250	1	3	2.06	.736
Reason	250	1	4	2.36	.998
Profit	250	1	3	1.64	.816
Valid N (listwise)	250				

The above table demonstrates the mean and std. deviation of different variables. The results demonstrate that the managers working in Pakistani banks have some understanding of corporate social responsibility, although there are few unaware aspects of CSR. The managers should recognise that providing safe working environment is part of their ethical responsibility. Moreover, it will be beneficial for the banks in Pakistan to create more awareness of CSR within the organisation and recognise that CSR can attract investors and increase the financial performance.

5.5.5 Hypothesis Testing

This section of the data analysis is related to the testing of hypothesis which were created by researcher from the research question. The researcher has used different statistical tests to test the hypothesis. The tests are divided in different sections which are the variables used in questionnaire. Moreover, the researcher used abbreviations in the statistical testing because it was easy for the researcher, illustrated in following table.

Full form	Abbreviation
Philanthropic responsibilities	Phi
Employees	Emp
Customers	Cus
Environmental	Env
Legal	LEG
Financial performance	FP
Strongly Agree	SA
Agree	A
Neutral	N
Disagree	D
Strongly Disagree	SD
Well Below Average	WBA
Below Average	BA
Average	A
Above Average	AA
Well Above Average	WAA

Table 13 Abbreviations used in Data analysis

5.5.6 Philanthropic Responsibilities.

Funding scholarship programs or activities

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	SD	15	6.0	6.0	6.0
	D	55	22.0	22.0	28.0
	N	113	45.2	45.2	73.2
	A	52	20.8	20.8	94.0
	SA	15	6.0	6.0	100.0
	Total	250	100.0	100.0	

The above table shows that 6.0% of participants strongly disagree that their banks participate in funding scholarship programs. 22% disagree with the statement. However, majority of the respondents selected neutral for the statement that was 45.2 % while 20.8% agree with the fact that their bank provide scholarships. Only 6% strongly agree with the statement.

Sponsoring public health projects

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	SD	15	6.0	6.0	6.0
	D	59	23.6	23.6	29.6
	N	108	43.2	43.2	72.8
	A	55	22.0	22.0	94.8
	SA	13	5.2	5.2	100.0
	Total	250	100.0	100.0	

This above table shows that banks in Pakistan involve in sponsoring public health project. Most of the participant which was 43.2 percent were neutral about the statement while 22% agree

with it. Where 23% disagree with the statement that their bank invests in health projects. Similarly, the following table shows that 41.6% participants were neutral and with the statement that their bank provide donation and participates in activities like sports and arts. 23% strongly agree with the statement while 58% disagree with the fact.

Donations of cash, products, or employee services to support community activities, events, arts, sports

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	SD	15	6.0	6.0	6.0
	D	58	23.2	23.2	29.2
	N	104	41.6	41.6	70.8
	A	59	23.6	23.6	94.4
	SA	14	5.6	5.6	100.0
	Total	250	100.0	100.0	

Sponsoring education conference, seminar, workshop or art exhibits Aiding disaster victims

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	SD	15	6.0	6.0	6.0
	D	58	23.2	23.2	29.2
	N	108	43.2	43.2	72.4
	A	55	22.0	22.0	94.4
	SA	14	5.6	5.6	100.0
	Total	250	100.0	100.0	

The above table shows the frequency of the statement. It shows that 43% participants were neutral and 22% agreed while 23.2% disagreed that their bank provide sponsor education conference, seminar, workshop arts exhibits and aiding disaster victims. The following table illustrates that 44% of participants agree that their bank provide support and encourage the development of rural areas of the country. Where 31.2% of participants were neutral and 20.4% disagreed with the statement.

Supports and encourages the development of rural areas of the country

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	D	51	20.4	20.4	20.4
	N	78	31.2	31.2	51.6
	A	112	44.8	44.8	96.4
	SA	9	3.6	3.6	100.0
	Total	250	100.0	100.0	

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Funding scholarship programs or activities	250	1	5	2.99	.955
Sponsoring public health projects	250	1	5	2.97	.952
Donations of cash, products, or employee services to support community activities, events, arts, sports	250	1	5	3.00	.967
Sponsoring education conference, seminar, workshop or art exhibits	250	1	5	2.98	.959
Aiding disaster victims	250	1	5	3.00	.967
Supports and encourages the development of rural areas of the country	250	2	5	3.32	.836
Valid N (listwise)	250				

The above table demonstrates the descriptive statistics of philanthropic responsibilities. It includes the mean and std. deviation of all items. The average of all items is mostly value of 3 while std. deviations of all variables are around 0.95.

5.5.7 Employees.

This section of the investigation presents frequencies and descriptive statistics of the employees related statements which were included in questionnaire. The following table shows that most of the participants were selected neutral with the statement that Pakistani banks give rewards to employees that is 46.0%. where 19.6% agreed and 20.8% disagreed with the statement. Moreover, few participants strongly disagreed which is 8% while 5.6% strongly agreed with it.

Gives rewards to employees

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	SD	20	8.0	8.0	8.0
	D	52	20.8	20.8	28.8
	N	115	46.0	46.0	74.8
	A	49	19.6	19.6	94.4
	SA	14	5.6	5.6	100.0
	Total	250	100.0	100.0	

Provides health care for the employees including health assistance, maternity leave

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	SD	20	8.0	8.0	8.0
	D	55	22.0	22.0	30.0
	N	112	44.8	44.8	74.8
	A	50	20.0	20.0	94.8
	SA	13	5.2	5.2	100.0
	Total	250	100.0	100.0	

The above table shows the frequency of the statement that banks provides health care including assistance and maternity leave. It is illustrated that 44.8% of participants selected neutral while 22% disagreed with the statement. 20% agreed and 8% strongly disagreed with it.

Provides finance or loan to the employees for their higher education

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	SD	20	8.0	8.0	8.0
	D	54	21.6	21.6	29.6
	N	110	44.0	44.0	73.6
	A	53	21.2	21.2	94.8
	SA	13	5.2	5.2	100.0
	Total	250	100.0	100.0	

The above table shows that 44% of participants were neutral and 21.2% of participants agreed with the statement that their banks provide loan to the employees for their higher education. Where 21% of participants disagreed and 8% strongly disagreed. However, only few participants 5.2% strongly agreed with the statement. Similarly, the following table illustrates the frequency of another statement. In which 48% of participants agreed and 10% strongly agreed that their bank provide better working environment for employees. While 26.8% were in the neutral and 10.8% disagreed with the statement. It shows that most of Pakistani banks are taking care of their employees.

Provides better working environment for employees

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	SD	9	3.6	3.6	3.6
	D	27	10.8	10.8	14.4
	N	67	26.8	26.8	41.2
	A	122	48.8	48.8	90.0
	SA	25	10.0	10.0	100.0
	Total	250	100.0	100.0	

Comply with health and safety standards and regulations

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	D	53	21.2	21.2	21.2
	N	79	31.6	31.6	52.8
	A	109	43.6	43.6	96.4
	SA	9	3.6	3.6	100.0
	Total	250	100.0	100.0	

This above-mentioned table demonstrates that most of the participants 43.6% agreed with the statement that their bank complies with health and safety standards and regulations. 31.6% of participants selected neutral while 21.2% disagreed that their bank is not considering health and safety rules. The researcher believes that it is essential and ethical for any organization to follow the health and safety guidelines.

Provides better working environment to employees

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	SD	9	3.6	3.6	3.6
	D	27	10.8	10.8	14.4
	N	67	26.8	26.8	41.2
	A	122	48.8	48.8	90.0
	SA	25	10.0	10.0	100.0
	Total	250	100.0	100.0	

Correspondingly, the above table shows that 48.8% of participants tend to agree and 10% strongly agree with the statement that their bank provides a better working environment. 26.8% selected neutral and 10.8% disagree with the statement. The researcher believes that a better working

environment can motivate employees which will lead to increase financial performance of an organisation.

Has rules related to employee discrimination

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	D	26	10.4	10.4	10.4
	N	66	26.4	26.4	36.8
	A	137	54.8	54.8	91.6
	SA	21	8.4	8.4	100.0
	Total	250	100.0	100.0	

Last but not the least, the above table demonstrates that most of the participants that is 54.8% agreed with the statement that their bank has rules related to employee discrimination. 26% of participants selected neutral while 10.4% disagree with the statement. Only 8.4% of participants strongly agreed with the statement. It is crucial in researcher's opinion to follow the discrimination rules in any organisation. The following table is of descriptive statistic of employees related statements which includes the mean and std. deviation.

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Gives rewards to employees	250	1	2.94	.974
Provides health care for the employees including health assistance, maternity leave	250	1	2.92	.973
Provides finance or loan to the employees for their higher education	250	1	2.94	.978
Provides Employees training	250	1	2.93	.973
Complying with health and safety standards and regulations	250	2	3.30	.841
Provides better working environment to employees	250	1	3.51	.941
Has rules related to employee discrimination	250	2	3.61	.785
Valid N (listwise)	250			

5.5.8 Environmental.

This section of the research demonstrates the frequencies of the environment related statements in the questionnaire. The following table illustrates that most of the respondents, 40.4% agreed and 28.0% strongly agreed with the statement that their bank has environmental policies. 22% selected neutral while 9.2% disagree with the statement.

Has environmental policies

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	SD	1	.4	.4	.4
	D	23	9.2	9.2	9.6
	N	55	22.0	22.0	31.6
	A	101	40.4	40.4	72.0
	SA	70	28.0	28.0	100.0
	Total	250	100.0	100.0	

The following table shows the frequency of another statement which demonstrates that 31.6% selected neutral and 19.6% agreed that their bank provides importance to reduction in pollution. However, a number of respondents that is 27.6% disagreed with the statement.

Gives importance to pollution reduction

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	SD	23	9.2	9.2	9.2
	D	69	27.6	27.6	36.8
	N	79	31.6	31.6	68.4
	A	49	19.6	19.6	88.0
	SA	30	12.0	12.0	100.0
	Total	250	100.0	100.0	

Believes in conservation of natural resources (energy conservation)

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	D	41	16.4	16.4	16.4
	N	55	22.0	22.0	38.4
	A	125	50.0	50.0	88.4
	SA	29	11.6	11.6	100.0
	Total	250	100.0	100.0	

The above table illustrates that 50% of respondents tends to agree with the statement that their bank believed in conservation of natural resources or energy conservation. 22% respondents selected neutral, 11.6% strongly agreed with the statement. Although, 16.4% disagreed with the statement. Similarly, the following table shows that 39.2% strongly agree that their banks has efficiency in waste management. 26.0% selected neutral and 28% agreed with the statement while only 6% participants disagreed with it.

Efficiency in waste management.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	D	15	6.0	6.0	6.0
	N	65	26.0	26.0	32.0
	A	72	28.8	28.8	60.8
	SA	98	39.2	39.2	100.0
	Total	250	100.0	100.0	

Engaged in eco-friendly products

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	SD	1	.4	.4	.4
	D	16	6.4	6.4	6.8
	N	73	29.2	29.2	36.0
	A	51	20.4	20.4	56.4
	SA	109	43.6	43.6	100.0
	Total	250	100.0	100.0	

The above table illustrates that 43.6% participants strongly agreed and 20.4% participants agreed with the statement that their bank use eco-friendly products. Where 29.2% selected neutral while only 6.4% disagreed and 0.4 strongly disagreed with it. Moreover, the following table shows the descriptive statistics of the environmental statements. In which mean of all environmental statements is mostly around 3 and St. Deviation is around 1 and 0.9.

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Has environmental policies	250	1	5	3.86	.943
Gives importance to pollution reduction	250	1	5	2.98	1.151
Believes in conservation of natural resources (energy conservation)	250	2	5	3.57	.899
Efficiency in waste management.	250	2	5	4.01	.946
Engaged in eco-friendly products	250	1	5	4.00	1.012
Valid N (listwise)	250				

5.5.9 Customers.

This section represents the frequencies of customers related statements in the questionnaire of the study. The following table illustrates that 53% of respondents agreed and 14.4% strongly agreed with the statement that their bank responds to the customers' complaints in a satisfactory manner. 20.8% of respondents selected neutral while 11.6% disagreed with the statement.

Responds to the customer's complaints in a satisfactory manner

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	D	29	11.6	11.6	11.6
	N	52	20.8	20.8	32.4
	A	133	53.2	53.2	85.6
	SA	36	14.4	14.4	100.0
	Total	250	100.0	100.0	

The following table displays that 56% of participants agreed and 15.6% strongly disagreed with the statement that their bank has ethical and policies related to advertising of the product and service. 16.8% respondents selected neutral while 11.6% disagreed with the statement.

Has ethical standards and policies related to advertising of the product and services

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	D	29	11.6	11.6	11.6
	N	42	16.8	16.8	28.4
	A	140	56.0	56.0	84.4
	SA	39	15.6	15.6	100.0
	Total	250	100.0	100.0	

Provides Clear and accurate information to customers

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	SD	1	.4	.4	.4
	D	17	6.8	6.8	7.2
	N	71	28.4	28.4	35.6
	A	134	53.6	53.6	89.2
	SA	27	10.8	10.8	100.0
	Total	250	100.0	100.0	

The above table shows that 53.6% participants agreed and 10.8 strongly agreed that there is clear and accurate information to customers is provided by their bank. 28% respondents selected neutral while 6.8% disagreed with the statement. Moreover, the following table illustrates descriptive statistics of the statement related to customers. It shows that all statements mean is around 3 and Std. Deviation is around 0.8.

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Responds to the customer's complaints in a satisfactory manner	250	2	5	3.70	.855
Has ethical standards and policies related to advertising of the product and services	250	2	5	3.76	.855
Provides Clear and accurate information to customers	250	1	5	3.68	.773
Valid N (listwise)	250				

5.5.10 Legal.

The frequencies of legal related statement of the questionnaire are presented in this section. The following table depicts that most of the respondents 62.4% agreed and 8.4% strongly agreed that their bank pays all the taxes on time. While 24.4% selected neutral and 4.8% tend to disagree with the statement.

Pays all the taxes on time

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	D	12	4.8	4.8	4.8
	N	61	24.4	24.4	29.2
	A	156	62.4	62.4	91.6
	SA	21	8.4	8.4	100.0
	Total	250	100.0	100.0	

The following table shows that 68.8% of participants agreed and 10% strongly agreed that their bank is complying with various federal, state and local regulations. 17.6% respondents selected neutral while 3.6% of participants disagree with the statement.

Complying with various federal, state, and local regulations.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	D	9	3.6	3.6	3.6
	N	44	17.6	17.6	21.2
	A	172	68.8	68.8	90.0
	SA	25	10.0	10.0	100.0
	Total	250	100.0	100.0	

Providing goods and services that at least meet minimal legal requirements.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	D	12	4.8	4.8	4.8
	N	68	27.2	27.2	32.0
	A	148	59.2	59.2	91.2
	SA	22	8.8	8.8	100.0
	Total	250	100.0	100.0	

The above table shows that 59% respondents agreed and 8.8% strongly agreed with the statement that their bank is providing good and services that at least meet minimal legal requirements. 27.2% selected neutral while 4.8% disagreed with the statement. Moreover, the following table illustrates that 68% of respondents agreed with the statement that their bank perform in a manner consistent with expectations of government and law. 18.4% of respondents selected neutral while 4.4% disagreed with it.

Performing in a manner consistent with expectations of government and law.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	D	11	4.4	4.4	4.4
	N	46	18.4	18.4	22.8
	A	170	68.0	68.0	90.8
	SA	23	9.2	9.2	100.0
	Total	250	100.0	100.0	

The following table demonstrates the descriptive statistics of legal statements of the questionnaire. It shows that mean of all variable is around 3 while Std. Deviation is around 0.6.

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Pays all the taxes on time	250	2	5	3.74	.675
Complying with various federal, state, and local regulations.	250	2	5	3.85	.632
Providing goods and services that at least meet minimal legal requirements.	250	2	5	3.72	.690
Performing in a manner consistent with expectations of government and law.	250	2	5	3.82	.649
Valid N (listwise)	250				

5.5.11 Financial Performance.

This is the last section of frequencies of statements of financial performance from the questionnaire. The following table shows that 45.2% of respondents agreed that the net profit of their bank in previous five years was average while 22.4% respondents selected below average. 20.4% of respondents tend to agree with above average while 6% selected well below average.

Net profit of your bank in previous five years was

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	WBA	15	6.0	6.0	6.0
	BA	56	22.4	22.4	28.4
	A	113	45.2	45.2	73.6
	AA	51	20.4	20.4	94.0
	WAA	15	6.0	6.0	100.0
	Total	250	100.0	100.0	

Similarly, the following table shows that 43% of respondents agreed that earning per share (EPS) of their bank in previous five years was average and 19.6% selected above average. 23.6% of participants selected below average while 8% selected well below average.

EPS of your bank in previous five years was

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	WBA	20	8.0	8.0	8.0
	BA	59	23.6	23.6	31.6
	A	108	43.2	43.2	74.8
	AA	49	19.6	19.6	94.4
	WAA	14	5.6	5.6	100.0
	Total	250	100.0	100.0	

ROA of your bank in previous five years was

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	WBA	5	2.0	2.0	2.0
	BA	47	18.8	18.8	20.8
	A	85	34.0	34.0	54.8
	AA	93	37.2	37.2	92.0
	WAA	20	8.0	8.0	100.0
	Total	250	100.0	100.0	

The above table illustrates the frequency related to financial performance of the bank. 37% of respondents agreed with the statement that their bank ROA was above average and 34% selected average. 18.8% selected below average where 8% selected well above average. Similarly, the following table shows that 42% of respondents agreed that ROE of their bank in previous five years was above average and 26.4% selected average while 21.6% selected well above average.

ROE of your bank in previous five years was

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	BA	23	9.2	9.2	9.2
	A	66	26.4	26.4	35.6
	AA	107	42.8	42.8	78.4
	WAA	54	21.6	21.6	100.0
	Total	250	100.0	100.0	

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Net profit of your bank in previous five years was	250	1	5	2.98	.955
EPS of your bank in previous five years was	250	1	5	2.91	.986
ROA of your bank in previous five years was	250	1	5	3.30	.933
ROE of your bank in previous five years was	250	2	5	3.77	.893
Valid N (listwise)	250				

The above table shows the descriptive statistics of the statements related to financial performance from the questionnaire of the study. It shows that most of the mean of statements are around 3 and Std. Deviation is around 0.9.

The following section of the research presents the correlation among CSR and financial performance. However, it is essential to perform the normality test before conducting any other test. It is observed by many researchers that the most popular used statistical methods are correlation and regression but they based on the normal distribution of data (Das & Rahmatullah Imon, 2016).

5.5.12 CSR And Financial Performance.

5.5.13 Pearson's Correlation.

It is indicated by the literature that many scholars support the positive effect of corporate social responsibility on financial performance in long run (Clarkson, 1995; Ruf, et al., 2001; Stanwick & Stanwick, 1998). Stakeholder theory suggested that an organisation can satisfy stakeholders by means of arrangement of organisational resources and by using suitable CSR and it can enhance the reputation of the firm (Waddock & Graves, 1997; Lewis, 2003). CSR can motivate employees and can cause behind the increased productivity and financial performance (Basu & Palazzo, 2008; Orlitzky, 2008).

This investigation applied Pearson's correlation to investigate the correlation amongst the variable and find out the relationship between corporate social responsibility and financial performance. The correlation illustrated in the following table shows that all independent variables are significantly positively correlated to the dependent variables.

Pearson's correlation coefficient is denoted by r and is defined by:

$$r = \frac{n \sum xy - \sum x \sum y}{\sqrt{\{n \sum x^2 - (\sum x)^2\} \{n \sum y^2 - (\sum y)^2\}}}$$

The value of r always lies between -1 and 1 inclusive

That is, $-1 \leq r \leq 1$. If Y increases when X increases, there is positive or direct correlation between variables.

However, if Y decreases when X increases (or vice versa), they are negatively or inversely correlated (Field, 2006).

Figure 25 Values of Pearson's Correlation

Correlations

		FP_C	Phi_C	EMP_C	ENV_C	CUST_C	LEG_C
FP_C	Pearson Correlation	1	.631**	.579**	.218**	.377**	.452**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.001	.000	.000
	N	250	250	250	250	250	250
Phi_C	Pearson Correlation	.631**	1	.104	.028	.161*	.259**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.101	.659	.011	.000
	N	250	250	250	250	250	250
EMP_C	Pearson Correlation	.579**	.104	1	.154*	.131*	.268**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.101		.015	.039	.000
	N	250	250	250	250	250	250
ENV_C	Pearson Correlation	.218**	.028	.154*	1	.058	.120
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.001	.659	.015		.358	.058
	N	250	250	250	250	250	250
CUST_C	Pearson Correlation	.377**	.161*	.131*	.058	1	.214**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.011	.039	.358		.001
	N	250	250	250	250	250	250
LEG_C	Pearson Correlation	.452**	.259**	.268**	.120	.214**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.058	.001	
	N	250	250	250	250	250	250

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

The above table demonstrates that the correlation between CSR and financial performance variables are highly significant. It shows that participants of this investigation tend to agree that Pakistani banks CSR has positive impact on their financial performance.

5.5.14 Independent sample T-test.

Moreover, the researcher used the independent sample t-test is employed to compare the mean between two groups. The following table provides the descriptive statistics for public and private banks with the mean and standard deviation.

	Profile	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
FP_C	Public	93	2.3441	.41526	.04306
	Private	157	3.1799	.68514	.05468

The following table demonstrates the actual result of the independent t-test. It is indicated that the group means are statistically significantly different from each other. The sig. 2 tailed value are different for each group. It means that participants of private banks tend to agreed that their financial performance is better while for public banks participant the situation is different. As a rule of thumb, Sig. value should be > 0.05 to accept the hypothesis and in the following table the Sig. is .000 which is less than .05, therefore the null hypothesis is rejected. Which means there is a difference in financial performance of public and private banks in Pakistan.

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances				
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
FP_C	Equal variances assumed	16.751	.000	2.093	248	.037
	Equal variances not assumed			2.358	247.852	.019

5.5.15 One-way ANOVA.

The researcher used one-way ANOVA to analyse the relationship between size of the banks and financial performance. The following table shows the output of ANOVA analysis and whether there is a statistically significant difference between groups means. It is indicated in the table that the significance value is .008 which is less than p-value 0.05, therefore the null hypothesis is rejected. It means that both independent variables are differed significantly, and the size of the bank is positively related to their financial performance.

ANOVA

FP_C

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	3.454	2	1.727	4.891	.008
Within Groups	87.214	247	.353		
Total	90.667	249			

5.5.16 Post Hoc Tests

Homogeneous Subsets

In this section the researcher employed Post Hoc comparisons using Duncan's test for size and financial performance of Pakistani banks. It reveals that respondents agreed that large banks had significantly higher financial performance than small and medium size banks.

FP_C

Duncan^{a,b}

Size	N	Subset for alpha = 0.05	
		1	2
Small	40	3.1353	
Medium	101	3.2624	
Large	109		3.4750
Sig.		.213	1.000

Means for groups in homogeneous subsets are displayed.

- a. Uses Harmonic Mean Sample Size = 68.065.
- b. The group sizes are unequal. The harmonic mean of the group sizes is used. Type I error levels are not guaranteed.

The above graph demonstrates that most of the participants tends to agreed that large banks had better financial performance as compare to small and medium banks.

5.5.17 Hypotheses Results.

Hypothesis	Result
H ₁ = There is a positive and significant correlation between philanthropic responsibilities and financial performance of Pakistani banks.	Accepted
H ₂ = There is a positive and significant correlation between employees related CSR and financial performance of Pakistani banks.	Accepted
H ₃ = There is a positive and significant correlation between environmental responsibilities and financial performance of Pakistani banks.	Accepted
H ₄ = There is a positive and significant correlation between customers related responsibilities and financial performance of Pakistani banks.	Accepted
H ₅ = There is a positive and significant correlation between legal responsibilities and financial performance of Pakistani banks.	Accepted
H ₆ = There is a positive and significant correlation between CSR and financial performance of Pakistani banks.	Accepted
H _n = There is no significant difference in the financial performance of Public and Private Pakistani banks.	Rejected
H _n = There is no significant difference between financial performance and size of the Pakistani banks.	Rejected

Table 14 Hypotheses Results

5.6 Analysis of Interviews.

The interviews taken by researcher to complete this investigation were ten and they were telephonic interviews. The researcher considered the ethical aspects related to willingness to contribute or participate. Moreover, the analysis of qualitative data is arranged by two different which is making and interpretation of transcripts and giving code by generalisation with the recognition of match or similarity.

The researcher has accomplished interpretation of data by using distinct techniques which includes analytic comparison that acknowledges the hypothesis established on previously recognised theories. The uniformities and comparison of the data was identified by researcher and then determined uniformities going in direction of confined zone to broad level.

5.6.1 Coding

In a qualitative analysis, the most often a word which representatively allocates a comprehensive, significant attribute for a portion of language base data is code. It includes transcript, videos, observation notes and so on. The repetitive patterns of action and consistencies was indicated by researcher. The researcher Pattern coding assigned codes to the data collected from the interviews which is the stage of open coding. Line and paragraphs of the transcript were put into categories and different themes has developed. Higher order codes can be produces by means of hierarchical coding. The particular prove for the certain theme by assessing them with another example is the next stage of coding. The patterns can be characterized by:

- Similarity
- Difference
- Frequency
- Sequence
- Correspondence
- Causation

The approach of using analytic comparison are followed by pattern coding of the data. This is employed by researcher for interpretation analysis which can provide meaning to the participants' social world.

5.6.2 Interview participants background:

This section of the study includes an overview of the interviews with analysis of their demographic statistics. The respondents in the study were divided as representatives of particular groups and were given their node code by use of NVivo version 12. The interviews were analysed by making transcripts and creating codes. Moreover, the following table shows the group of participants and their code.

Serial Number	Participants' Group	Code
1	Supervisors in the Bank	SB
2	Manager in the Bank	MB
3	Senior Manager in the Bank	SMB
4	General Manger of the Bank	GMB
5	Director/CEO of the Bank	DCB

Table 15 Coding of Participants' Group

Table 16 Organisational Sector of Participants

S.no	Code	Private Sector Bank	Public Sector Bank	Islamic Bank
1	SMB	1		
2	MB	1		
3	DCB		1	
4	GMB	1		
5	SMB	1		
6	MB	1		
7	MB		1	
8	GMB			1
9	SMB	1		
10	MB	1		

The above table shows that most of the participant of the interview were from the private sector banks in Pakistan. Only few of participants were from public and Islamic banks. These all interviewees are from the marketing department of the different Pakistani banks which also includes the corporate communication department. The following table illustrates the education and experience of the participants.

Table 17 Education and Experience of Participants

Participant Code	Education		Experience	
	Post Graduate	Graduate	1-5years	5-10years
SMB1	1			1
MB		1	1	
DCB	1			1
GMB	1			1
SMB		1	1	
MB		1	1	
MB	1		1	
GMB	1			1
SMB	1		1	
MB		1	1	
Total	6	4	6	4

It is illustrated in the table that most of the participants are the at management level of Pakistani banks are most of the have post graduate degree. Only four of the participants had graduate degree. When it comes to the experience of these participant six out of ten had experience between one to five years and four of them had more than five years of experience. By analysing the education level of the participants, it is clear that that they have reached to management level based on their higher education and hard work. The next section of the research is about the analysis of the discussion of corporate social responsibility with the participants.

Everyone has its own perception and every participant had his own definition of corporate social responsibility. The researcher has interpreted the delineation of CSR according to the interviewees.

Interpretation of CSR Definition of Participants

1. Social accountability	8. Part of business
2. Reputation of the firm	9. Marketing
3. Pressure of authorities	10. Saving taxation
4. Community involvement	11. Reputation of the firm
5. Protection of environment	12. Return to the society
6. To be in good books	13. Charity/ Donations
7. Sports activities	14. Not well defined (less awareness)

Table 18 CSR Definitions

Although many interviewees differ from each other, there was a collective perception of CSR which was social help and charity. All banks in Pakistan are focusing on charity and donations to any NGO to fulfil corporate responsibility. This method demonstrates the exact terminologies used by interviewees for CSR. Many interviewees also gave importance to the social responsibility and reputation of the organisations. It was also considered as marketing strategy by banks to promote their product and services and ultimately lead to the profit for the company. The researcher has given different codes to the responses of the participants and then has described it all in detail.

Table 19 Coding the transcripts.

Position of respondents	Participant's response	Codes
SBM	<p>“I think we have CSR policy, I know that the bank has done quite a lot of social work in previous three years which include sponsoring sports like PSL, we have spent huge amount on it”.</p> <p>Yes, that's true, our organisation is taking part in good things, as I told you about the PSL, no one was ready to sponsor PSL, then our bank took initiative, which is really good initiative because now cricket is back in the country. People are doing good deeds in different organisations, Karachi and overall in Pakistan.</p>	<p>CSR</p> <p>Philanthropy</p> <p>Philanthropy</p>
	<p>is organising Hajj (Religious pilgrimage) schemes and they also offer Cristian, Hindu and other religion for that scheme.</p>	<p>Philanthropy</p>
SBM	<p>you know that the bank has had paid penalty of RS. 22 billion and whenever we do such thing we always consider employees, investors and customers. Every year we have appraisals, when the bank makes profit it gives bonus, promotions and increments. And always think of the stakeholders because they are the main or</p>	<p>Ethical</p>

	should I say the back bone of the company. The bank has almost 16000 employees.	
BM	Yes, we have CSR in our bank, our bank has involved with charity and specially with sports, we support liyari (Less privilege areas) football teams and also cricket. If you want to know more about the charity and CSR activities of the bank you can always look up to the annual report of the bank, you can find names of NGO and different organisations, I think we have more than ten companies associated with the bank.	<p>Philanthropy</p> <p>Philanthropy</p>
BM	Many organisations are not participating in CSR but when we talk about banks mostly banks do it. Big banks are doing it and other big organisations like Pakistan steel use to Participate in it by contribution in constructing infrastructure, like construction of bridges in the country, which all were free of cost and even they didn't tag their name in it. Similarly, many banks are participating like Alflah bank supports Alfatimi blood bank.	<p>Awareness</p> <p>Size</p>
BM	Yes, that's true, because NGOs always need some support on	Philanthropy

	<p>which behalf they can run their operations and big organisations help them like banks support through different branches.</p>	
	<p>I think, they want to play their role in the society, if an organisation is operating in a society it has some responsibility towards society and for well-being</p>	<p>Ethical</p>
	<p>yes, we do have student loans, it is in regulation, according to State Bank of Pakistan which introduced regulation in 2004 that every bank will offer student loan and it will deduct from the future salary of the student. When they will get a job.</p>	<p>Ethical</p>
BM	<p>it is possible that banks do charities because of the taxation, but there is no state law for it that you have to do CSR, if it was the case then most of companies would have chosen to practice CSR and Pakistan would be a changed place</p>	<p>Legal</p>
BM	<p>There is one specific amount which is allocated to charities and donations and if someone wants to give some extra donation they have to take approval from the board of directors.</p>	<p>Philanthropy</p>

BM	<p>yes, I think it's for brand image and ultimate financial gain, it brands image of the company will increase, it improves the reputation of the firm and people will take a company as a responsible for the society. It's kind of tools for companies.</p>	<p>Financial performance</p>
	<p>if you talk about green banking, companies who are not environment friendly, banks do not give loan to them and they need specific certification for environment, if the company do not submit that certificate bank will not pass their loan. Now its mandatory in Pakistan.</p>	<p>Environment</p>
	<p>it can be both, if a bank is providing support to NGO and doing proper marketing of it, like using it on bill boards and adverts than you can say they are doing it to attract customers and for profit, but our bank doesn't do a lot of marketing of these activities.</p>	<p>Philanthropy Financial performance</p>
	<p>yes, you are right. Many companies even don't know what CSR is</p>	<p>Awareness</p>
	<p>In Pakistan, there is less awareness of CSR, large organisations are practicing CSR but medium size and small</p>	<p>Awareness Size</p>

	<p>companies are not aware of that. Like I know one textile company they provide health care free of cost but at least there should be environmental policy in every organisation.</p>	<p>Environment</p>
	<p>I know that's really unethical, but I think that only happens in public banks, not in private sector, because we have very strict policies. And now State Bank has strict regulation about it that you have to give prior notice to customers before putting any charges. We have one sale department and independent department to review these things they reject it if they think it's not right and these things are recorded and if something wrong happens they take disciplinary action for it.</p>	<p>Customers</p>
	<p>no, I don't think so they don't consider stakeholder as part of CSR.</p>	<p>Stakeholders</p>
	<p>Yes, they should encourage CSR activities, but the profit is not directly proportional.</p>	<p>CSR Profit</p>
DCB	<p>Sometimes we have to do what government ask us, for example we supported an event because authorities ask us to do so.</p>	<p>Legal</p>

	Many organisations are only participating in activities because they have to follow the authorities.	Legal
	There is no specific guide lines in our bank and even many employees don't feel happy when we do some activities and consider that we should rather spend money on them.	Awareness Employees

Figure 26 NVivo Hierarchy chart of Coded items.

The above figure demonstrates the node coded in the transcripts. The large coloured area reflects the large number of coded nodes of items in transcripts. Moreover, the following figure illustrates the CSR is coded in all ten transcripts as it the most discussed item amongst participants.

Figure 27 CSR coding in Transcripts.

5.6.3 Code no 1 : Philanthropy (Charity and donations)

Charity and donations are philanthropic activity in which a person or an organisation gives away for the social well-being. There are many organisations which provide assistance to the under- privileged people of a society. In Pakistan, a number of banks are giving charity and donations for the betterment of the society. It was indicated by many participants that banks are participating in CSR activities and preferred to do charity and donations. Health care was specified by participant that their banks are supporting Shaukat Khanum Memorial Cancer Hospital and Research centre, The Indus Hospital, Omair Sana Foundation (OSF) and Sindh Institute of Urology Transplant (SUIT). Some of the bank are supporting NGOs and non-profit organisations, and as pointed out by the participant that the bank allocates specific amount for charities. A number of Pakistani Banks also contributes some percentage of its profit to foundations to promote equal opportunities within society. Few banks also help blood banks.

Moreover, the Edhi Centre, which is one of the famous charity centres in Pakistan is supported by numerous banks of Pakistan. Talent hunt programs are also operating by few banks to select meritorious students and offer them support. Investment in education is also of paramount significance to empower the success of the country. And banks denotations are imparting quality of education to the youth of the society. As mentioned by one of the participants:

“Our bank does make donations (related to education) to different organisations like Suleman Dawood School of Business (LUMS), Custom Public School, Tehzeeb Social Welfare Organisation and Institute of Business Administration (IBA)”.

Although the researcher believes that some of these organisations are well known and large educational institutes, it will be advantageous if contributions made by banks assists to the needy or under-privilege institutes.

However, the philanthropic activity is one part of the corporate social responsibility. Participants accepted with the fact that most of organisations only focus on the charity. Where small and medium size enterprises even do not contribute in any charity and donations. Annual report is published by listed and large organisations and therefore it is essential for them to perceived as socially accountable by stakeholders. The researcher had evaluated the annual reports of a various banks of Pakistan and observed that maximum investment was on charity, when it comes to CSR activities. The banks in Pakistan should have to take further these societal activities.

Figure 28 Number of Philanthropic Responsibilities Coded.

Additionally, the above figure illustrates percentage of philanthropic responsibility coded in interviews transcripts. It is indicated that the item is coded mostly in transcript 2 and transcript 9 while it is less coded item in transcript number 6 and 7.

5.6.4 Philanthropy (Sports).

Sports is one of the famous activities by people in Pakistan. There are different types of sports but everyone in Pakistan has great affect towards cricket. Banks are interested in contributing to sports activity and become a part of a society. It is accepted by participants that their banks are attracted to sports.

A mentioned by one participant that

“There is one series of cricket “Pakistan Super League (PSL)”, which is a cricket league founded in Lahore in 2015. Habib bank limited (HBL) had supported PSL by providing amount around RS. 11 million”.

Moreover, it also came up in the discussion of CSR with participants that some banks are engaging people from under-privileged areas to help them to stay away from the illegitimate activities. The researcher consider that it is beneficial way to involve the young generation but there should promote them towards education as well. HBL is also associated with Azad foundation provide assistance to elevate street children through engaging with sports and promote them to international level. Sports has been one of the main areas which empowers country to attain huge admiration in the world and many banks had comprehended some accountability towards promotion of sports. Vintage & Classis Car Club of Pakistan (VCCCP) which organises car rally from Karachi to Islamabad is one of the famous sports activities supported by some banks. Polo Tournament and golf tournaments are other sports sponsored by banks in Pakistan.

However, it is pointed out by many participants that:

“only few big banks are involved with sports while a large number of organisations do not prefer to participate in any sports”.

5.6.5 Philanthropy (Schemes).

Another code given by researcher in interpretation of qualitative data is schemes. There are different banks in Pakistan that offers a number of schemes. These schemes can be considered as an element of corporate social responsibility. These schemes include education schemes like student loan. A number of banks are offering student loans to the people of Pakistan which is regulatory now. However, it was indicated by participant that banks do have specifications for example a specific educational institution selected by bank and only student of that institution can get benefit from the scheme. According to researcher the mortgage without interest and offering religious pilgrimage packages are consider to be a part of Corporate social responsibility. It is the fact that many banks do not offer these schemes but if all banks in Pakistan participate, could bring a significant change in the society.

5.6.6 Code no 2 : Environmental.

Protection of environment is the essential responsibility of any individual or a country. Many organisations in Pakistan are trying to protect environment by reducing pollution, reducing the extent of wastage and keeping the air clean. Banks are also participating to help the society by protecting environment. The State Bank of Pakistan had introduced the Green Banking guidelines (GBG) which is compulsory for every bank in Pakistan. Green banking has recognised the accountability of banks or financial sector in supporting guidelines initiatives for changing economy of the country. The purpose of Green Banking guidelines is to decrease susceptibility of banks from risks rising from the environment. Banks in Pakistan give finance to companies by considering the environmental laws. Companies which do not have environmental guidelines and create pollution to the environment are often not welcome by banks for any finance or investments. The researcher consider that it is the significant step of banks towards the protection of the environment. Participants also indicated that there are a number of platforms for paper less services for example use of emails and websites for accounts information and notifications. However, it is not the case of every bank in Pakistan some banks are entirely not aware of the environmental policies. As indicated by one of the participants

who is working in top management in public bank in Pakistan that they don't have any environmental policies but it depends on individual if they prefer to use less paper. Some of the upper management person in public banks ask their personal assistants to print the email and highlight the specific points. These attitudes are common in Pakistan, in which educated and high level of management employee do not consider about environmental protection. It is the responsibility of educated employees and the management of an organisation to create awareness for the fortification of ecosystem for the well-being of the society.

5.6.7 Code no 3 : Size of an organisation.

Large organisation is another code derived from the interpretation of the interviews. This word is used by most participants. Large organisation also includes multinationals operating in Pakistan. It is pointed out by many participants that only big companies are aware of term corporate social responsibility and implementing in their way. Many multinationals operating in Pakistan are involve in CRS activities for example Coca cola is supporting Edhi foundation and some big textile organisations are providing health care for free. Participants discussed that organisations like Pakistan Steel also had some environmental policies. Nevertheless, small and medium size organisations are not aware of corporate social responsibility. It was also indicated by participant that even some big Pakistani organisations are not participating in any kind of CSR activity. Private banks are observed to be more into CSR practice instead of public banks in Pakistan. It is also mentioned by one of the participants that:

“it is the fact that most of the big or large banks are participating in CSR. I think small companies do not even understand it as the concept is not very popular.”

5.6.8 Code no 4 : Financial performance.

A number of participants accepted that banks in Pakistan are involve with CSR because they take it as a marketing tool that means banks consider CSR activities as an action of promoting and selling their products and services and increase financial performance. The promotion of societal activities can attract customers and investors because the bank with societal activities will be perceived as socially accountable. Participants articulated that some banks do not promote their societal activities. For example, few banks promote its activity related to the supporting a sports league but do not promote the charity or donation. Although, participants responses are according to their own knowledge. The researcher beliefs that it is not possible for the bank or a non-charitable organisation to avoid promoting their brand.

Moreover, it is crucial to mention that the researcher attained these data from the coding of the transcripts. As it is indicated in the following figure that financial performance is the item coded in all ten transcripts.

Figure 29 Financial Performance is Coded in all Transcripts.

Additionally, it is also indicated by participants in interviews that employees in the banks are often unaware of societal activities made by their organisation. Most of the workforce is ignorant from the notion of corporate social responsibility. One of the participants who works in upper management of a public bank articulated that employees are often unaware of societal activities made by bank and it is not appropriate to share all the activities with them because they would not feel contented. Moreover, most of employees working are from middle class family and would prefer to have a bonus or increment for their selves instead of social investment. It is the reality that an average employee might not comprehend the effectiveness of contribution to the society. However, it is the responsibility of an organisation to promote their activities internally and also make employees understand that how this investment is beneficial for the country.

Many participants pointed out the motive behind banks practicing CSR is brand reputation. Brand reputation means that customers are satisfied with the services of the company and would prefer to purchase product or services of the company again. If banks promote their societal activities by using traditional and modern way of advertisement, it will attract consumers and investors. The consumer and investors will perceive their bank as a socially responsible organisation. It is accepted by most of the participants that CSR activities have great impact on the brand reputation of an organisation.

5.6.9 Financial performance (Profit).

Profit making and long-term benefits are the ultimate goal of any business. Pakistani banks are also concern about their earnings per share and net profit. It is accepted by most of the participant that banks are participating in corporate social responsibility to attain long term benefit and profit. Some banks allocate specific amount of their profit to CSR activities. The direct relationship amongst CSR and profit is difficult to justify as indicated by participants but it has some impact on the profitability of the company. It is mentioned by one participant that

“the earning per share and net profit of our bank has increased in past few years but I don’t know if I can relate it directly to the CSR activities, for me it is difficult to directly relate profit to social activities”.

5.6.10 Code no 5 : Legal (Taxation).

Paying tax is one of the foremost responsibilities of an organisation. However, some organisations endeavour to avoid to fulfil this responsibility honestly. In Pakistan, some organisations are deceiving by showing receipt of the donations and charities which they never made, to avoid the taxation. It is unethical practice which some organisations are practicing in Pakistan as indicated by participants.

5.6.11 Government Pressure.

Participants pointed out the one of the crucial motives behind the companies practicing corporate social responsibility and that is government pressure. Most of the participant accept the fact that there is pressure from the government. State bank of Pakistan had introduced the guidelines which every bank has to follow. Moreover, it is articulated by participant that sometimes bank has to sponsor event because of authorities however, they don't have any particular policy on CSR. The situation of government is not very stable in Pakistan and it is difficult for the state to focus on every issue in the country. Every individual and every company should realise their accountability towards society and must contribute. Even small contribution can make big differences.

5.6.12 Code no 6: Ethical (Society and religion)

Society is a main part of any country and every society has different culture. The culture of Pakistan is unlike western countries. People are religious and emotional in the country. Topics like religion and politics are very sensitive in the country. Pakistan is an agricultural country and the level of education is relatively low. However, urban areas of the country are more towards education. The power distance is exceedingly high in Pakistan and most people are from middle class family. People are not aware with the notion of CSR and a large number of people consider CSR as customer services representative, as indicated by participants of the

research. Charities and donations are considered as a religious accountability. Whenever it comes to philanthropic activity, people will relate it to religion. Although, it must not be the case for organisations. Employees are normal people of the society and they make organisation as articulated by one of the participants. The researcher respects all the religions and belief that it can be one of the motives for an individual or an organisation to make donations but if its non-charitable organisation it may take profit or long-term benefits into account.

5.6.13 Code no 7 : Awareness

It is elucidated in above analysis that the level of CSR awareness is low in Pakistani organisations. Large organisations are participating in societal activities but small and medium size organisations are far behind. It is the responsibility of large organisations to create awareness amongst employees and other people to attain benefit as a whole.

5.6.14 Code no 8 : Employees and Customers.

Stakeholders are very important for an organisation. Many banks do consider stakeholders whilst making policies and taking decisions. But some of the big banks do not take stakeholders into account. As articulated by upper management employee of a public bank that it is common in the country to increase the rate or putting charges on specific services without prior notice to customers, which is extremely unethical. Additionally, many investors are interested in profit and do not have any apprehensions for societal activities. Banks should practice ethical activities and take it as a responsibility.

Interviewees indicated that their banks always focus on customers satisfaction and take customers complaints seriously. As mentioned by one of the managers that:

“we have different departments in our bank and give priority to customer services as it can impact the relationship of bank and our customers. Also, I as a manager always ensure that my team take customers complaints seriously and resolve it as soon as possible”.

Similarly, many participants agreed that their bank has employees related policies for example as one of the managers mentioned:

“our bank gives importance to employees, we have human resource section to manage all the concern related to employees. The bank gives rewards and health benefits to employees as health care is not free in Pakistan, it become one of the reasons to motivate employees by giving them these benefits. We also have employee’s welfare funds which includes pension schemes and we always mention these all things in financial statements of the bank.”

However, some of the participants indicated that making policies and strategies is the job of upper management and the bank do not include employees in decisions making.

5.7 Summary of the Chapter.

The chapter is about the result and analysis of the result. This chapter is divided into three sections. The first section showed the secondary data analysis in which it is elucidated that ROA, ROE, EPS and profit of banks have some relation with the investment of corporate social responsibilities. The second section is about quantitative data analysis which demonstrates the statistical analysis of the primary data attained through questionnaire. The results indicated the association between profit and encouragement of CSR. The last but not the least part is of qualitative data analysis which depicts the reality of Pakistani banks obtained by in-depth interviews of upper management employees of banks.

6 Chapter Six.

6.1 Discussion, Recommendation and Implementation.

6.2 Introduction.

This chapter of the research focus on the discussion on the obtained results from the primary and qualitative data analysis. The evaluation of documentation and in-depth interview of participants of Pakistani Banks were congregated into themes. The interpretation of the data and discussions on the results are made with the consideration of CSR literature presented in the study. The recommendations and implementations are also made on the basis of findings.

6.3 Research Findings.

The result has demonstrated that there is a positive relationship between corporate social responsibility and financial performance of any Pakistani bank. The motive behind practicing CSR varies with the bank's nature. However, the in-depth interviews reveal that there are CSR policies in annual reports but absence of awareness and their implementation.

In Pakistan, mostly large and private banks are participating in corporate social responsibility. When it comes to the association between training of CSR and employee satisfaction, the results showed that there is no connection amongst them. It is also analysed that employees are not ready to accept the change and banks are required to implement change management before creating awareness of CSR.

Moreover, managers in Pakistani banks have some knowledge about the notion of CSR. However, activities related to CSR are mostly considered as charity and environment protection. Some managers relate CSR with the brand reputation and religion. The organisations in Pakistan which are not practicing CSR have distinct reasons. In the end, the analysis of hypotheses shows that there is a positive relation between ROE, ROA and EPS with CSR. Further discussion on the findings are elucidated in following section.

6.3.1 Philanthropic Responsibility.

One of the main elements of CSR pyramid is philanthropic responsibilities. It is demonstrated by the finding obtain from the quantitative and quantitative analysis that many Pakistani banks are involve in philanthropic responsibilities. Banks are participating in social welfare programs and support different NGOs. There are various Pakistani banks which have allocated specific amount from budget to charities. There are different types of charitable activities in which Pakistani banks are participating for example donations to hospitals and charity to NGOs. Support for education, health projects and development in rural areas are other activities by Pakistani banks. In particular, it is evident that CSR in context of Pakistani banks are strategic in their approach and consider their philanthropic responsibility.

6.3.2 Ethical Responsibility.

The researcher considered employees, customers and environmental activities in ethical responsibilities. It is demonstrated in analysis that Pakistani banks are involved in employees related activities. Banks provide health care and rewards to their employees. Some banks also provide finances or loan to employees. The banks consider their ethical responsibility as a part of their CSR practice. Ethical responsibility means an organisation has to act morally. Good ethical and moral behaviour can enhance the trust of Pakistani banks. The results showed that Pakistani banks give priority to ethical responsibilities and consider it as a part of CSR. The challenge of ethical responsibilities is in establishing the limitations for the ethical practice. There are different practice or deeds of Pakistani banks and ethical acts considered are diverse. The results showed that Pakistani banks are fulfilling their ethical responsibilities. However, it was indicated in the literature of this research that some banks are lacking behind in complying their ethical accountabilities. Moreover, the issue of involvement of employees in CSR was also raised by some management members of the banks. It was indicated by managers of public banks in Pakistan that employees often do not adopt new strategies related to CSR. The researcher believes that banks should create awareness of CSR and about the advantages of CSR amongst employees.

6.3.3 Legal Responsibility.

The legal responsibility of banks is obligatory and it is ethical for an organisation to fulfil their legal responsibilities. According to Carroll (1991) it is essential for a firm to obey the rules and regulation of the country in which the firm operates. It is a half fulfilment of the agreement with the society that an organisation has to achieve their goals within the societal framework and within the law of the country. Pakistani banks perceive legal responsibilities as part of their policy. All banks pay their taxes in time and follow the rules and regulations of the state. However, the secondary data of the research revealed that the level of corruption in Pakistan is relatively higher. The researcher agrees with the fact that it is crucial for any organisation to work within the legal framework.

6.3.4 Economic Responsibility.

As an elemental necessity of existence any organisation has an economic accountability toward the society that allowed them to be originated and sustained. The only way for a firm to sustain is to be profitable and able to share their success amongst their shareholders. People perceive businesses as institutions which will produce and sell products and services to fulfil their requirements and desires (Carroll, 2016). Pakistani banks are generating profit and disclose their success in their annual reports. The researcher measures the financial performance of the banks by ROA, ROE, EPS and net profit of the banks.

The findings of the analysis demonstrated that there is a positive and significant association between CSR and financial performance of Pakistani banks. However, there are few facts about the country which cannot be disregarded by the researcher. The following section elucidates the reality or situation of Pakistan which will leads to the recommendation of the research.

6.4 Reality of Pakistan.

The Pakistani culture is entirely different from the Western Countries. It is found by previous researches that the people in Pakistan are usually from middle and lower middle-class families. Most of the population is struggling to maintain their status in the society. When a middle-class person works, mostly, his approach is restrained to his personal benefits. The concept of Corporate social responsibility is relatively new for many organisations in Pakistan and normal human being are not aware of such activities. Moreover, the education level is also low as more than eighty per cent population are farmers. Rural areas of Pakistan are still struggling to fulfil the basic needs of life and have no interest in organisational issues. Poverty can make human sensitive and emotional and therefore it is also the truth that Pakistani people are very emotional. The topic like religion and politics are very sensitive topics to discuss in the country. Many people think that organisations do charity work because of their religion.

Another aspect of the reality is the corruption in the country. It is possible, to find the financial statistics in the annual report of an organisation but not necessarily the truth. Some organisations counterfeit their documentation in front of the authorities to reduce the taxation. Apparently, a number of banks and large organisations are participating in activities relate to corporate social responsibility although it is doubtful that every fact in the annual report is spent by the company in reality.

Furthermore, pressure of government and authorities are one of the main elements or hindrances for the country to be a developed one. Sometimes, organisations have to support CSR or any other activity because of the pressure from the authorities. The above elucidated concerns of the country are only the foremost one by the author and it is the reality that CSR is growing. But the question arises that is it really growing or companies are doing it to complete the formality. If every large and medium size organisation in Pakistan, realise their social accountability and participate in CSR, it can bring huge difference to the development of the society.

6.5 Concerns related to CSR in Pakistani banks.

The above discussion from the research findings demonstrates that there are few issues in CSR in Pakistani banks. The purpose of this research was to find the current CSR practices in Pakistani retail banking sector and to investigate about CSR impact on CFP. The findings show that there is a positive impact of CSR on CFP, however, in the process of data gathering and evaluation the researcher have found few concerns in the current CSR practices of Pakistani banks. They have less focus on CSR as the outcomes of the results shows that banks mostly consider charity and sports as main CSR activities. Lack of awareness among employees and lack of acceptance of change are other issues. Most of Pakistani banks are using same activities of CSR and have less focus on developing a new strategy. Therefore, the researcher has made some recommendation and implementation of CSR for Pakistani banks which will eventually impact their reputation and financial performance.

The following figure illustrates the concerns of CSR in Pakistani banks, concluded from the findings of this research.

Table 20 Concerns of CSR in Pakistani Banks

(Author's work)

6.6 Recommendations.

This section of the study presents the recommendation by researcher to Pakistani banks. As CSR has become a global phenomenon with increasing acceptability amongst stakeholders. Banks have to consider stakeholders and should give priority to CSR. The participation in corporate social responsibility is not an obligation by state law in Pakistan but it can generate profit and therefore need to be included in organisational strategy of Pakistani banks. It is also recommended that the policy makers of Pakistani banks to ensure to make policies related to CSR and its disclosure which can not only increase finances or profit but will enhance the market value of the bank. The banks in Pakistan should have to divide sections and make four divisions. People, customers, shareholders and community. It is essential for any bank to consider these four before making any policy or taking any decision.

The researcher also supports stakeholder's theory and recommend banks to satisfy their stakeholders. The analysis in this investigation demonstrates that there is positive association between CSR and financial performance of Pakistani banks. However, employees in Pakistani banks has less awareness of CSR. The researcher recommends that banks should focus on change management before implementing new strategies. Moreover, CSR has different aspects which Pakistani banks can use in their business strategies to contribute in society and to generate increased financial performance.

6.7 Implementation of CSR.

In order to implement CSR in Pakistani banks, the management should consider six main tasks. It is essential for banks to develop the level of CSR for several reasons as discussed in the literature of the study. The researcher presents the following framework for CEOs, managers and employees of banks which will assists them to evaluate the bank's effects on society and the challenges and opportunities related with using these impacts in decision making. It is important for Pakistani banks to consider CSR activities as integral part of their organisational strategy as they are also the part of the society. If society will grow, the business will flourish. Therefore, the researcher of this study presents the following implementation framework for Pakistani banks.

Implementation framework

When? (Conceptual phase)	What? (Task delineation)	How? (Checkpoints on the journey)
Plan ↓	1. Conduct a CSR assessment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assemble a CSR leadership team; • Develop a working definition of CSR; • Identify legal requirements; • Review corporate documents, processes and activities, and internal capacity; and • Identify and engage key stakeholders.
	2. Develop a CSR strategy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Build support with CEO, senior management and employees; • Research what others are doing, and assess the value of recognised CSR instruments; • Prepare a matrix of proposed CSR actions; • Develop ideas for proceeding and the business case for them; and • Decide on direction, approach, boundaries and focus areas.
Do ↓	3. Develop CSR commitments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Do a scan of CSR commitments; • Hold discussions with major stakeholders; • Create a working group to develop the commitments; • Prepare a preliminary draft; and • Consult with affected stakeholders.
	4. Implement CSR commitments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop an integrated CSR decision-making structure; • Prepare and implement a CSR business plan; • Set measurable targets and identify performance measures; • Engage employees and others to whom CSR commitments apply; • Design and conduct CSR training; • Establish mechanisms for addressing problematic behaviour; • Create internal and external communications plans; and • Make commitments public.
Check ↓	5. Assure and report on progress	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Measure and assure performance; • Engage stakeholders; and • Report on performance, internally and externally.
Improve ↓	6. Evaluate and improve	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evaluate performance; • Identify opportunities for improvement; and • Engage stakeholders.
Cross-check: One cycle completed ←		Return to plan and start the next cycle.

Table 21 Implementation of CSR.

(Hohnen, 2007)

The above table demonstrates the implementation process of CSR for Pakistani banks. The first step is to conduct CSR assessment in their banks. CEOs and management of the banks should examine the current CSR activities that will provide the key CSR issues which can affect the bank's performances. The assessment should identify the main risks and opportunities that can impact on business decisions. Pakistani banks should assemble a CSR team to develop the CSR definition of bank and identify the legal requirements. It is also important for banks to identify and consider to engage stakeholders in CSR because they play an important role in enhancing CFP as demonstrated in literature review. However, this is important to consider this process in practical and current situation of banks. These questions may arise in these procedures will be of time, confident leader and cost or budget.

Figure 30 Concerns in assessing CSR.

(Author's work)

Considering the above demonstrated concerns, Pakistani banks then have to develop CSR strategy with the support of CEO and senior management of the banks. CSR strategy will be a road map for banks to overcome CSR issues and move forward. This will allow Pakistani banks to maintain long term CSR and that will impact the financial performances of banks in long

run. Its strategy should include the stakeholder’s perspectives, time line and responsible employees of banks to work on this. The banks will require support of management and employees to build strategy. It is essential for leadership team to build support amongst employees and in the process of CSR implementation. CSR managers are critical change agents, however, their role required to be acknowledged and strengthened if banks desire to turn out to be leaders in sustainability (Wickert & Bakker, 2019).

It is also important for Pakistani banks to consider few usual mistakes which can occurs in the process which are lack of vision, scale of change and risk and opportunities. One of the best ways to assess the value of recognised CSR in banks is to build a matrix which will provide ideas for proceeding and develop CSR in banks. The following table illustrates the example of matrix of proposed CSR which can be used by Pakistani banks.

Example of matrix of proposed CSR actions

	Environmental activity		Social activity (e.g., workers, communities)		Economic activity (e.g., quality assurance, customer satisfaction)	
	Current	Proposed	Current	Proposed	Current	Proposed
Processes	Registered to ISO 14001*	Kyoto emission reductions?	Certified to OHSAS*	SA8000* or Fair Labor Association (FLA)	Registered to ISO 9001*	Integrated management systems (IMS)?
Products/ services	Some products use known logo (e.g., Rainforest Alliance, Organic)	Could products be certified to local energy standard?	None at present	Possible SA 8000 or FLA product certification	Use of ISO 9001 logo on company letterhead	Keep abreast of ISO work on IMS?
Impacts	Internal impact assessment undertaken	Supply chain/ community impacts?	Internal impact assessment undertaken	Supply chain/ community impacts?	Internal impact assessment undertaken	Supply chain/ community impacts?
Responsibility centre	Environmental affairs department		Human resources department		Manager, quality/ customer satisfaction	

Table 22 Example of Matrix of Proposed CSR.

(Hohnen, 2007)

Determining the priorities and before developing CSR strategy is very crucial for Pakistani banks. Additionally, it is essential to ensure that the CSR strategy should linked or developed

according to the mission and vision of the bank. As it was demonstrated in the results of the research that employees of the banks do not get excited about CSR, therefore it is important for upper management to show them that how it can enhance the financial performance and will be beneficial for bank in long term. Banks should develop CSR commitment which flows from the CSR strategies of the banks which will provide guidance to employees that how should they implement on them. They need to scan their CSR commitment and discuss it with their major stakeholders and then create a working group to develop these commitments. Revision of CSR commitments and publishing of them are also important for the development of CSR. Pakistani banks should set CSR targets for development of CSR but these targets have to be SMART (simple, measurable, achievable, reliable and time-bound).

Engagement of employees in CSR commitments is also essential for Pakistani banks as they play central role in CSR implementation. Banks can engage their employees through CSR in three different ways a transactional approach, where programs are undertaken to meet the requirements of employees who want to participate in the CSR activities; a relational approach, established on a psychological agreement that give emphasis to societal accountabilities; and a developmental approach, that intends to initiate societal accountabilities in a firm and to improve its employees to be responsible corporate citizens (Mirvis, 2012).

Employees can bring new ideas and their commitment to CSR can lead to the progress of the bank. Banks should design and conduct CSR training for employees or daily workshop can be also reduce the cost of training. Pakistani banks need to train their employees to get directly involved in CSR activities. Evaluation can track the progress of CSR approach and activities in Pakistani banks. Managers can create spread sheets to track the evaluation from year to year.

The above-mention discussion is about the CSR implementation which Pakistani bank can adopt to develop CSR. Moreover, the following section is based on the proposed strategy for banks to deal with the current CSR issue as concluded earlier from the research outcomes.

6.8 Proposed Strategy for Pakistani Banks.

In order to create develop CSR in Pakistani banks and propose strategy, the researcher has started from value creation. Blue Strategy model is used to create value; however, it is to consider that completing this grid of ERRC is challenging and this is based on the findings of the research. In practical, management of banks should consider different factors (Kim & Mauborgne, 2015). Based on the outcomes of the investigation, the researcher has constructed the following value creation for the development of CSR in Pakistani banking sector.

Eliminate: The communicational gap amongst stakeholders
Raise: Awareness of CSR through training, workshops and daily briefs.
Reduce: Conventional style of CSR and issues related to CSR.
Create: Innovation ideas for CSR.

Table 23 Value Creation

(Author's work)

Moreover, the researcher has proposed strategy for banks in Pakistan in this section of the research. As indicated in the findings that employees of the banks are less aware of the concept of CSR and do not feel contented with new strategies. If the employees of bank are not satisfied with the strategies, it can impact their performance. Therefore, it is essential for Pakistani banks to create awareness of CSR and its advantages amongst employees through training and workshops. The banks should use change management as a strategy before introducing new strategies. The researcher believes that CSR can assist society to resolve issues and internal promotion of banks CSR activities can motivate employees as well. It is also an ethical responsibility of banks to involve stakeholders by informing them about the development and activities of CSR. It will be beneficial for banks to measure CSR to developed it and help society. The following table demonstrates the proposed strategy for Pakistani banks.

Proposed Strategy for Banks in Pakistan
Create Awareness of CSR Slowly
Change management
Help Society
Internal promotions
Involve Stakeholders
Evaluate it
Share the Success

Table 24 Proposed Strategy for Banks.

The above table demonstrates the proposed strategy for Pakistani banks. However, this is the proposal by researcher, it also depends on the organisational structure, strategies and most importantly the weight average cost of capital (WACC) of the bank which can vary from one bank to another. It is crucial to mention at this point that it is difficult to measure CSR, some of the techniques to evaluate CSR is elucidated in appendix 9.4.

These strategies will be beneficial for Pakistani banks and they have to implement it step by step with the consideration of their organisational vision and mission. The following discussion is about the process or steps of the above proposed strategy; however, the researcher believes that to include the detail following one is the most important for Pakistani banks as it showed in the results of the research there is a lack of acceptance of change.

6.8.1.1 Change Management.

The findings of the investigation demonstrated that Pakistani banks have CSR policies and they are participating in societal activities. However, there is an issue of awareness of CSR among employees of banks. Therefore, the researcher is recommending Pakistani banks change management strategy. This investigation included perception of manager about CSR because researcher realised that in order to implement any strategy, the bank has to ensure high level of

managerial and leadership skills. Any planned strategy of banks can become unsuccessful because of lack of framework for managing change. Pakistani banks have to make sure the following key points when implementing new strategies.

The top management has to get involve in the process of managing change and they have to engage employees of Pakistani banks with systematic planning. Managers role is essential in motivating employees for the change. The banks have to communicate change with their employees. If they have new strategy related to CSR, it is crucial it to communicate it to employees. The researcher beliefs that transparency in organisation can result in employees' motivation and satisfaction which will lead to increase financial performance. The following table shows the strategy to implement change Pakistani banks which is adopted from Kurt Lewin change model (Burnes, 2004).

Unfreezing:

This stage is the first and very essential stage. Pakistani banks have to make certain that all employees comprehend the significance of change and make their selves ready to move to the fore and to leaves the comfort zone. Before introducing new strategy of CSR, management has to ensure that employees are aware of the importance of new CSR strategy.

• Change:

In next phase, the Pakistani banks have to implement changes. However, Change is not rapid and this will be a procedure which will be complicated. Therefore, banks have to give training and coaching to encourage and motivate employees. It will be beneficial to make communication open and eliminate the communication gap between management and employees. Daily briefs can be cost effective way to do discussion with employees.

Refreezing:

In last stage, banks have to determine stability of change that is refreeze it. It is always important to measure the CSR development by using change strategy on regular basis.

Figure 31 Kurt Lewin Change model

(Burnes, 2004).

Moreover, the process and method of implementing change in any organisation is complex and Pakistani banks have to manage or deal with the resistance to change. Kurt Lewin's change model appears to be simple however, banks have ensured good leadership to manage change and motivate employees. The banks can also adopt the following steps presented by Kotter in 1995 (Kotter, 2012).

Steps to implement Change

In the real situation of Pakistani banks, the above-mention model may be advantageous, however it is always challenging to change the perception of employees and culture of the bank. Therefore, the researcher has presented the eight steps of implementing change by as shown in the following figure.

Figure 32 Eight steps to Implement Change

(Kotter, 2012)

Figure redacted for copyright reasons

1. **Create Urgency:** Pakistani banks have to create urgency and also create open communication amongst employees. It is important for employees to understand the need of change in CSR strategy.
2. **Form a Powerful Coalition:** Banks have to convince employees that change is necessary and can impact financial performance of the company. It is necessary to find potential leaders and assign tasks. Leaders can motivate and support employees and can help in the implementation process.
3. **Create a Vision for Change:** Banks have to make sure that the vision of change is clear to all employees that can provide proper assistance and direction to all employees. Managers should determine the value for change and provide summary to all employees.
4. **Communicate the Vision:** the management has to make sure that there is strong internal communication. It is crucial to communicate the vision amongst employees. Daily briefs and workshop are useful ways to reduce communication gap.
5. **Remove Obstacles:** another important step in implementation of change is that management has to recognise the factors of resistance to change. The leader or manager of the bank has to remove barriers and it is also important to encourage employees to make change occur.
6. **Create Short-Term Wins:** Pakistani banks should create short-term targets to make it achievable. And when it is achieved the management should give rewards to employees for their hard work and consistency.
7. **Build on the Change:** real change runs deep thus the Pakistani banks have to take hold of every opportunity from each success. It is crucial to consider continues progress and always generate new ideas and emphasis on long-term change.

8. **Anchor the Changes in Corporate Culture:** the change has to be a part of the culture of Pakistani banks. The banks have to make constant determination to make sure that change has been seen by all departments of the banks. The managers of the bank always have to support change for the long-term growth.

6.9 Summary of the Chapter.

The outcomes of the research have shown that there is a positive relationship between CSR and CFP. The researcher has used CSR pyramid to construct the framework and results has demonstrated that in Pakistani banks the main activity of CSR is philanthropy. Pakistani banks mostly participate in social welfare programs and support NGOs. Additionally, banks provide importance to ethical and legal responsibilities. They pay all the taxes but there is some corruption in the system. Moreover, the results demonstrate that there are few concerns with CSR in Pakistani banks. These issues include lack of awareness of CSR amongst employees, lack of acceptance of change and lack of development in new CSR strategy. Therefore, this chapter included the recommendation and implementation for Pakistani banks. The researcher has presented the process of CSR and eight steps to implement change. However, this recommendation and implementation is on the basis of outcomes of the research (which is conducted in limited time). Thus, banks have to consider different factors to implement on these strategies like time, cost, budget and most importantly vision and mission of the company.

7 Chapter Seven.

7.1 Conclusion and Limitations and Reflection.

This section of the research presents the theoretical contribution of the knowledge, implication of the investigation, limitation and future research directions. The structure of this chapter has two principles indicated by Trafford and Leshem (2008) by cross-linking between the beginning and the end of the study, and proposing conclusions from the particular or descriptive through to the general and conceptual. The researcher has connected the research purpose with research outcomes and in the end of this section the conclusion of the investigation is elucidated. The first section is about the summary of the research followed by theoretical perception and limitation of the study. Moreover, the researcher has presented reflection of the process and conclusion in this chapter.

7.2 Summary of the Research.

The research has presented comprehensive discussion on CSR and its impact on CFP. The purpose of this research was to investigate about the current CSR practice and its impact on financial performance of Pakistani retail banking sector. The aim researcher used CSR pyramid model presented by Carroll (1991) to construct a framework. A number of organisations in developing countries are practicing corporate social responsibility, however, the concept of CSR is relatively new in developing countries particularly Pakistan.

Therefore, this research was taken for both practical and theoretical purposes. Many researchers have investigated about the relationship of CSR and CFP but there are only few studies and less literature about emerging countries. Theoretically, this research filled the gap in knowledge related to the association amongst CSR and CFP in context of Pakistan. Moreover, this investigation has practical implication for banking sector and it can be beneficial for any other management to gain competitive advantage by adopting CSR with increasing knowledge of CSR from this study.

The literature review discussed the background of the country and CSR definition with its evolution. It is also comprising of CSR theories and the current situation of CSR in developing countries and Pakistani retail banking sector. The research framework and hypotheses of the research was developed on the base of CSR pyramid (Carroll, 1991). Each element of the pyramid was tested and then associated with the financial performance of Pakistani banks. The

researcher has divided these responsibilities in little sub-divisions. As illustrated in chapter 3 that has included stakeholders in the pyramid which are employees and customers.

In order to achieve the research objectives, the researcher has selected the appropriate research methodology. The research methodology chapter includes research paradigm and philosophies used in this study. The chapter proposed the methodology and the justification for chosen methodology. It also provided the reasons for selection of post-positivist paradigm. It also justifies the use of mixed methods which are qualitative and quantitative approaches. It also explained the use of convergent design and sampling method and issues. The researcher selected stratified sampling. To attain quantitative data the researcher used surveys and for qualitative, the researcher selected structured interviews. Before collection of survey, the questionnaire was tested through pilot test. Moreover, it also includes the validity and reliability test of qualitative and quantitative data.

In chapter 5, the collected quantitative and qualitative data were tested through statistical analysis. The researcher used frequencies to analyse the demographic data of participants and correlation test to evaluate the relation of CSR and CFP. Additionally, qualitative data was analysed by using NVivo and thematic approach. The results support the view that Pakistani banks are practicing CSR but they should consider more involvement in it. Corporate social responsibility strategies can improve the productivity and creativity of workers resulting in improved financial performance. Hence, the researcher has achieved the objective of this research and also have found some concern in CSR in Pakistani banks and made some recommendation and implementations. Hence, the research question of this investigation was answered in the following: The investigation has found that there is a positive relationship amongst corporate social responsibility and financial performance of Pakistani retail banks.

However, the researcher has found that there are some issues in CSR in Pakistani banks which includes lack of awareness of CSR, development of CSR and lack of acceptance to change. Therefore, the researcher has made some recommendation and implementation for CSR strategy which also included the steps to implement change. The management of the bank has to consider different factors like cost, time and vision and mission of the company before implementing the presented recommendations.

7.3 Theoretical Contribution to Knowledge.

This section of the research presents the elemental contribution to knowledge of the study on CSR practice by banks in emerging country. The investigation established the notion of CSR in Pakistani context and associated the CSR pyramid by Carroll (1991) to Pakistani banks. The concept of CSR is growing and thus possibly will modify in future. The study suggested the elements of CSR are related to stakeholders and the pyramid of CSR is integrated and unified whole. The researcher constructed conceptual framework inspired by Carroll (1991), but included sub elements of the four-basic component of pyramid.

A business behaviour is considered as socially responsible when they fulfil their economic responsibility and generates profit, be ethical with following all the rules and regulations of the state and support society Carroll (1991). This model was constructed in context of developed country by Carroll (1991). However, this investigation is about Pakistan which is an emerging country. The study demonstrated that economic growth and financial performance of Pakistani banks are associated with each other. There are different CSR activities in which banks are participating but mostly the main support to society by banks was through philanthropic activities. Additionally, the researcher believes that in CSR pyramid there is a requirement of section of 'culture'. Which has great impact on each element or every responsibility. The following figure illustrates the proposed model of CSR.

Figure 33 Culture have impact on CSR pyramid

(Author's work)

7.4 Implications of Research.

The analysis and findings of the research about the Pakistani banks suggests wide-ranging CSR involvements and activities ranging from philanthropic responsibilities to society progress projects. These projects comprise of different sectors like education, health, sports and art. In the study it was indicated that the impact of CSR on financial performance of Pakistani retail banks, however there is no evident indicator to gauge on societal affect and direct financial involvement or contributions. There was also implication for managers related to CSR practice in banks. The management of banks have opportunity to comply with the strategies and contributions of CSR mentioned in research which can lead to the long-term benefits. Currently, most of the managers participated have some knowledge of the concept of CSR and it can enhance the expertise with this particular research.

7.5 Limitation and Future Research Directions.

The investigation has developed in particular area and there are some limitations of research findings. The outcomes of this study have shortcomings which are addressed in this section with the suggestion of future research.

The focus of this investigation is on financial sector which is retail banks of Pakistan. Further research can be conducted in different sectors in Pakistan like oil industry or textile industry. The results of this investigation are established on restricted data for limited time frame. More, valid and detailed data can be attained if the future research contained longitudinal approach of research. The data of this research is relevant for CSR which is limited to the developing country. Different developing countries have diverse challenges and culture and this study belongs to Pakistan and the researcher cannot make assumption that the results are applicable across all emerging countries. This investigation was related to financial performance of CSR and it did not present the detail CSR concerns. Corporate social responsibility also depends on the size of an organisation. Therefore, future research can conduct to investigate the relationship of CSR and size of the firm.

7.6 Reflection.

This section of the study is about the researcher and the development of the researcher, in context of thinking. It includes the analysis of the activities which the researcher has faced in completing the research. Learning which the researcher has achieved become the cause of change in personality and enhanced skills of the researcher. This investigation was the main project for DBA programme which provided the researcher an opportunity to explore about the CSR. Doctoral students can spend many years in completing their research and the relationship of a supervisor and candidate plays fundamental role. The relationship of the researcher of the study with her director of studies was positive and had improved over time. The researcher has achieved a great deal of learning through conversation with the director of studies. In every meeting the researcher left his office feeling affirmed and respected for the knowledge. The director of studies style was empowering and intellectually supportive.

The researcher had personal interest in the topic and this research has given her an opportunity to investigate about CSR in Pakistani banks. The researcher has felt that there is a need to change the way of thinking about CSR and attitude of people in Pakistan particularly in banking sector. The researcher was exploring about the topic which is near to her as one of the thinking behind the investigation was to demonstrate people of Pakistan that CSR in every organisation can change the society. The researcher was emotionally attached and involved with the topic of the study.

Moreover, different skills have achieved while working on this project. In order to explain the forms and level of learning achieved from this research, it will be appropriate to use a model known as 'bloom's taxonomy' which was presented by Benjamin Bloom (1956). It is a concept to create a classification of cognitive skills (Adams, 2015). The model comprises six categories of cognitive skills from lower-order skills to high degree skills. The first step of this model is knowledge, which is the initial cognitive skill and indicates to the remembering of particular piece of information. The researcher started recognising and recalling the provided information and tried to collect or gathering information about the CSR. This was the start of the project in which the main focus was clarification of the concept of CSR specifically in Pakistani banks. The second phase was of comprehension of the concept and the researcher started summarizing the notion and stated building research question with aims and objectives. The researcher has

classified similar items into a group and started comparing and contrasting at this stage. It is more than remembering as it requires more cognitive processing and the researcher began to combine knowledge into the existing understanding. This provided an opportunity to use knowledge and skills in new paradigm. And that is the next level of the model, application. In which the researcher started application of knowledge to existing cognitive outlines. The following level in the model is of analysis. the researcher started thinking critically at this stage. The researcher identified the aspects and procedure and methodology which was essential for the investigation. Then the researcher assesses different elements and ensure the measure of the requirements. Synthesis is the next stage in which the researcher has created a new product in term of study. The final one is evaluation that is also related to critical thinking of the researcher. Different or novel structure was created for CSR in Pakistani banks. The recommendation and implementation were made for the development of CSR in Pakistani banks.

Additionally, in the process of this investigation, there were different barriers and challenges confronted by the researcher. It includes process of data collection, time and cost of the study. As a researcher, there was an ethical responsibility towards all the participants, therefore the researcher had to pay attention to the specific ethical principle for investigation. One of the main concerns when collecting primary data is ethical issues. In the relationship with the participants, it is to be expected that the issues with the power come into attention and requires continuous inspection. The researcher interrogates her own position, perception and behaviour to avoid to be in state of power. The researcher was clear and provided relevant information about the investigation at the early stage of negotiation. The researcher has shared the power to discuss the form and content of the communication with participants. Moreover, as a full-time academic the life of researcher was divided in research, administration, attendance, meetings and most importantly funding. The long process of the investigation sometime became cause behind the anxiety and depression for the researcher. However, the researcher managed to overcome all the challenges and has complete the project efficiently.

When the researcher of the study looks back from where she is today, the stage of the process unfolded and the researcher can make sense of her experiences in different way. The researcher has developed her cognitive, management, problem solving, analytical and critical skills. Reflecting on different aspect whilst this investigation, this researcher has great impact on her personal and professional growth.

7.7 Conclusion.

CSR is popular practice by organisations in developed countries however, the notion is relatively new in emerging countries. This investigation is about the impact of corporate social responsibility and its impact on financial performance of Pakistani retail banks. The purpose of the study is to explore the current practice of CSR and the relationship of CSR with financial performance of Pakistani banks. The research is based on critical evaluation of literature of CSR and statistical analysis of the findings. Corporate social responsibility has four distinct elements include philanthropic, ethical, legal, and economic responsibilities (Carroll, 1991).it is suggested that it is essential for a firm to create balance amongst these responsibilities. (Harzing & Pinnington , 2015). Many companies invest in CSR activities which comprise charity and donations to enhance the value of stakeholders (Lee, et al., 2018).

There are different definitions of CSR which are elucidated in literature of this study. For instance, social impact hypothesis which supports the concept a firm has to fulfil the expectations of stakeholders which can have positive impact on the market share of a firm. (Cornell & Shapiro, 1987). Some of the scholars indicated the positive relationship of CSR and financial performance while some supported negative association. There are few scholars that supported the u-shaped relationship amongst CSR and FP. In this particular research the conceptual framework was built by researcher based on Carroll's (1991) pyramid of CSR.

The notion of CSR is relatively new in Pakistan, although the fascination toward activities related to CSR are increasing. Many organisations pay no attention to CSR activities. There are different reasons behind lack of participation in CSR. One of the most indicated reasons in this research was deficiency of awareness of the notion. However, this investigation is about the relationship of CSR with FP in Pakistani banks. The researcher used mixed method and stratified sampling in this investigation. The findings were obtained by using statistical analysis.

It is indicated in the finding that Pakistani banks are participating in activities related to CSR. However, the implementation of level CSR implementation is not very high in all banks. The results showed that there is a positive correlation between CSR and FP. The limitation of the study is that it is in context of Pakistan only and the researcher cannot assume the same finding

in different context. The detail investigation on relationship of size of the firm and CSR and about the reason behind lack of CSR practice can be suggested for future research.

Moreover, the research has found some concerns related to CSR activities in Pakistani retail banking sector. Therefore, the researcher has included recommendation and the process of implementation. It was found that Pakistani banks has old strategy for CSR and have less development in CSR. Employees of banks are less aware of the notion of CSR and it is very difficult to implement change in the banks. The management of the banks have to implement change management process and make sure that every one understands the importance of development in CSR and new change strategy. Additionally, the researcher has also proposed theoretical framework for CSR pyramid, in which the fundamental base of the pyramid is culture. Ay organisation has to consider cultural beliefs, norms and values before focusing on CSR pyramid.

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9 Appendices.

9.1 Questionnaire.

In last few decade, the corporate social responsibility (CSR) has become one of the dominant themes in developing countries. Many firms in Pakistan are also using CSR as fundamental organisational strategy to retain customers and increase financial performance. The purpose of this study is to explore the current CSR activities in Pakistani Banks and its impact on financial performance.

I am grateful to you for your participation and taking time out for completing the survey. All responses are confidential, voluntary and only for the academic research purpose. There are no correct or incorrect answers and the researcher will evaluate all responses as a group.

Thanking You for participating in survey

Researcher

The following figure illustrates the CSR pyramid presented by Carroll, (1991)

Figure 1: The Pyramid of Corporate Social Responsibility (Carroll, 1991b)

Figure redacted for copyright reasons

Section 1

Please indicate the level of your agreement with each of the following statements on the scale of 1 Strongly disagree to 5 Strongly Agree

MY BANK:

	SD	D	N	A	SA
Philanthropy					
Provides funding scholarship programs or activities					
Sponsors public health projects					
Provides Donations of cash, products, or employee services to support community activities, events, arts, sports					
Sponsors education conference, seminar, workshop or art exhibits Aiding disaster victims					
Supports and encourages the development of rural areas of the country					
Ethical					
Employees Related					
Gives rewards to employees					
Provides health care for the employees including health assistance, maternity leave					
Provides finance or loan to the employees for their higher education					
Provides Employees training					
Complies with health and safety standards and regulations					
Provides better working environment to employees					
Has rules related to employee discrimination					

Environmental					
Has environmental policies					
Gives importance to pollution reduction					
Believes in conservation of natural resources (energy conservation)					
Efficiency in waste management.					
Engaged in eco-friendly products					

Customers.					
Responds to the customer's complaints in a satisfactory manner					
Has ethical standards and policies related to advising of the product and services					
Provides Clear and accurate information to customers					
Legal					
Pays all the taxes on time.					
Is Complying with various federal, state, and local regulations.					
Providing goods and services that at least meet minimal legal requirements.					
Is Performing in a manner consistent with expectations of government and law.					

- Please rate from 1 to 5 scales, where 1 is Well Below Average and 5 is Well above average

Economical	WBA	BA	A	AA	WAA
Net profit of your bank in previous five years was					
EPS of my bank in previous five years was					
ROA of my bank in previous five years was					
ROE of my bank in previous five years was					

Section 2

Manager's Perception

What is the meaning corporate social responsibility for you?

- Contributing in societal activities
- Generating value for stakeholders
- Paying Taxes
- Providing good customer services
- Abiding the laws of the state
- Providing safe and pleasant working environment

Different organisation practice CSR for different purpose, in your opinion what is the reason behind enhancing societal activities?

- Innovation
- Government pressure
- Cost saving
- Suppliers' relations
- Increase Sales
- Consumer's satisfaction
- Investors' attention
- Competitive advantage

Does your organisation practice any one of these societal activities?

- Charity
- Health and Safety
- Protection of law
- Environmental activities
- Employees training
- Scholarship to students

In your opinion which is the reason behind the lack of CSR in a firm.

- Expense
- Lack of interest
- Lack of awareness of CSR

In your opinion corporate social responsibility activities can

- Promotes long-term profit
- Attract investors
- Sustain customers

Please specify the profile of company that you are representing:

- Public Sector bank
- Private Sector bank

What is your current position in this organisation?

- Operation
- Supervisor
- Manager
- Senior Manager
- General Manager
- Director/MD/CEO/Vice President

In which primary division do you work?

- Customer services
- Treasury Management
- Marketing
- Human resources
- Information technology / systems
- Revenue management
- Sales and marketing

- Other

Do you agree that CSR activities can increase profit of bank?

- Yes
- No
- Not sure

What is the size of your company?

- Small
- Medium
- Large

What is the highest education you have held?

- High School
- College
- Bachelor's degree
- Master's degree
- Doctoral degree
- Other:

Thank you for your participation.

9.2 Interview Questions.

1. What is your management level?
2. What is the Profile of your bank (Private or Public)?
3. What is the size of your bank
4. What was the net profit of your bank in previous five years?
5. Does your bank have CSR policy?
6. Do you have CSR policy in your banks?
7. How your bank is participating in CSR?
8. How would you describe CSR and its importance related to economical, legal ethical and philanthropic responsibilities?
9. Who is responsible for developing your CSR in your bank?
10. How does the CSR agenda fit in/align with your corporate strategy?
11. How does your bank deal with employees and customers?
12. Does your bank give rewards to employees?
13. Do you have employee engagement in your bank and do you think it is a part of CSR?
14. Does your bank focus on providing good working environment and do you have transparency in your bank?
15. How does your bank deal with customers complaints?
16. How does your bank deal with legal responsibilities?
17. Does your bank provide student loans and donations?
18. How does your bank deal with environmental policies?
19. Do you think, is there any relationship between CSR and financial performance?
20. Anything else would you like to mention about CSR and financial performance.

9.3 Stakeholders and their expectation on an organisation.

Stakeholder	Expectations on the company
Owners and Investors	Profit Transparency Growth in enterprise value
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Customers • • 	Quality products and services Reasonable price After-sales service
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Business Partners • 	Quality contracts and negotiations Timely fulfillment of obligations
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Employee benefits for their work • • • 	Reasonable salary and non-wage Good working conditions Professional growth and education Reconciling personal and professional life
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Local Community • 	Financial or material support Know-how of corporate volunteers
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Environmental Non-Profit Organization and services • 	Ecological production of products Minimum burden on the environment

9.4 How to measure CSR.

Figure redacted for copyright reasons